

Development of a One Health conceptual framework for socio-ecological systems

One Health Observatory Lighthouse HOBE Project Technical Report

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Introduction

The One Health **Observatory Lighthouse** – HOBE (“better” in the Basque language) project is being carried out in the Bay of Plentzia, the Butroe River that flows into it, and all its watershed. It is implemented by the Plentzia Marine Station (PiE, by its acronym in the Basque language) and by the Basque Center for Climate Change (BC3). The HOBE project aims to understand how climate change modifies the impacts of coastal pathogens on human, animal, and ecosystem health using a One Health perspective.

The objectives of subproject 2 of the HOBE project (lead by BC3) aim: (i) to develop a conceptual framework which could assist the analysis of the case study area from a watershed perspective in order to understand the interconnections among multiple factors and pressures, such as environmental contamination, climate change and socio-economic activities in the coastal-marine landscape, and (ii) to support the construction of a pilot One Health Living Lab, aiming at encouraging collaboration among local agents in the case study area, and supporting multidimensional analysis, collaboration, and research to provide increased evidence of pollution, climate change, and other impacts from the One Health approach and the watershed perspectives. This deliverable presents and discusses the first objective and the results obtained. Divided into three sections: 1. Conceptual framework for One Health in a socio-ecological system, 2. Pressures that affect the health of Northern Spain's Coastal-Land Socio-Ecological Systems and 3. Case study: Transition of the Butroe River and Bay of Plentzia.

The One Health High-Level Expert Panel (OHHLEP et al., 2022) defines One Health as “**an integrated, unifying approach that aims to sustainably balance and optimise the health of people, animals, and ecosystems and requires mobilising multiple sectors, disciplines, and communities to overcome threats to health and ecosystems. It recognises that the health of humans, domestic and wild animals, plants, and the wider environment (including ecosystems) are closely linked and interdependent**”. The principles on which it is based are (1) equity between sectors and disciplines, (2) socio-political and multicultural parity, (3) socio-ecological equilibrium, (4) stewardship and the responsibility of humans to change behaviour and adopt sustainable solutions and (5) transdisciplinary and multisectoral collaboration (OHHLEP et al., 2022).

One Health toward a sustainable healthy future as developed by the OHHLEP (2022)

Convergences and divergences of the “One Health” approach

The understanding that humans and other animals live on the same planet and share the same environment has led over the last half of the century to the emergence of new ways of addressing health, both in its physical and mental components (Lerner & Berg, 2017). Nowadays, some of the most influential approaches, characterised by their holistic and interdisciplinary perspective, are One Health, EcoHealth and Planetary Health (Lerner & Berg, 2017). They acknowledge the interconnectedness between living organisms’ health and the supporting environments and ecosystems, comprehensively recognising the complexity of human-natural systems interactions at different levels (Duboz et al., 2018). However, each of these approaches has arisen from different origins and, to date, maintains its particular nuances (Buse et al., 2018; Lerner & Berg, 2017).

Holistic health approaches

One Health (OHHLEP, 2022, p.2)

“One Health is an **integrated**, unifying approach that aims to **sustainably balance and optimise the health of people, animals, and ecosystems**. It recognises the **health of humans, domestic and wild animals, plants, and the wider environment (including ecosystems) are closely linked and interdependent.**”

Ecohealth (Charron, 2012, p. 6)

“Ecohealth research formally connects ideas of **environmental and social determinants of health** with those of **ecology and systems thinking** in an action-research framework applied mostly within social and economic development context. Ecosystem approaches to health focus on the interactions between the **ecological and socioeconomic dimensions** of a given situation, their influence on human health, **how people use or impact ecosystems, the implications for the quality of ecosystems, the provision of ecosystem services, and sustainability.**”

Planetary health (Whitmee et al., 2015, p.1978)

“Our definition of planetary health is the achievement of the highest attainable standard of health, wellbeing, and equity **worldwide** through judicious attention to the **human systems – political, economic and social** – that shape the future of humanity and the **Earth’s natural systems that define the safe environmental limits** within which humanity can flourish.”

Field development	Time of emergence	Fundamental principles
One Health (OHHLEP et al., 2022)	Mid-late 20 th , although it gained predominance in the early 21 st .	(1) Equity, (2) Socio-political and multicultural party, (3) socioecological equilibrium, (4) Stewardship, (5) Transdisciplinarity.
Ecohealth (Charron, 2012)	Late 20 th .	(1) System thinking, (2) Transdisciplinary research, (3) Stakeholder participation, (4) Sustainability, (5) Gender and social equity, (6) Knowledge to action.
Planetary Health (Lerner & Berg, 2017)	Early 21 st .	(1) Health at the individual, community and population scale, (2) Equity, and (3) Sustainability for humans.

One Health (OH) emerged in the 20th century from the “One Medicine” concept in the 1960s, with a biomedical focus on combining human and veterinary medicine (Lerner & Berg, 2017). In the 2000s, it became popular after significant crises of severe acute respiratory syndrome and avian influenza epidemics (Buse et al., 2018). Still, recently, it has been criticised by many for its emphasis on human-animal interactions and its focus on zoonotic diseases, food safety and antimicrobial resistance (Buse et al., 2018; De Castañeda et al., 2023; Rabinowitz et al., 2018). Others have suggested the concept of One Health as an entanglement of the human, non-human and environmental spheres rather than an overlapping of spaces (Davis & Sharp, 2020).

The One Health approach was redefined after the COVID-19 pandemic in 2022, including the importance of environment/ecosystem health, adopting fundamental principles from social sciences and becoming, in a joint effort under the multidisciplinary One Health High-Level Expert Panel (OHHLEP)¹, closer to the Ecohealth approach, as other authors already had suggested (Harrison et al., 2019; Rabinowitz et al., 2018; Zinsstag, 2012)

Ecohealth emerged from the “ecosystem health” concept in the late 20th century and was based on the systems’ organisation, productivity, based on the systems’ organisation, productivity and resilience (Rapport et al., 1999). It evolved from there, adding the social and political dynamics, to adopt a socio-ecological approach to health (Buse et al., 2018; Lerner & Berg, 2017) based on six principles: systems thinking, transdisciplinary, stakeholder participation, sustainability, gender and social equity, and knowledge to action (Charron, 2012).

Ecohealth differs from One Health because it attributes health to aggregations, systems, and processes rather than individuals (Lerner & Berg, 2017). For example, humans are not only parts of a whole ecosystem, along with other non-human organisms, but the human body is also understood as an ecological community-holobiont – consisting of the human as a host and its microbiome (Prescott et al., 2018). This approach has mainly been used in socio-ecological challenges but not so much in public health (Duboz et al., 2018).

The Rockefeller Foundation-Lancet Commission has developed the Planetary Health approach as an alternative to the previous two (Whitmee et al., 2015). According to Lerner and Berg (2017), in this approach, humans are given significant consideration, while the surrounding environment and organisms are seen only as a supportive system on which humans depend, without recognising the intrinsic values of the ecological systems or the value of animal welfare for the animal’s own sake. Planetary health research has been more focused on issues related to climate change and social determinants of health (De Castañeda et al., 2023) at all social levels (personal, community, national, regional, global and planetary), but especially from a human perspective (Buse et al., 2017).

HOBE Project perspective

One of the HOBE project's initial assumptions is adopting the One Health approach using the OHHLEP (2022) definition. The most recent definition incorporates new elements and integrates aspects that Ecohealth and Planetary Health definitions should have considered. This new concept of One Health represents a holistic approach designed to achieve a sustainable equilibrium in the health of humans, animals, and ecosystems by acknowledging their interconnected and interdependent nature (OHHLEP et al., 2022). Although not specified in its definition, the importance of socio-political and multicultural aspects, as well as of socio-ecological systems, stewardship and transdisciplinary, are included in its fundamental principles (principles shared with Ecohealth).

¹ <https://www.who.int/groups/one-health-high-level-expert-panel>

This approach is crucial for tackling health-related challenges. It has garnered global backing through the Quadripartite Alliance for One Health, which includes the World Health Organisation (WHO), the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH), The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), facilitating a comprehensive strategy for health issues across various sectors and disciplines. It achieves a fully integrated approach across disciplines demands, providing substantial support, political commitment, facilitating financial resources (Giraudoux et al., 2022), and a shift in mindset and behaviour.

For instance, the IPBES Workshop Report on Biodiversity and Pandemics (IPBES, 2020) emphasises the importance of enhancing One Health practices for pandemic prevention through strategies like sustainable land management and wildlife conservation beyond mere public health initiatives. Additionally, One Health strategies have proven to be effective in managing diseases related to food production and ecosystem health, including avian influenza, antimicrobial resistance, and various neglected tropical diseases.

However, there are still limitations on addressing or integrating this concept of multiple interrelationships within specific settings and concrete applications. We used the DPSEEA model (de Araújo-Pinto et al., 2012; Stedile et al., 2018) integrated with cognitive mapping methodology (Gray et al., 2015; Olazabal et al., 2018) to develop this complex system and identify the most relevant components and interconnections.

The novelty lies in grounding the framework on the “One Health High-Level Expert Panel” broader vision (OHHLEP et al., 2022). The objective is to encompass not only the analysis from its original reductionist conception of disease control but also a broader model linked to prevention. We incorporate this holistic approach that addresses the research gaps (criticisms) identified in the literature. One of these gaps is that within One Health research and programs, human health is usually confined to a biological or epidemiological perspective, disregarding key social determinants of health. Another gap has been recognised in the need to show evidence of the intimately entangled nature of human, animal and ecosystem health. Hence, these three elements are co-constitutive factors or issues rather than separated and fixed entities, as considered in the original approach (Davis & Sharp, 2020). A third gap lies in integrating social sciences and other disciplines into One Health programs. In HOBE, we wish to address these three gaps by developing a One Health framework adapted for a socio-ecological system.

The Health and Climate research group at BC3's past projects have analysed how changes in natural ecosystems and socioeconomic environments affect human health, considering the relationships between climate change, environmental changes and human health (Chiabai et al., 2018).

In the HOBE project, we take the following four assumptions for the construction of the One Health framework to be applied afterwards in the case study area of the Bay of Plentzia:

1. *Human and non-human beings depend on ecosystems (Glaser et al., 2008).*
2. *One Health approach is developed in a social-ecological system (Ostrom, 2009).*
3. *Our study area is a Socio-ecological system (SES) nested or embedded in a telecoupling² system (Liu et al., 2019).*
4. *One Health definition from the One Health High-Level Expert Panel (OHHLEP et al., 2022).*

²A telecoupling is a process that connects distant systems. Examples include trade, migration, tourism, air circulation, and technology or information transfer over distances. Telecouplings have five major components- systems, agents, flows, causes, and effects (Liu et al., 2013).

This deliverable contains four chapters. Chapter 1 developed a conceptual framework proposal for One Health applied to a socio-ecological system to study the interlinkages between people and nature, social and ecological components, integrate social sciences into One Health, and propose broader conceptualisations of health beyond biomedical approaches.

In Chapter 2, we reviewed the literature on the nexus between health (or disease) and different kinds of pressures, such as pollution, fisheries and aquaculture exploitation, non-indigenous species, habitat loss, river obstacles, coastal construction, ports and shipping traffic, climate change and variability, and agricultural productive systems. The literature review focused on northern Spain, including Asturias, Cantabria, and the Basque Country.

Finally, Chapter 3 focuses on the case study. It contains a general description of the Butroe River basin and the characterisation of our focal area in the Transition of the Butroe River and Bay of Plentzia according to the components of the conceptual framework.

CONCEPTS BOX

The transdisciplinary **landscape** concept encompasses five dimensions: (1) landscape as a spatial entity, (2) landscape as a mental entity, (3) landscape as a temporal dimension, (4) landscape as a nexus between nature and culture, and (5) landscape as a complex system (Tress & Tress, 2001).

An **ecosystem** (or ecological system) is a system where organisms and environmental elements interact among them (Chapin et al., 2011). The biotic and abiotic components interact through nutrient cycles and energy flows.

Ecosystem health is a metaphor used to describe the state or condition of an ecosystem (Lackey, 2001; Rapport et al., 2009) in which its dynamic attributes are expressed within the normal ranges of activity relative to its ecological state of development (Andel & Aronson, 2009).

Socio-ecological Systems (SES) are “complex adaptive systems in which people and nature are inextricably linked, and both the social and ecological components strongly influence outcomes. The social dimension includes actors, institutions, cultures, economies, and livelihoods. The ecological dimension includes wild species and the ecosystem they inhabit” (IPBES³, 2024). This is a “concept used in a variety of analytical approaches intended to examine the relationship between people and nature as inter-linked, recognising that humans should be seen as a part of, not apart from, nature, and nature as inter-linked to social systems” (Berkes & Folke, 2002; Ostrom, 2009).

The **telecoupling systems** framework is “hierarchically structured, so it relies on a multilevel analytic approach. The telecoupled system level includes an interrelated set of coupled human and natural systems connected through flows among them” (Liu et al., 2019).

The **environment** is a complex system of physical, chemical, and biotic factors (such as climate, soil, and living things) that act upon an organism or an ecological community and ultimately determine its form and survival (Britannica, 2024).

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³ IPBES for the acronym Intergovernmental Science–Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services

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1. Conceptual framework for One Health in a socio-ecological system

Historically, the One Health approach has tended to prioritise human health, a view criticised for its short-sightedness (Coghlan et al., 2021). We agree that using the term "health" is intended to bring closer communication between scientists (e.g., biologists, social scientists, medical doctors and psychologists) and non-scientists. However, the resilience or adaptive capacity of the ecological system is an essential element for human, animal and plant health (Andel & Arosón, 2009).

Rabinowitz and colleagues (2018) provided an inspiring vision about system levels for different types of One Health interactions by showing how 'sentinel events' occurring in animals and humans can provide warnings of health threats at higher global and planetary levels from a multi-scale perspective. The inclusion of ecosystem health by OHHLEP in 2022 was critical and successful.

Inspired by Rabinowitz's approach, we show all the elements and relationships involved in a broader vision of One Health in a SES and developed in Figure 1-1. This figure illustrates the interconnected elements and scales that contribute to the health of humans, animals, and ecosystems. The environment encompasses the atmosphere, lithosphere, hydrosphere, and biosphere⁴. Within this framework, we identify diverse abiotic components—including built habitats, fomites⁵, air, water, soil, and molecules—that interact with every element of the biosphere. Collectively, these components are organised across multiple scales. The biosphere itself consists of biomes, ecosystems, natural habitats, microbiota⁶, and the kingdoms of life: animalia (including humans), plantae, fungi, chromista, protozoa, archaea, bacteria, and viruses. Notably, these interactions operate within a multiscale, transdisciplinary, nested, and intricate socio-ecological system defined by spatial and temporal dimensions. The green arrows in the figure symbolise the dynamic interplay of these relationships.

The figure also shows human beings as a subgroup interacting at all levels with other species and the environment. Likewise, the nation/culture has socioeconomic and political implications for the environment. We want to emphasise that humans are active actors with an extraordinary capacity for transformation and decision-making. Furthermore, it is essential to stress the need for different types of disciplinary expertise and to collaborate for a transdisciplinary approach.

⁴ The biosphere is the part of a planet's environment where life exists.

⁵ Fomites are any inanimate/abiotic object that can transfer disease to a new host when contaminated with or exposed to infectious agents (such as pathogenic bacteria, viruses or fungi).

⁶ The microbiota consists of all living members forming the microbiome.

Figure 1-1. System levels for One Health in a socio-ecological system. Interactions are illustrated in green arrows. The scope of the HOB E project is in the blue box.

We adjust the levels and scales according to the elements of the biosphere (biotic) and their relationship with the rest of the environment's abiotic elements. We suggest that a social-ecological system is complex, profoundly interconnected, and adaptive, with people and nature inextricably linked. In our approach, everything is intertwined, sparking curiosity about the potential findings.

Building on this expanded vision, which is not new, Zinsstag et al. (2011) introduced the concept of health in social-ecological systems, which examines complex, interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary interactions in all health-related fields. This approach has gained relevance as numerous studies demonstrate how global challenges - such as climate change and biodiversity loss - are intrinsically linked to human and animal health outcomes (Chiabai et al., 2018; Eissa, 2024; Mora et al., 2022; Pfenning-Butterworth et al., 2024). The emergence of the new 'One Health' definition (OHLEP et al., 2022) further underlines the interconnectedness of these dimensions, emphasising the need for integrated strategies to address health challenges across species and environments. Strengthening multisectoral coordination is central to this framework, as highlighted by Zinsstag et al., (2023).

The Driving Force-Pressure-State-Exposure-Effect-Action (DPSEEA) framework is a linkage-based framework created by the World Health Organization to guide the development of environmental indicators (Corvalán et al., 2000). This framework links the impact on the environment to human health through a chain of causal effects and allows the identification of the full spectrum of interconnections of cause-effects.

To design a One Health conceptual framework for a socio-ecological system, we integrated the DPSEEA (Corvalan et al., 2000) with cognitive mapping (Gray et al., 2015; Olazabal et al., 2018) methodology to develop this complex system and identify the most relevant components and interconnections that can define the behaviour of the socio-ecological system.

Taking the DPSEEA model as a starting point for this conceptual framework, we restructured it using four groups: (1) drivers, (2) pressures, (3) a socio-ecological system defined in terms of state-exposure-effects, and (4) actions. We propose an innovation to the original DPSEEA model, with the "state-exposure-effects" defined as a joint set of interconnections describing the socio-ecological system.

1.1. Categories and components of the conceptual framework

1.1.1. Drivers

Drivers are fundamental forces, either natural or anthropogenic, that initiate changes in the system, often beyond immediate control. These drivers represent broad and systemic influences, such as population growth, economic development, and climate change, shaping environmental and health outcomes (Harwell et al., 2019). For instance, demographic shifts and urbanisation exert long-term impacts on land use, resource demand, and waste generation, cascading through the framework as pressures and environmental states.

Drivers like economic policies can influence industrialisation, leading to air quality emissions, a key environmental state affecting health. Similarly, climate change, driven by greenhouse gas emissions, alters ecosystems and increases health risks, such as heatwaves and vector-borne diseases (Chiabai et al., 2018; Mora et al., 2022). Addressing these drivers often requires strategic, cross-sectoral interventions aimed at systemic transformation rather than localised actions, emphasising their complexity and scale.

1.1.2. Pressures

Pressures exerted due to human activities can lead to unintended or intended changes in social-ecological systems. The central pressures affecting coastal-marine landscapes are a broad set of pollutants (including nutrients, pesticides, organic pollutants, heavy metals, oil spills, personal care products, debris, litter, plastics, harmful algal blooms and pathogens); fisheries and aquaculture exploitation; non-indigenous, introduced or exotic species; habitat or ecosystem loss, alteration, degradation or fragmentation; freshwater river diversions, detours or obstacles; infrastructure, urbanisation; coastal construction; ports or shipping traffic; climate change or variability; and agriculture, forestry and other land use (AFOLU) activities, including livestock. This list of pressures will be developed in Chapter 2, within the context of the north of Spain.

1.1.3. One Health in a socio-ecological system as a combined set of components defining the "state-exposure-effects"

Our approach is rooted in ecosystem health (Rapport, 1998), emphasising the role of the environment in providing the foundation upon which the rest of the health determinants are built (for both humans and animals). The socio-ecological system is proposed as a combined set of components that ultimately define the "state-exposure effects" in a traditional DPSEEA.

The determinants proposed for ecosystem health define the state of the environment. The determinants proposed for human and animal health include and define exposure and effects (for example, chronic or infectious diseases caused by a modified state of the environment—degraded or contaminated, for example).

Therefore, we propose a conceptual framework for One Health developed within a socio-ecological system, characterised by the combination of multiple determinants describing the health of humans, animals and ecosystems.

We selected components from two established frameworks: the determinants of human health (WHO, 2024; Choi & Sonin, 2018) and nature's contributions (Díaz et al., 2018). In the absence of a consolidated framework for animal health, we selected elements from the social determinants of animal health and health inequalities proposed by Card et al. (2018), other elements proposed by Wittrock & Duncan (2019) for fish and wildlife, and those proposed by Bauman & Parmley (2021) for companion animals. Socioeconomic elements influencing human and animal health from the determinants of human health (WHO, 2024; Choi & Sonin, 2018) were grouped separately to avoid duplicate components.

We categorised these determinants into four categories as described below: (a) Human health, (b) Domestic and wildlife animals health, (c) Socioeconomic aspect for humans and animals, and (d) Ecosystem. Finally, we include "one health" as a general concept where all dimensions converge.

To generate our OH in SES, we carried out a task force activity to collect representations of One Health mental models from BC3 and PiE researchers using a cognitive map (CM). A CM is a participatory, semi-quantitative method that allows the integration of views from different participants and constructs an aggregated model (Özesmi & Özesmi, 2004). The methodological features involved in CM make it a helpful tool for knowledge co-production in systems characterised by complexity, uncertainty and scarcity of data (Blacketer et al., 2021; Olazabal et al., 2018).

These determinants ultimately define the "state-exposure-effects" in a traditional DPSEEA. The determinants proposed for ecosystem health define the "state" of the environment, and the determinants proposed for human and animal health define the "effects" (e.g., chronic or infectious diseases caused by a modified state of the environment—degraded or contaminated). The behavioural and lifestyle factors represent the "exposure." All these determinants are interconnected with complex non-linear and multi-factorial relationships and define the behaviour of the socio-ecological system.

In this conceptual framework, it is essential to note that some determinants apply to various categories. The body function and microbiome appear only in the human health category, but we could be valid for other components, as we will see in the results (see Table 1.1).

a. Human health

The determinants of human health (DHH) include the conditions in "which people are born, grow, work, live, and age, as well as the broader set of forces and systems shaping the conditions of daily life. These forces and systems include economic policies and systems, development agendas, social norms, social policies and political systems" (Choi & Sonin, 2018).

The DHH significantly influence health inequities - the unfair and avoidable differences in health status seen within and between countries (Choi & Sonin, 2018; WHO, n.d.). It has been reported that 89% of health problems occur outside the clinical space due to genetics, behaviour, environment, and social circumstances (Choi & Sonin, 2018).

According to Choi and Sonin (2018), the DHH categories are environment, individual behaviour, medical care, social circumstances, genetics, and biology. We separated the 12 socioeconomic components from human health determinants because, in this case, they are shared by humans and animals. Additionally, we include the microbiome, which is not included in their approach but is mentioned in other studies as a vital component of human health (Elton, 2021). Research findings suggest that gut microbes could affect cognitive health, behaviour, and mood through links between brain health and gut dysbiosis (Sherwin et al., 2019; Singh et al., 2022).

The environment refers to our natural and human environments and includes everything from our cities' infrastructure to the air quality we breathe and the water and soil quality. The physical environment is an essential factor contributing to our health, and although it can critically affect health, it has the most 7% of impact out of all the determinants (Choi & Sonin, 2018).

Individual behaviour, such as smoking habits, sleep and exercise patterns, sexual activity, and mood levels, is a critical determinant of our physical, mental, and overall well-being. Positive changes to our behaviour can reduce the risk of developing various diseases, and many public health interventions have already focused on avoiding behaviours that could lead to higher health risks or promoting healthier lifestyles (Choi & Sonin, 2018).

Medical care refers to factors correlated with care by a trained provider, such as provider availability and healthcare quality (Choi & Sonin, 2018). However, we often must realise that medical care only contributes to a small portion of our overall health. The most prevalent issue in medical care today is the inequities in access to health services and a decreasing level of health literacy in the general population. This combination can be hazardous since poorer groups are more exposed to impacts related to pollution or unhealthy lifestyles; at the same time, health inequalities and lack of knowledge usually translate into higher health impacts.

Social circumstances reflect the social environment in which we grow and live. An individual's social status, early childhood development and culture impact their social development and personal health. Poor social circumstances such as discrimination, concentrated poverty, and low education levels often result in poor health outcomes and a lower quality of life (Choi & Sonin, 2018).

While genetics and biology may be considered the primary components of health, genetic makeup, physical body structure, and bodily function determine only about a fifth of our measurable health. Genome sequencing will become more important for predicting and preparing for future health outcomes, but it is not feasible to sequence everyone's genome. Some biological and genetic factors have varying impacts on different segments of the population, so variance must be considered when applying the determinants of health. The effects of ageing and inherited conditions (sickle-cell anaemia, cystic fibrosis, etc.) are factors with varying levels of impact on the population (Choi & Sonin, 2018).

The microbiome is a community of microorganisms (e.g., fungi, bacteria and viruses) in a particular environment. In humans, the microbiome consists of both helpful and potentially harmful microbes. Most are symbiotic (benefiting both the human body and the microbiota), and some, in smaller numbers, are pathogenic (disease-promoting). In a healthy organism, pathogenic and symbiotic microbiota coexist without problems. However, if this balance is disturbed - caused by infectious diseases, specific diets or the prolonged use of antibiotics or other bacteria-destroying drugs - a dysbiosis interrupts these regular interactions. As a result, the body may become more susceptible to disease.

Table 1.1. Human health components and their descriptions.

Components	Description
Allergens	According to the National Institute of Environmental Health Science ⁷ , allergies arise if the body's immune system overreacts to certain foreign substances (allergens) that are generally harmless in most people. Common allergens include pollens, fungal spores, house dust mites, and animal epithelial materials, but they can also include drugs, biological products, and insect venoms.
Exposure/Access to Firearms	Access to loaded firearms that are readily available plays a potential role in impulsive suicidal behaviour or rapidly escalating violent interpersonal events. Also, firearms play a role in hunting and conserving wildlife. (Ikeda et al., 2003)

⁷ National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences: <https://www.niehs.nih.gov/>

Components	Description
Location	The neighbourhoods people live in significantly impact their health and well-being. Healthy People 2030 focuses on improving health and safety in the places where people are born, live, learn, work, play, worship, and age (CDC, 2018 ⁸). This includes access to healthy foods, crime level, transportation quality, crowding conditions, public space, educational opportunities, job opportunities, walkability, residence quality, recreational activities, and green or blue areas.
Pollution	According to ATSDR ⁹ , Pollution can harm human health and the environment. It can be pollutants found in air, water and soil. It can also be harmful noise or artificial light. Exposure to toxic chemicals can lead to chronic and often irreversible health conditions such as neurodevelopment problems and congenital defects and diseases associated with endocrine disruption. The emergence of new environmental hazards, such as electronic waste, nanoparticles, microplastics, chemicals that alter the endocrine system, and water scarcity.
Diversity and Diet Patterns	According to the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services and the U.S. Department of Agriculture ¹⁰ , Healthy dietary patterns can help lower the risk of chronic disease. The core elements of a healthy dietary pattern include consuming vegetables of all types, fruits, grains (especially whole grains), low-fat or fat-free dairy, protein foods, and oils while also paying attention to portion size. Access to foods that support healthy dietary patterns supports health not only then but also across the lifespan and possibly for future generations.
Sleep Patterns	According to AASM ¹¹ , Healthy sleep habits can improve your ability to fall asleep and stay asleep. Sleep deficiency is linked to chronic health problems, including heart disease, kidney disease, high blood pressure, diabetes, stroke, obesity, and depression. It is also linked to accidents that can result in injury or death. Factors contributing to insufficient sleep include environmental, familial, socioeconomic, social media use, and lack of physical activity.
Physical Activity	Physical activity is any bodily movement produced by skeletal muscles that requires energy expenditure. Physical activity refers to all movement, including during leisure time, for transport to and from places or as part of a person's work. Both moderate- and vigorous-intensity physical activity improve health. Regular physical activity is proven to help prevent and manage non-communicable diseases such as heart disease, stroke, diabetes and several cancers. It also helps prevent hypertension, maintain a healthy body weight and improve mental health, quality of life and well-being (WHO, 2022 ¹²).
Psychological Assets	Resilience-based interventions often target psychosocial assets such as persistence, tolerance of negative affect, self-efficacy, planning, and prosocial behaviours (e.g., empathy, kindness, teamwork, and other social skills). (Leventhal et al., 2015)
Negative Mood	According to Better Health ¹³ , a negative mood can be described as any feeling that makes you miserable and sad. These emotions make you dislike yourself and others and reduce your confidence, self-esteem, and general life satisfaction. Emotions that can become negative are hate, anger, jealousy, and sadness.
Health Literacy	Health Literacy is the knowledge and competence to access, understand, appraise, and apply health information to make health-related judgments. (Sørensen et al., 2012)
Quality of Healthcare	According to Simply Connect ¹⁴ , Health Access and quality are defined as the extent to which people have equitable, affordable and available access to needed healthcare services. This definition includes physical accessibility and availability via financial means, transportation options, and other factors. It also includes the quality of care received after seeking care. Equitable access to healthcare is key as the poorest groups

⁸ (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2018). Social Determinants of Health: Know What Affects Health. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/socialdeterminants/index.htm>)

⁹ Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ATSDR): <https://www.atsdr.cdc.gov/> European Environment Agency: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/topics/in-depth/pollution>

¹⁰ U.S. Department of Health and Human Services and U.S Department of Agriculture. (2020). 2020-2025 Dietary Guidelines for Americans: 9th Edition.

¹¹ American Academy of Sleep Medicine (AASM). Sleep Education. <https://sleepeducation.org/healthy-sleep/healthy-sleep-habits/#:~:text=Keep%20a%20consistent%20sleep%20schedule,7%2D8%20hours%20of%20sleep.https://www.nhlbi.nih.gov/health/sleep-deprivation>

¹² World Health Organisation (WHO). Physical Activity. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/physical-activity>

¹³ Better Health Channel. Negative emotions. <https://www.betterhealth.vic.gov.au/health/healthyliving/negative-emotions>

¹⁴ Simply connect. Social Determinants of Health: Healthcare Access & Quality <https://simplyconnect.me/blog/social-determinants-of-health-healthcare-access-quality/>

Components	Description
	in the population are the most vulnerable to the negative impacts of climate change, pollution and lifestyle factors, and therefore, those suffering from poorer health.
Body Function	According to the WHO's International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF) ¹⁵ , body functions are categorised into different subfunctions. Mental functions, such as the brain's, can be differentiated into global mental functions (consciousness, energy, drive) and specific mental functions (memory, language, calculation). Sensory functions include seeing, hearing, tasting, etc., and the sensation of pain. Voice and speech functions produce sounds and speech. There are functions of the cardiovascular system (heart and blood vessels), the haematological and immunological systems (blood production and immunity), and respiratory systems (respiration and exercise tolerance), as well as functions of the digestive system (ingestion, digestion, and elimination), the metabolic system, and the endocrine system.
Human gene pool	According to NIH ¹⁶ , a gene pool combines all the genes (including alleles) in a reproducing population or species. A large gene pool has extensive genomic diversity and is better able to withstand environmental challenges.
Microbiome	According to NIH ¹⁷ , the microbiome consists of both helpful and potentially harmful microbes. Most are symbiotic (benefiting both the human/animal body and the microbiota), and some, in smaller numbers, are pathogenic (disease-promoting). In a healthy organism, pathogenic and symbiotic microbiota coexist without problems. Nevertheless, if this balance is disturbed – caused by infectious diseases, specific diets or the prolonged use of antibiotics or other bacteria-destroying drugs – a dysbiosis occurs that stops these regular interactions. As a result, the body may become more susceptible to disease.

b. Domestic and wildlife animals' health

When we talk about animals, we include domestic (pets and productive animals) and wildlife animals.

According to Card et al. (2018), veterinarians and veterinary associations can advocate for a more egalitarian society to improve animal health. In veterinary medicine, explanations of animal health and welfare are often framed in terms of protecting the "five freedoms" and not focusing on social determinants of health. However, this approach does not analyse the effects of animal caretakers' income, education, employment, or social status on their welfare.

Considering that the relevance of health gradients concerning animals and the veterinary profession has not been thoroughly studied and debated, Cipolla et al. (2015) offered a potential contribution of veterinarian aspects to public health. Card and colleagues (2018) proposed a set of elements for social determinants of animal health and health inequalities. Wittrock & Duncan (2019) for fish and wildlife health, and Bauman & Parmley (2021) for companion animals. With these inputs, we develop a proposal for determinants of animal health. This is a list with five components and their descriptions.

Table 1.2. Domestic Animals and Wildlife health components (6) and their descriptions

Components	Description
Animals Food security and nutrition	Animals can access healthy food and have sufficient food or a healthy diet (Cipolla, 2015; Card, 2018).
Animal Pharmacology & Drugs	Animal medicines protect the food security of millions of people worldwide by enabling farmers to deliver food efficiently, safely and affordably.

¹⁵ World Health Organisation (WHO). International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF). <https://www.who.int/standards/classifications/international-classification-of-functioning-disability-and-health>

¹⁶ National Human Genome Research Institute (NIH). Gene Pool. <https://www.genome.gov/genetics-glossary/Gene-Pool#:~:text=Definition,able%20to%20withstand%20environmental%20challenges>

¹⁷ National Human Genome Research Institute (NIH). Microbiome. <https://www.genome.gov/genetics-glossary/Microbiome#:~:text=Definition,the%20skin%20or%20gastrointestinal%20tract.>

Components	Description
	Understanding the degradation of antibiotics in the environment is essential, as antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is an increasing global threat. When antibiotics spill into the soil and waterways, resistant strains of bacteria can emerge in the environment. They can infect animals and humans that come into contact with them. Also, antibiotic-resistant bacteria of treated animals can be present in manure and, therefore, be disseminated into the environment and to wildlife ¹⁸ .
Mortality pressure	Morbidity and mortality of wildlife and domestic animals can be attributed to a variety of factors, such as human activities like land development, predation (from wildlife to domestic animals), wildfire, poaching, electricity accidents, human consumption, culling, hunting, fishing, and automobile traffic ¹⁹ .
Animal genetic endowment	Basic biology and organic makeup are fundamental determinants of health. Genetic endowment provides an inherited predisposition to various individual responses that affect health status. Genetic endowment sometimes predisposes specific individuals to particular diseases or health problems. ²⁰
Animal social environment	Social competence is defined as the ability of an animal to optimise the expression of social behaviour as a function of the available social information. The social environment encountered early in life can affect the expression of various social behaviours later in life. The suite of interactions that occur between animals of the same species (Intraspecific) and different species (Interspecific), e.g., with humans (Taborsky et al., 2012)
Needs for daily living	To survive, animals need access to and availability of quality water and food, migration opportunities, stable population demographics, safe shelter and quality habitats (Wittrock & Duncan, 2019).

c. Socioeconomic determinants of health for human and animal health

In this category, we present socioeconomic determinants shared by humans and animals (domestic or wildlife) from Choi and Soni (2018). We included the following categories: economics, employment, political governance, demography, and built environment. We obtained a list with 12 components.

Table 1.3. Socioeconomic components (12) and their descriptions

Components	Description
Access to Healthcare	<p>Access to healthcare²¹ for humans means having "the timely use of personal health services to achieve the best health outcomes" (IOM, 1993). It consists of four components: (i) Coverage facilitates entry into the health care system. Uninsured people are less likely to receive medical care and more likely to have poor health status. (ii) Services: Having a usual source of care is associated with adults receiving recommended screening and prevention services. (iii) Timeliness: the ability to provide health care when the need is recognised. And (iv) Workforce: capable, qualified, culturally competent providers. Many of these apply to animals (pets and livestock) access to veterinary care</p> <p>On the other hand, access to veterinary care is not always homogenous across communities and currently lacks a consistent definition. However, definitions have been proposed, such as "geographical proximity of resources and service; accessibility of professionals and ease of contact" (Pyatt et al., 2017), "the availability of a service in a location and its affordability for various livestock keepers" (Gizaw et al., 2021), and "geographical proximity of up-to-date resources and facilities, accessibility of professionals (physical and communicative), and ease of contact" (Pyatt et al., 2020)</p>

¹⁸ Global Animal Health Association. Food Security. <https://www.healthforanimals.org/importance-of-animals/food-security>

¹⁹ Indian Law Portal. Causes of Death in Wildlife. <https://indianlawportal.co.in/causes-of-death-in-wildlife/>

²⁰ Nova Scotia Health Authority. Biology and Genetic Endowment <http://www.cdha.nshealth.ca/dartmouth-community-health-board/population-health/biology-and-genetic-endowment>

²¹ Institute of Medicine (US) Committee on Monitoring Access to Personal Health Care Services. Access to Health Care in America. Millman M, editor. Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US); 1993. PMID: 25144064. Healthy People 2020. <https://www.ahrq.gov/research/findings/nhqdr/chartbooks/access/elements.html>

Components	Description
Built environment	According to the Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry ²² , the places of our lives – our homes, workplaces, schools, parks, and houses of worship – affect the quality of our health and influence our experience with disease and well-being. The built environment includes the buildings in which we work and learn, the parks in which we exercise, the roads and transportation systems we use to travel from place to place, as well as the water distribution systems, electrical grids, and mobile and broadband networks we use to access information and stay connected. Characteristics of the built environment may limit our access to healthcare, healthy food, clean water, and safe places for physical activity.
Culture and Tradition	Culture ²³ is a collective term that identifies specific ideas, customs, and social behaviours. It represents a group of people or a society, combining their knowledge, beliefs, morals, and laws. Tradition ²³ , on the other hand, is a more specific term. It is often used to describe an individual event or practice, such as removing one's shoes when entering one's home.
Demographic	According to Indeed (2024 ²⁴), demographics are statistics that describe human and animal populations and their characteristics. In humans and animals, analysis studies a population based on age, race, and sex.
Education	Education ²⁵ refers to the discipline concerned with teaching and learning methods in schools or school-like environments, as opposed to various nonformal and informal means of socialisation.
Income	The term "income" ²⁶ generally refers to the amount of money, property, and other transfers of value received over a set period in exchange for services or products.
Markets and Fair Trade	A market ²⁷ is where buyers and sellers can meet to facilitate the exchange or transaction of goods and services. Fair Trade ²⁷ is a trading partnership based on dialogue, transparency, and respect that seeks greater equity in international trade. It contributes to sustainable development by offering better trading conditions to and securing the rights of marginalised producers and workers.
Political governance	Political governance may be defined as a political process by which public authority is exercised and policies are implemented (Lee, 2019)
Race and ethnicity	Race ²⁸ refers to dividing people into groups based on physical characteristics and ascribing social meaning to those groups. Ethnicity ²⁶ describes the culture of people in a given geographic region, including their language, heritage, religion and customs.
Social Connectedness	According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, human social connectedness ²⁹ is the degree to which people have and perceive a desired number, quality, and diversity of relationships that create a sense of belonging and being cared for, valued, and supported (CDC). On the other hand, animal social behaviours often occur within an extensive interconnected network of social ties, and it is clear that these connections play an important role in animal behaviour (Brent, 2015).
Social Status	Social status, in humans, is the relative rank that an individual holds, with attendant rights, duties, and lifestyle, in a social hierarchy based upon honour or prestige ³⁰ . In animals, social status or structure defines an important class of ecological relationships between nearby conspecifics. It may include competition, cooperation, dominance in acquiring mates or resources, competitive or cooperative care of offspring, and cannibalism (Dahlgren & Whitehead, 1991).

²² Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry. Place and Health <https://www.atsdr.cdc.gov/placeandhealth/howdoesPlaceaffectHealth.html>

²³ Preemptive Love. The Difference between culture and tradition. <https://preemptivelove.org/blog/difference-between-culture-and-tradition>

²⁴ Indeed, 2024; What Are Demographics? (Definition, Examples and Uses) <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/demographics-definition>

²⁵ Britannica. Education. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/education>

²⁶ Investopedia. Income Definition: Types, Examples, and Taxes <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/i/income.asp>

²⁷ Fair Trade Advocacy Office. Definition of Fair Trade <https://fairtrade-advocacy.org/definition-of-fair-trade/>

²⁸ Washington University in St. Louis. Race and Ethnicity Self-Study Guide <https://students.wustl.edu/race-ethnicity-self-study-guide>

²⁹ Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Emotional Well-Being. <https://www.cdc.gov/emotional-wellbeing/social-connectedness/affect-health.htm>

³⁰ Britannica. Social Status. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/social-status>

Components	Description
Work Conditions	<p>Working conditions cover a broad range of topics and issues, from working time (hours of work, rest periods, and work schedules) to remuneration, as well as the physical conditions and mental demands that exist in the workplace (ilo.org)(International Labour Organization https://www.ilo.org/).</p> <p>On the other hand, according to the Animals Ethics³¹ NGO, many animals are used as workers. They are used as a means of transport, to pull ploughs, carry goods, and power mills. For example, dogs are used as police or guides. Jobs for which nonhuman animals are used are often tiresome and may cause physical pain, such as when the animals have to carry heavy loads, or they are hit with whips or other objects to make them run, carry weight or perform some other type of work.</p>

d. Ecosystems

Aldo Leopold used the metaphor of the “health” of ecosystem health for the first time in 1941. The environment’s role in health has long been recognised. *“Man is an integral part of most ecosystems, not only influencing but being influenced by his environment, that his physical and mental health, now and in the future, are intimately linked with the dynamic system of natural objects, forces and processes that interact within the biosphere and also including those of man’s culture”* (UNESCO, 1968). Ecosystem health was officialised in 1992 with the principle seven of the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development. This principle addresses the need to protect and restore the health and integrity of the earth’s ecosystems. On the other hand, “environmental health” focuses only on human health and its relationship with the environment as a branch of public health; it promotes human health and well-being and fosters healthy and safe communities (American Public Health Association, 2023).

Costanza, in 1992, suggested that ecosystem health is intrinsically connected to sustainability, perceived as a comprehensive, multi-level, dynamic indicator of system resilience, structure, and vitality. However, other authors propose five additional measures of ecosystem health and status changes: diversity, stability, yield, productivity, and resilience (Sherman, 1994). Then, Costanza and Mageau (1999) defined a healthy ecosystem as one that is sustainable—that is, it can maintain its structure (organisation) and function (vigour) over time in the face of external stress (resilience).

This is why the concept of ecosystem health has broadened to incorporate a more integrated approach encompassing environmental, economic, and human health dimensions. This articulates the growing emphasis on sustainability within society and enters the realm of inter (Ramírez-Carrillo et al., 2018) and trans-disciplinarity. This holistic perspective recognises the interconnectedness of natural systems and the need for balanced consideration of ecological integrity, economic viability, and social equity in sustainable development (Costanza, 1992; Rapport, 1998).

The most applied parameters defining ecosystem health are organisation, vigour, and resilience (Costanza & Mageau, 1999), productivity, resilience, and organisation (Rapport & Maffi, 2011), or structure, function, resilience, and abiotic elements (Canning & Death, 2019). However, we found two leading methodologies in Latin America that focus on the sustainability landscape: adaptability and robustness (Ramírez-Carrillo et al., 2018) or multifunctionality, productivity, and well-being (Redondo et al., 2019), and will help assess and analyse prescriptive scenarios.

Ecosystem health is fundamental to understanding the landscape context; it must be analysed and measured independently using one of the proposed dimensions above. It refers to an ecosystem’s structural and functional integrity, including its capacity to sustain services and benefits over time. In our case study, to address the health of ecosystems, we use Nature’s

³¹ <https://www.animal-ethics.org/animals-used-workers/>

Contributions³²(NC)(Díaz et al., 2018) as a consolidated framework from a pragmatic point of view with direct links to human and animal health. Nature's contributions encompass the tangible and intangible benefits humans derive from ecosystems, including provisioning (e.g., food, water, and raw materials), regulating (e.g., climate regulation, water purification), and cultural (e.g., spiritual value, recreation) contributions.

To evaluate ecosystem health via nature's contributions, we can consider several aspects: Quality of contributions, stability and resilience, sustainability of supply, abundance and accessibility. We can classify ecosystems as healthy or degraded based on their ability to consistently provide high-quality, stable, and sustainable contributions. A Healthy Ecosystem can support abundant, high-quality nature's contributions with resilience to external pressures, ensuring long-term benefits to both humans and biodiversity. On the other hand, a degraded ecosystem shows reduced quantity, poor quality, or instability in NCP, coupled with diminished resilience, often resulting from unsustainable practices or environmental degradation.

This is a list with 18 components and their descriptions (Brauman et al., 2020).

Table 1.4. Nature's contributions to people (and animals) components (18) and their descriptions.

Components	Description
Formation and protection of soils	Soil formation and long-term maintenance of soil fertility, including sediment retention and degradation or storage of pollutants.
Habitat maintenance	Maintenance of the natural habitat maintains the formation and continued production of ecological conditions necessary or favourable to humans [and all living beings].
Pollination and dispersal of seeds	Animal facilitation of pollen movement and seed dispersal.
Regulation of air quality	Filtration, fixation, degradation or storage of pollutants and gasses.
Regulation of climate	Emission and sequestration of greenhouse gases, biogenic volatile organic compounds, and aerosols; biophysical feedbacks (e.g., albedo, evapotranspiration).
Regulation of detrimental organisms to humans	Regulation of pests, pathogens, predators, competitors, parasites, and potentially harmful organisms.
Regulation of freshwater quality	Ecosystem filtration and addition of particles, pathogens, excess nutrients, and other chemicals.
Regulation of freshwater quantity	Regulation of surface and groundwater flow's quantity, location, and timing.
Regulation of hazards and extreme events	Amelioration of the impacts of hazards; reduction of size or frequency of hazards.
Regulation of ocean acidification	Regulation by photosynthetic organisms on land and sea of atmospheric CO ₂ concentrations and thus seawater pH.
Energy resources	Biomass-based fuels such as biofuel crops, animal waste, and fuelwood.
Food and feed	Food and feed from wild, managed, or domesticated organisms from terrestrial, freshwater, and marine sources.
Materials and assistance	Cultivated or wild materials and direct use of living organisms for industrial, ornamental, company, transport, labour, and other uses.
Medicinal and genetic resources	Naturally derived medicinal materials, genes, and genetic information.
Learning and inspiration	Capabilities developed through education, knowledge acquisition, and natural inspiration for art and technological design.
Maintenance of options	Capacity of nature to keep options open to support quality of life in the future.
Physical and psychological experiences	Physically and psychologically beneficial activities, healing, relaxation, recreation, and aesthetic enjoyment based on contact with nature.

³² According to IPBES, they are all the positive and negative contributions of living nature (i.e., diversity of organisms, ecosystems, and their associated ecological and evolutionary processes) to the quality of life for people [and non-humans]. Beneficial contributions from nature include such things as food provision, water purification, flood control, and artistic inspiration. In contrast, detrimental contributions include disease transmission and predation that damages people or their assets. Many NCPs may be perceived as benefits or detriments depending on the cultural, temporal or spatial context (Díaz et al., 2018).

Supporting identities	The basis for religious, spiritual, and social cohesion; sense of place, purpose, belonging, or rootedness associated with the living world; narratives, myths, and rituals; satisfaction from a landscape, seascape, habitat, or species.
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To develop our conceptual framework, we used cognitive mapping methodology to identify the interconnections between all the determinants in the four proposed categories. Determine components for One Health in a SES.

A cognitive map is a participatory, semi-quantitative method that allows the integration of views from different participants and constructs an aggregated model (Özesmi & Özesmi, 2004). The methodological features involved in CM make it a helpful tool for knowledge co-production in systems characterised by complexity, uncertainty and scarcity of data (Blacketer et al., 2021; Olazabal, Chiabai, et al., 2018).

For this, we carried out a task force activity to collect representations of One Health models from the HOBE team through the elaboration of mental maps (Annex Chapter 1-1³³). Participants were given 51 components representing the determinants related to the four categories proposed in section 1.1.3 .

Participants included three master's students, two researchers from the Marine Station of Plenzita (PiE, by its acronym in Basque), and seven researchers from BC3, covering the fields of ecology, toxicology, economy, engineering, biology and microbiology. The participants received by e-mail a document with the instructions, a Mental Modeler file with the 51 components, and a video with general indications on how to build the Cognitive Map (CM) using Mental Modeler software (Gray et al., 2013). The exercise was developed asynchronously between December 2023 and January 2024.

The task force exercise aimed to answer the following questions: (1) "What are the most relevant components related to human, animal and ecosystem health?" (2) "How do these components relate to each other to contribute to human, animal and ecosystem health?"

The objective was to identify the most relevant components and how these components relate to each other, weighting their interactions with a range between 1 and -1.

1. Analysis of individual-lens approach (individual cognitive maps)

We first analyse and discuss the 12 individual cognitive maps (Figure 1-2). Analysing individual maps helps us understand key elements and interconnections from the point of view of different experts. Also, using the Mental Modeler software, each map was described using network metrics: total components, total connections, density, connections per component, N of driver components, N of receiver components, N of ordinary components, and complexity score. Table 1.5 shows the description and meaning of these metrics.

Table 1.5. Description of the network metrics.

Metric	Description	Meaning
Total components	Number of variables included in the map	Higher numbers of components indicate more concepts included in the mental map.
Total connections	Number of connections included between variables	Higher numbers of connections indicate higher degrees of interactions between components in the mental map.

³³ Include instructions, video, mental model file in English and Spanish, and the informed consent document.

Metric	Description	Meaning
Density	Number of connections compared to the number of all possible connections	The higher the density, the more potential management policies exist.
Connections per component	Number of connections divided by the number of components	The lower the score, the higher the degree of connectedness in a system.
N of driver components	Components which only have "forcing" functions, with no incoming connections	Indicates the number of components that affect other system components but are not affected by others.
N of receiver components	Components which only have "receiving" functions, with no outgoing connections	Indicates the number of concepts that are affected by other system components but have no effect.
N of ordinary components	Components with both "forcing" and "receiving" functions	Indicates the number of concepts that influence and are influenced by other concepts.
Complexity score	Ratio of receiving variables to driver variables	Indicates the degree of resolution and measures the degree to which driving force outcomes are considered.

Figure 1-2 shows 12 cognitive maps using 51 components of human, animal, ecosystem, and socioeconomic determinants. The figure is intended to compare the diversity of shapes each CM has, the number of connections it contains, and the number of components used. This depends on each participant's experience.

Figure 1-2. Cognitive map diversity of the twelve participants using 51 predetermined components involved in the one health in socio-ecological systems. Components are in colour boxes: nature contributions in green, humans in light pink, animals in blue and socioeconomic in grey (all details are in Annexes).

2. Homogenisation and aggregation

Some participants included new components or separated the original ones during the task force. One participant (CM6) interpreted the task force question differently by relating each component to the concept of OH. After internal discussion, CM6 was omitted, and the rest of CM was homogenised according to Olazabal et al. (2018) to have the same components' names (ungrouped components were regrouped, and new components were discarded). Then, all remaining 11 CM were exported in an Excel matrix format and aggregated (Olazabal et al., 2018; Özesmi & Özesmi, 2004). Weights of the connections were added, and to maintain the range between 1 and -1, the results were divided by 10.

We obtained a first draft of the integrated cognitive map with 51 components and 353 connections (Figure 1-3). This result was analysed in a focal group with the participants (unless 4 of them), where they argued that the whole cognitive map represented the One Health approach. Therefore, the One Health component was removed from the network, and we rebuilt it (In Annex 1-2).

The resulting network has 50 components and 475 interconnections.

Figure 1-3. Collective network, the result of the aggregation of 11 cognitive maps.

3. Network of One Health in socioecological systems

The collective cognitive map is very complex to visualise and analyse; therefore, we decided to prioritise the components with higher centrality and their interconnections for two reasons: to propose a first set of One Health determinants, which are defined as those components with higher centrality (≥ 3) and to identify possible actions and understand repercussions in the other determinants of the system.

We computed and analysed the network metrics to understand the system's structure and dynamics, including centrality, in-degree, out-degree, and network density. To identify the network core, we selected the most critical components with centrality values higher than three and all their associated connections. This resulted in a refined network of 25 components and 183 connections (Figure 1-4) versus the original one with 50 components and 475 connections. This network's density was 0.305, indicating a more interconnected and cohesive structure than the broader network (Figure 1-3), which had a density of 0.19. Figure 1-4 shows the refined network of components and connections that define One Health in a SES, representing the collective network core (Figure 1-4).

Figure 1-4. Principal components and interconnections for One Health in a Socio-ecological system.

This collective map (Figure 1-4) represents a state-exposure-effects (SEE) approximation of the DPSEEA model. To identify the components with the highest relevance in the aggregated map, we computed three network indexes using the Mental Modeler software (Grey et al., 2013): centrality, in-degree, and out-degree. The centrality of a component, computed by adding the absolute value of all incoming and outgoing connections, indicates the conceptual importance of that individual component on the overall network structure (Kosko, 1986). In-degree strength represents the total absolute value of incoming connections, indicating the extent to which others influence a component. On the other hand, the out-degree strength is computed with the outgoing connections, reflecting the influence capacity of that component on the overall network (Gray et al., 2014).

We tried to select the 15 priority components and selected the top 5 components for each index (centrality, in-degree and out-degree). The essential characteristics of the collective network are the components to which most incoming arrows (in-degree) or outgoing arrows (out-degree). Table 1-5 shows the top five components in each category.

Table 1-5. Top five components per importance (highest centrality ≥ 3), impacted (highest in-degree) and influencing (highest out-degree) of the integrated cognitive map. Network statistics were obtained from Mental Modeler software.

Top 5	Centrality	In-degree	Out-degree
1	7.2	5.2	5.0
	Habitat maintenance	Body function	Political governance

2	7.1	Food and feed	4.2	Microbiome	4.3	Habitat maintenance
3	6.7	Pollution	4.2	Food and feed	3.7	Pollution
4	6.3	Body function	3.2	Psychological assets	3.4	Education
5	5.3	Microbiome	3.0	Pollution	3.2	Income

This classification highlights the importance of nine components as preliminary key One Health determinants: natural *habitat maintenance*, *food and feed*, *pollution*, *body function*, *microbiome*, *political governance*, *education*, *income*, and *psychological assets*. From the 15 components listed in Table 1-5, five components appear multiple times, leaving a set of nine unique components (*pollution*, *microbiome*, *food and feed*, *body function*, and *habitat maintenance*).

The five components with the highest centrality are natural *habitat maintenance*, *food and feed*, *pollution*, *body function*, and the *microbiome*, which represent pivotal elements within the network due to their extensive interconnections. Similarly, components with high indegree, including body function, the microbiome, food and feed and psychological assets, are heavily influenced by other factors, highlighting their vulnerability in the network. Conversely, those with high out-degrees, such as political governance, natural habitat maintenance, education and income, act as significant influencers, driving changes across the network.

The five components with the highest in-degree (more incoming arrows) are *body function*, *microbiome*, *food and feed*, *psychological assets*, and *pollution*. This means that these components are strongly affected (positively or negatively) by any change in the network and will therefore experience the most significant impact in the network.

On the other hand, the five components with the highest outdegree (outgoing arrows) will have the most significant influence on the network components, which, in our case, are political governance, habitat maintenance, pollution, education, and *income*.

Figures 1-4 show that natural *habitat maintenance* is the most central component. This is vital for *food and feed*, which connects directly to pollination, seed dispersal, soil formation and protection, and all the biodiversity involved, including the microbiome. On the other hand, we can see how pollution negatively affects many network components, including habitat maintenance, pollination and seed dispersal, soil formation and protection, microbiome, body function, and *working conditions*.

Figures 1-4 show our proposal for One Health in a socioecological system network. In a state-effect exposure, the nodes represent the state, the arrows represent *effects* (positive or negative), and the *exposure* is illustrated by an earth drawn in the background, where everything is happening simultaneously.

1.1.4. Actions

Actions mean any intervention that affects the system, in this case, our One Health in the socio-ecological system. All actions will improve its excellent functioning. We suggest actions that can be applied in the central nodes from different perspectives. We must enhance environmental research and education focusing on pollutants, Nature-based Solutions (NbS), One Health promotion, environmental education, sustainability landscapes, food systems, and smart cities (see Table 1-6). This part will be extensively developed in the living lab.

Table 1-6. Possible types of actions

Action	Description
Scientific Research and Innovation	Research and innovation are fundamental processes that drive knowledge and technological advancement. Research involves systematic investigation to discover new information and understand phenomena,

	often through hypothesis testing, data collection, and analysis, leading to documented findings. Innovation, on the other hand, is the application of creative ideas and discoveries from research into practical solutions, resulting in new products, services, or processes that add value. While research provides the necessary foundation of knowledge, innovation translates this knowledge into tangible benefits, fueling progress across various sectors. Together, they form a cycle of continuous improvement and societal development (OCDE, 2018; National Science Foundation, n.d.)
Environmental education	We agree with Ihobe's Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) definition, which enables people to alter their thinking and actions towards a sustainable future. This educational process encourages individuals to examine environmental challenges, participate in problem-solving, and act to enhance the environment. Consequently, people gain a greater insight into environmental problems and acquire the necessary skills to make knowledgeable and ethical choices. https://www.ihobe.eus/environmental-education
Nature-based solutions	Address societal challenges through actions to protect, sustainably manage and restore natural and modified ecosystems, benefiting people and nature simultaneously. They target major challenges like climate change, disaster risk reduction, food and water security, biodiversity loss, and human health, and they are critical to sustainable development. https://iucn.org/our-work/nature-based-solutions
e-One health promotion	This perspective would generate stability, harmony, and resilience—improving our world (De Leeuw et al., 2024). These authors propose developments squarely in two crucial perspectives: 1) health promotion and salutogenic one and 2) a focus on the spaces, places, and contexts where a healthy One Health plays out (De Leeuw, 2021).
Landscape sustainability	Landscape sustainability is the capacity of a landscape to consistently provide long-term, landscape-specific ecosystem services essential for maintaining and improving human well-being in a regional context and despite environmental and sociocultural changes (Wu, 2013)
Food systems	Refers to all the elements and activities related to producing and consuming food and their effects, including economic, health, and environmental outcomes. https://www.oecd.org/food-systems/understanding/
Smart and green cities	Organic urban systems integrate data, resources, policies, and people through technology to achieve a conscious, environmentally sustainable development in transportation, buildings, energy, open spaces, water, and waste management areas (Bashirpour Bonab et al., 2023).
Science Communication	Science communication is the practice of informing, raising awareness of science-related topics, and getting involved with audiences that include, at least in part, people from outside the science community.

Figure 1-5 shows all these elements articulated in a DP(SEE)A for the One Health model in a socio-ecological system.

Figure 1.5. One health in a socio-ecological system with pressures and actions

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2. Pressures that affect the health of Northern Spain's Coastal-Land Socio-Ecological Systems

Before focusing on northern Spain, we reviewed the literature to understand the most critical pressures in a coastal land socioecological system. In this review, we found that the most critical pressures are pollutants (nutrients, eutrophication, pesticides, organic pollutants, heavy metals, oil spills, personal care products, debris, litter, plastics, harmful algal blooms and pathogens), fisheries/aquaculture exploitation; non-indigenous species; habitat degradation; freshwater diversions, detours or dams; infrastructure and urbanisation; ports and shipping traffic; climate variability and climate change, finally agriculture, forestry and other land use (Annexe 2-1).

Then, we followed with an analysis of the One Health vision or approach in Spain, which is the first part of this chapter. After that, as we found very few bibliographic references to One Health in northern Spain, we conducted a literature review using keywords such as "health or illness" (elaborated as explained in section 2.2) caused by multiple pressures in Asturias, Cantabria, and the Basque Country communities.

2.1 Context in Spain

In Spain, as throughout Western Europe, training and research activities using the "One Health" approach was initiated between 2014 - 2016 when the concept started to be increasingly recognised by policymakers and researchers, and it focused on infectious diseases (Sikkema & Koopmans, 2016).

The Spanish National Plan against Antibiotic Resistance (PRAN, for its acronym in Spanish) was approved in 2014 by the Interterritorial Council of the National Health System and by the Intersectoral Conference on Agriculture in response to the European Commission Communication of 17 November 2011. This plan includes six strategies to combat antibiotic resistance and to ensure, for as long as possible, continuity of successful treatment of bacterial disease with effective and safe medicines used responsibly and accessible to all who need them (Muñoz-Madero et al., 2016). The PRAN 2022-2024 was published in September 2022.

We conducted a Scopus review to learn about the One Health literature in watersheds. From 2010 to 2023, we found 108 One Health documents in Spain. However, none of the documents are related to watersheds, catchments, or basins.

According to our review, recent studies have highlighted the complex interplay between human, animal, and environmental health, particularly in zoonotic diseases and antimicrobial resistance. One notable case involved the detection of rabies in Toledo, underscoring the persistent threat of this lethal virus (Pérez De Diego et al., 2015). Research has also focused on zoonoses at the human-livestock-wildlife interface, such as *Coxiella burnetii*, the causative agent of Q fever (Candela et al., 2017). Clonal diversity analysis of extended-spectrum β -lactamase (ESBL)-producing *E. coli* isolated from various sources, including environmental, human, and food samples, has further illuminated the widespread nature of antimicrobial resistance (Carvalho et al., 2020; Ojer-Usoz et al., 2017).

From 2020 onwards, there has been an increase in studies addressing various health threats. Research on leishmaniasis has expanded, reflecting growing concerns about this parasitic disease (Martín-Sánchez et al., 2020). The prevalence of antimicrobial-resistant bacteria in vultures (Blanco et al., 2020) and wild boars (Torres et al., 2020) has been examined, highlighting wildlife as reservoirs of resistance. Investigations into drug usage in the human and livestock sectors and its impact on foodborne antimicrobial resistance have also been significant (Mesa Varona et al., 2020).

Additionally, studies have assessed the occurrence and distribution of ESBL-resistant enterobacteria and antimicrobial resistance genes in wild European hedgehogs (Garcias et al., 2021) and the presence of zoonotic intestinal protozoans in urban rat populations in Barcelona (Galán-Puchades et al., 2021). The carriage of *Salmonella spp.* by pet reptiles in Valencia's pet shops and households (Marin et al., 2021) and within the Spanish food chain (Rodriguez et al., 2023) has been documented. Furthermore, research has indicated a high prevalence of obesity among dog owners in the Canary Islands, suggesting a link between pet and owner health (Suarez et al., 2022). Other studies have reported the first instances of the mosquito *Culicoides caucoliberensis* affecting wildlife and livestock (Gonzalez et al., 2023) and *Mycobacterium caprae* infection in humans related to goat farms in Almeria (Martínez-Lirola et al., 2023).

Looking for a little more information, we found that in May of 2023, veterinarians and medical doctors in a round table developed in the IV Congress of International cooperation a decalogue of pandemics and One Health: (1) consolidating the idea of "one world, one health" that protects ecosystems, fauna, flora and humans at the same time, (2) the high population density and unprecedented mobility of the population promote an infinite number of routes of contagion; (3) pandemics occur when we open breaches in nature in an uncontrolled manner (trade, hunting, consumption of wild animals, deforestation and overexploitation of livestock); (4) to inventory potential emerging viruses and to know the favourable environmental conditions that promote their jump to animals, plants, and from there, to humans; (5) prevention of events, coordinating wildlife, environment and human, animal and plant health sectors; (6) management of ecosystems so that the next infectious agent emerges as late as possible; (7) limit the interaction between domestic species and humans in stressful environments (market, high density of animals); (8) change human habits and customs; (9) establishment, improvement and reinforcement of global epidemiological surveillance systems; (10) maintaining the environment in good condition (mitigating climate change, reducing biodiversity loss and various forms of pollution) (Portal Veterinaria, 2023).

However, this first literature review reveals that current research remains predominantly sector-specific or discipline-focused, with a notable scarcity of inter- or trans-disciplinary studies. There is a significant gap in research that comprehensively analyses and articulates the

interconnections between human, animal, and ecosystem health, particularly from a watershed perspective. Additionally, we did not find studies that explicitly discuss the "One Health" approach using its latest definition. Only one study links human-animal relationships and, recently, the risk of drugs in the environment. We suggest that future studies adopt a systemic and transdisciplinary approach to effectively address these complex health challenges.

2.2. Pressures in Northern Spain

We started looking for literature about One Health in northern Spain; we refer to Asturias, Cantabria and the Basque Country. Our research found that after 2010, research in Asturias advanced significantly, focusing on the interconnections between human and animal health. One of the pioneering studies was conducted by Palacios et al. (2016), which established a collaborative model between human and animal health professionals to precisely map the transmission of *Mycobacterium bovis* at the human-animal interface. This was followed by a study by Espí et al. (2021), which examined the seroprevalence of *Coxiella burnetii* in domestic ruminants and wild ungulates and investigated Q fever in humans in close contact with wildlife and livestock. Additionally, Vázquez et al. (2022) assessed the prevalence of colistin-resistant non-typhoid serovars of *Salmonella enterica* in food-borne isolates from 2014 to 2019, establishing this resistance's genetic basis and transferability. Moreover, Gallego et al. (2009) reported the first case of *Francisella tularensis* in humans in Asturias, tracing the infection to a patient who fed rabbits at her country house, indicating a likely vector.

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, Domingo-Echaburu et al. (2022) conducted a study in Vitoria-Gasteiz, measuring the concentrations of various drugs (hydroxychloroquine, lopinavir, ritonavir, cisatracurium, and azithromycin) in the influent and effluent of the city's wastewater treatment plant to estimate the potential environmental risk. This study is notably the only reference in the Scopus database concerning pollution and the One Health approach in northern Spain, highlighting the need for further research.

Considering the little information about one health in northern Spain and almost none based on the new definition of 2022, using the Scopus database, we decided to do a literature review where our keywords were "health or illness", different types of pressures and the geographical area we were interested in. We used the keywords as shown below:

<p>Health OR Disease OR Illness</p>	<p>AND</p> <p>Pollution: Nutrients OR eutrophication OR Pesticides OR Organic pollutants OR Heavy metals OR Oil spills OR Personal care products OR Debris OR litter OR plastics OR Harmful algal blooms OR HAB OR Pathogens</p> <p>Fisheries OR aquaculture exploitation</p> <p>Non-indigenous OR Introduced OR exotic AND species</p> <p>Habitat OR ecosystem AND loss OR alteration OR degradation OR fragmentation</p> <p>Freshwater OR river AND diversions OR detours OR dams OR infrastructure OR urbanisation</p> <p>Coastal AND construction OR infrastructure</p> <p>Ports OR shipping traffic</p> <p>Climate OR variability AND change</p>	<p>AND</p> <p>Asturian OR Asturias OR Cantabrian OR Cantabria OR Basque OR Biscay OR Vizcaya OR Gipuzkoa</p>
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agriculture OR livestock OR agriculture, forestry and other land use OR AFOLU

We found 322 articles in February of 2024, between 2010 and 2023. Figure 2-1 a, shows how publications on these topics have increased since 2016. In Figure b, we see that three authors stand out with 8 publications each: Ibarluzea, Iturritxa and Marigómez. In figure c, we see that the authors have collaboration networks with authors from multiple parts of the world, mainly other European countries. However, several Latin American countries also stand out. Figures d and e show that most publications are related to research in medicine, some differentiated by gender or age ranges. This second group focuses more on environmental or genetic monitoring in humans or animals.

Figure 2-1. (a) Number of documents per year; (b) authors production; (c) countries collaboration; (d) keywords networks; and (e) subject area associated with health or disease in the north of Spain.

2.1. Pollution

In this topic, we found that the intricate relationship between human health, environmental health, and the health of non-human organisms is well-documented in scientific literature. Numerous studies have demonstrated that various pollutants, including particulate matter (PM), metals, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), polychlorinated dibenzodioxins (PCDDs), and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), significantly impact respiratory health. Additionally, ingested pollutants like metals, pesticides, microplastics, bisphenols, and per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) pose serious health risks. Furthermore, care products containing toxic substances such as parabens, benzophenols, and phthalates contribute to the contamination. Research conducted in different regions, including Gipuzkoa and the Basque Country, highlights the severity and distribution of these pollutants. Industrial activities, urban development, and inadequate wastewater treatment infrastructures exacerbate these issues, leading to significant environmental and health challenges. Addressing these problems requires a holistic approach, integrating biological remediation methods to restore soil health and mitigate pollution. We are going to show principal ideas.

- ✓ **Relationship Between Human Health and Environmental Pollutants.** Many studies have shown the relationship between human health and environmental pollutants. Major respiratory-related problems are attributed to particulate matter (PM), metals, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), polychlorinated dibenzodioxins (PCDDs), and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs). Pollutants that may be ingested include metals, pesticides, microplastics, bisphenols, and per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). Additionally, care products containing toxic substances such as parabens, benzophenols, and phthalates are significant contributors (Ibarluzea Maurolagoitia, 2019).
- ✓ **Pollutant Concentrations in Gipuzkoa.** A study conducted in Gipuzkoa between 2017 and 2019 by Biodonostia found that Ordizia had the highest concentrations of PM_{2.5}, metals, and PAHs. Notably, the nickel (Ni) concentrations in the town exceeded and even doubled the threshold value set by Directive 102/2011 during the study period. Seasonal variations were observed for PAHs and PCDD/Fs, with higher values in autumn and winter. Moreover, dioxin concentrations were higher on weekdays than at weekends (Ibarluzea Maurolagoitia, 2019).
- ✓ **Impact of Industrial and Maritime Activities on Air Quality.** In marinas and ports with the diffuse influence of several industries and a power plant, Morillas et al. (2019) used a self-made passive sampler (SMPS) to detect the presence of heavy metals in PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} near the Basque Government environmental station. They found that the highest load of metal particulate matter originated from ship traffic, road traffic, and surrounding industries. This finding is critical given the Basque Country's 28 ports, which include three commercial harbours, six marinas, and 19 combined fishing and marina ports.
- ✓ **Environmental Assessment of the Northern Coast of Spain.** The Basque Country is a highly industrialised region, with significant industrial activities concentrated along the Nervion River. Despite the decline in large polluting iron and steel plants, there has been an increase in petrochemical and power industries. Díez et al. (2000) conducted an environmental assessment of the northern coast of Spain, revealing gross organic enrichment, oxygen depletion of the water, anaerobic sediment conditions, and high concentrations of heavy metals and trace organic pollutants (PAHs, PCBs, and pesticides), which have led to an extreme reduction of fauna in the Nervion estuary in

Bilbao. Furthermore, they identified deficits in the wastewater treatment infrastructure of coastal cities.

In 2006, Borja and colleagues constructed a checklist of estuarine and marine pressures for the Basque Country to assess the European Water Framework Directive's pressures and impacts (table 2).

Table 2-1. Estuarine and marine pressure checklist (Borja et al., 2006)

Pollution	Changes in morphology	Alteration of the hydrological regime
Urban discharges Stormwater and overflow Untreated and treated outfall Untreated and treated submarine outfall Diffuse source	Land reclamation (urban) Land reclamation (industrial) Land reclamation (harbours) Shore reinforcement / dyke Marinas Fishing harbours	Water abstraction Hydroenergy Aquaculture Thalassotherapy Flow regulation Sea walls Jetties River obstacles (barriers or dams)
Industrial discharges Gas / Petrol Chemicals Pulp, paper Textiles Food processing Brewing / distilling Power generation Wood / timber treatment Construction Iron / Steel Industrial mixed discharges Leachates	Permanent anchorage Occasional anchorage Dredging activities Dumping of dredged sediments Signposting Engineering works Infrastructure Bridges Tide mills Submarine ways Tunnel Promenade	Restoration and engineering activities
Agriculture / farm discharges Point source Diffuse source		Biology and uses Resource exploitation Fishing / angling Shellfishing Algae exploitation Changes in biodiversity Introduced species Introduced diseases
Aquaculture discharges Mining discharges Gas and oil Sand extraction Storage (slag, rubbish) lixiviation Maritime transport discharges Contaminated land Polluted sediments Clinker disposal Military sites Shipyard and boat repair Oil pump		Recreation Beaches Saltwater pools

- ✓ **Impact of Human Activities on Estuarine Ecosystems.** Human activities such as land reclamation for agriculture, urban development, industrial activities, and port developments have drastically reduced the size and quality of estuarine waters (Cearreta et al., 2004). The primary sources of pollution include urban, industrial, and agricultural waste, runoff, atmospheric deposition, dredging, port activities, and maritime traffic (Cajaraville et al., 2016).
- ✓ **Restoring Soil Health Using Biological Methods.** Given that human activities directly affect soils, prioritising actions to restore soil health and integrity is crucial as part of a One Health approach. Biological methods such as phytoremediation, bioremediation, and vermiremediation are cost-effective and environmentally friendly but require more time. Articulating these methods using plants, bacteria, and earthworms has shown

highly efficient recovery results, as demonstrated in a landfill contaminated with sewage sludge in Gernika-Lumo, Basque Country (Urionabarrenetxea et al., 2021).

Nutrients and eutrophication

Since 1950, the increase in nitrogen and phosphorus loads in the Biscay Bay inland seas has significantly altered coastal marine ecosystems, leading to eutrophication in some areas (Lefebvre & Devreker, 2020). This nutrient enrichment, particularly severe in the watersheds of developed countries, has profound implications for marine health. Studies in Northern Spain, especially around the Nervión and Oiartzun estuaries, highlight the high nutrient input from dense human settlements (L. Garmendia et al., 2011). Various methodologies, including CMEMS and 3D ecological models, have been employed to classify and understand the extent of eutrophication and its sources. Research has also focused on the effects of wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) and the variability of phytoplankton groups, providing insights into the anthropogenic pressures on these ecosystems. We found four principal topics:

- ✓ **Impact of Nutrient Enrichment on Coastal Marine Ecosystems.** Nutrient enrichment has intensified in the coastal waters of developed countries. For example, in the watersheds of Biscay Bay, the nutrient loads were 1175 kgN/km²/year; nutrient enrichment has increased even more severely in coastal waters of developed countries (Billen et al., 2011). Using CMEMS-Phosphate-Nitrate-Silica-Chlorophyll and Water-Transparency models, Sarelli et al. (2018) classified the seas around the Iberian-Biscay-Irish regions into four categories: non-problematic areas, problem areas, and areas with a tendency or possibility of eutrophication events. They found eutrophication problems, particularly in waters near high population density areas, river estuaries, and shallow waters.
- ✓ **Response to Freshwater River Discharge and Nutrient Loads.** Studies analysing the response to short-term changes in freshwater river discharge and nutrient loads from the Gernika Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP) in the shallow macro tidal estuary of Urdaibai showed that WWTP effluents, combined with the highest river discharge, lower the phytoplankton concentration (García et al., 2010). Furthermore, WWTP effluents and emissary discharges have been identified as the primary sources of contamination in the Cantabrian Sea (Sánchez-Avila et al., 2013).
- ✓ **Phytoplankton Variability and Anthropogenic Pressures.** Research has also focused on the spatial and seasonal variability of three general phytoplankton groups: diatoms, dinoflagellates, and others. Studies using a spatial gradient in fractionated chlorophyll "a" have provided valuable information on anthropogenic pressures (L. Garmendia et al., 2011; Gohin et al., 2019; Maguer et al., 2009). Additionally, 3D ecological models have been employed to estimate the contributions of various sources (riverine, oceanic, and atmospheric) to winter nitrate and phosphate marine concentrations (Ménesguen et al., 2018).

Pesticides

The relationship between human health and environmental pollutants has been extensively studied, particularly concerning the effects of endocrine-disrupting chemicals (EDCs) and other toxic substances. These pollutants, which include organic solvents, pesticides, and heavy metals, have been linked to various health outcomes such as low birth weight and small for gestational age infants. In Northern Spain, research has identified significant contaminants in

food and the environment, highlighting the need for continued monitoring and intervention. We found nine ideas, which are described below.

- ✓ **Effects on Human Health.** Studies suggest that mothers occupationally exposed to EDCs—particularly organic solvents, pesticides, and phthalates—are more likely to have infants with low birth weight (LBW; birthweight <2,500 g) or small for gestational age (SGA; birthweight <10th percentile for gestational age)(Birks et al., 2016; Shirangi et al., 2020). However, Ish et al. (2022) found limited evidence of an effect of maternal occupational exposures on ultrasound measures of foetal growth. They reported that specific occupational groups, such as women exposed to phthalates and domestic cleaners exposed to alkyl phenolic compounds (APCs), have a relatively significant burden of work-related EDC exposure. Another study evaluated the association between organophosphate pesticides (OC) concentrations in the serum of two cohorts of pregnant women from Gipuzkoa and Sabadell, including socioeconomic, reproductive, and dietary variables (Ibarluzea et al., 2011). Regarding OC effects on human health, Alvarez et al. (1993) evaluated greenhouse workers' exposure in the Basque Country.

PAHs in the air have been studied in two urban industrial areas of Gipuzkoa, with vehicular emissions being the predominant source (Oleagoitia et al., 2019). In humans, studies by García-Villarino et al. (2020, 2022) evidenced associations between specific persistent organic pollutants (POPs) and anogenital index in boys and girls aged four years, suggesting that pre/perinatal exposure to POPs has a feminising effect in males and a masculinising effect in females, altering genital development.

- ✓ **Food Contaminants and Dietary Exposure.** In the 1990s, studies analysed selected food contaminants, including heavy metals (mercury, lead, cadmium, and arsenic), organochlorine pesticides (HCB, HCH, DDT, DDE, TDE, dieldrin, aldrin, endrin, heptachlor, heptachlor epoxide, endosulfan, and methoxychlor), and selected trace element nutrients (zinc, selenium, and iron). Arsenic intake was much higher than estimated in other countries, and γ -HCH was detected at abnormally high levels in the bread group (Urieta et al., 1991, 1996). Another study evaluated three polychlorinated congeners in butter, eggs, and fish, finding none exceeded tolerance limits (Goñi et al., 1994). However, milk analysis near a waste incinerator had the highest Polychlorinated dibenzo-p-dioxins (PCDD) and polychlorinated dibenzofurans (PCDFS) ratio, and the PCDD/F average concentrations found in pasteurised commercial milk were lower than those found in raw milk (L. Ramos et al., 1997). Other studies identified and analysed levels of seven organochlorine pesticides in the adult population of Biscay (Zubero et al., 2010), finding higher levels in fish consumers and those consuming local produce (Zubero et al., 2015).
- ✓ **Pesticide Residues in Agriculture and Food.** Research has shown higher triazine levels in Galicia compared to Asturias (Santaeufemia et al., 2006), and the presence of organochlorine pesticides (HCB, α -HCCH, φ -HCCH, HEOD, DDT, TDE) and 34 PCB congeners in cattle (Blanco-Penedo et al., 2008). Studies also evaluated diets, contaminants, micro-toxins, pesticide residues, and food additives (Jalón González-Moreno, 2006). In unprocessed vegetables in the Basque Country, 56 active substances were detected, including fungicides and insecticides as the main pesticide types (Lemos et al., 2016).
- ✓ **Environmental Impact of Pesticides on Animals.** Studies identified various organic pollutants, including polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs), organophosphate pesticides (OPPs), polycyclic

aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), and pyrethroids in the body feathers of NW Spain feral pigeons (González-Gómez et al., 2020).

Research on Cantabrian fishes revealed organochlorine residues (Guitart et al., 2005), and analysis of fish muscle showed plastic-related products, pharmaceuticals, and pesticides or insect repellents (Musatadi et al., 2020). Studies also found a positive correlation between EDC levels (estrogenic hormones, polycyclic musks, bisphenol-A, phthalates, alkylphenols, and pesticides) and an intersex condition in thick-lip grey mullet populations in Basque estuaries (Bizarro et al., 2014; Ros et al., 2015). Persistent organic pollutants have been found in deep pelagic species, with PCBs predominating in fish and organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFASs), and PBDEs, showing highly variable concentrations among species (Munschy et al., 2022),

A study on diflubenzuron found aquatic invertebrates to be highly toxic to freshwater invertebrates, including marine/estuarine crustacea and molluscs (U.S. EPA, 1997). In another study, high levels of pollutants were detected in wild mussel populations near significant cities and industrialised areas of Cantabria (Bellas et al., 2014). Mussel tissues from the lower Bilbao estuary contained high levels of PAHs, PCBs, phthalate esters (PEs), butyltins, and metals (Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Hg, Mn, Ni, Pb, V, and Zn) (Bartolomé, Navarro, et al., 2010). Another study showed embryo growth inhibition and skeleton malformation in sea urchins exposed to toxicity from four WWTP effluents in Biscay (Mijangos et al., 2020).

- ✓ **Chemical Pollutants in Marine and Coastal Environments.** Research also pinpointed drivers of toxicity in the central wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) effluent entering the Bilbao estuary (Mijangos et al., 2020) and A Coruña (Rial et al., 2017) using sea urchin embryos. In Santander Bay, DDT in sediments was significantly correlated with OC's concentration on the northern Atlantic Spanish coast (Linares et al., 2006; Gómez et al., 2011).

Pharmaceuticals and personal care products (PPCPs)

The use of plants for the prevention and treatment of various physiological conditions and diseases dates back to the history of humankind. Phytotherapy, which involves using whole medicinal plants or their parts (such as flowers, leaves, and roots), their constituents (such as essential oils and extracts), and finished preparations (such as teas, tinctures, ointments, and capsules), has been a traditional and practical approach to health care. Conservationists and the pharmaceutical industry highly appreciate *Spain's Arnica montana L. (Asteraceae)*. A recent study provided detailed insights into the genetic diversity and structure of two populations of this plant in northern Spain, highlighting its importance and potential (Bouza et al., 2023). Concurrently, the environmental impact of pharmaceuticals and personal care products (PPCPs) has emerged as a critical concern. These compounds, capable of causing physiological effects in humans even at small doses, represent a significant group of environmental pollutants (Ebele et al., 2017). Research in the Adour estuary in the Basque Country has shown significant bioconcentration and biotransformation of contaminants of emerging concern in glass eels (*Anguilla anguilla*), with findings indicating high concentrations of antihypertensives and a reduced presence of fungicides, industrial chemicals, and herbicides (Alvarez-Mora et al., 2022). This intersection of phytotherapy and environmental science underscores the intricate balance between traditional medicine and modern environmental challenges.

Heavy metals and oil spills

Heavy metals, hydrocarbons, and other pollutants have long been a concern in northern Spain, affecting the environment and human health. The region's history of industrial activities, urban waste incineration, and significant oil spills has led to a complex web of contamination that scientists continue to study and address. Research highlights the presence of various heavy metals such as aluminium (Al), lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), and mercury (Hg), as well as the impact of urban waste incineration, industrial activities, and environmental accidents on local ecosystems and communities.

Studies on heavy metals in northern Spain have identified various sources and impacts. Urban solid waste incineration (SWI) emits heavy metals like lead, cadmium, chromium, and mercury. However, populations living near modern SWI plants do not show increased levels of these metals, except for detectable cadmium in their urine (Zubero et al., 2010). Lead, nickel, and chromium exposure from domestic water supply pipes has also been assessed in the Basque Country (Zaldua Etxabe et al., 2010). In Cantabria, manganese, nickel, and vanadium were identified as tracers in different locations (Ruiz et al., 2011).

Elevated cadmium and lead levels have been found in fish species in Biscay Bay (Mauffret et al., 2023). Medium-to-high-trophic level species, including crustaceans, sharks, and teleost fish, are susceptible to mercury bioaccumulation and biomagnification, as are harbor porpoises, which have died from infectious diseases linked to high levels of cadmium, mercury, selenium, and zinc (Mahfouz et al., 2014). Trophic indicators like fish are effective tools for assessing the impact of pollutants on ecosystems and health, important for fisheries and aquaculture management (Bourdaud et al., 2016).

The Nerbioi-Ibaizabal estuary in Bilbao experienced significant contamination between 1875 and 1975, including metals and metalloids (Garmendia et al., 2019). Mining activities have left mercury and arsenic in the sediments of the Asturian coasts, posing a risk if resuspended (García-Ordiales et al., 2020). Female shore crabs in Bilbao have been found with nickel, lead, mercury, and PCBs, linked to oil spills and industrial activities (Martín-Díaz et al., 2009). High concentrations of PAHs and trace metals like mercury, lead, and arsenic present a high risk to benthic organisms (Azaroff et al., 2021). Pollution from metals and hydrocarbons has significantly impacted the Bilbao estuary, exacerbated by accidents like the Prestige oil spill in 2002 off the Galician coast (Díez et al., 2009). The estuary has also been affected by emerging pollutants such as tributyltin and other organotin compounds, which act as endocrine disruptors (Bartolomé, Etxebarria, et al., 2010; Bizarro et al., 2014). Studies have shown high chromium and nickel levels in the Deba and Urola estuaries (Ramos et al., 1990). Still, a decrease in metal concentrations in mussels and oysters has been observed, coinciding with improvements in the most degraded estuaries (Solaun et al., 2013).

Infrastructure construction, industrial, and wastewater inputs, along with high-magnitude flood events, contribute significantly to the presence of zinc, copper, and chromium in the Deba River, with organic matter playing a major role in the uptake of these metals (Martínez-Santos et al., 2015). Oil spills, such as those from the Erika and Prestige tankers, have caused long-term environmental damage, affecting sea life, beaches, and seafood safety, with consequences felt for decades (NOAA, 2020). Maritime transport and port activities are major sources of oil pollution in coastal areas (Hecht, 1997).

The Biscay Bay has experienced significant oil spills, notably from the Erika in 1999 and the Prestige in 2002. These spills led to severe environmental stress and numerous studies on the impact of oil pollution on various species and ecosystems (Marigómez et al., 2013; Castège et al., 2014; Bilbao et al., 2010; Bustamante et al., 2010; Cajaraville et al., 2016). These events

underscore the need for ongoing monitoring and management to mitigate the effects of such environmental disasters.

Debris/litter/microplastic

Since 1950, global plastic production has been steadily increasing, significantly impacting the Bay of Biscay with rising levels of marine debris. Monitoring factors such as river flows, rainfall, wind, and waves are crucial for understanding the accumulation of debris. Consequently, local authorities seek cost-effective methods to reduce beach debris, especially during summer (Granado et al., 2019). This environmental concern extends to microplastics (MPs), which have been shown to bioaccumulate the food chain and pose risks to marine life and human health.

Research in the Bay of Biscay has demonstrated the transfer of microplastics in jellifying algae through various organisms, confirming bioaccumulation up the food chain from plankton to fur seals. Due to this accumulation, organisms at higher trophic levels show high toxicity rates (Bilbao-Kareaga et al., 2023). The presence of microplastics in both freshwater and marine ecosystems has been well-documented, posing a significant threat to biodiversity, community composition, and the health of organisms, including humans (Wang et al., 2020). Commercial species with economic value are not exempt from this issue, as microplastics have been found within them, affecting human health by altering the composition of the human colonic microbial community (Tamargo et al., 2022; Masiá et al., 2022; Volschenk et al., 2019).

In Asturias, studies on European glass eels (*Anguilla anguilla*) have revealed high levels of microplastic pollution, with some particles found outside the gastrointestinal tract, specifically in the dorsal muscle. Despite being critically endangered, this species is consumed by humans, raising health concerns (Menéndez et al., 2022). Additionally, mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) in Asturias show levels of microplastics that may pose a risk to human health upon ingestion (Masiá et al., 2022). These findings underscore the urgent need for effective monitoring and mitigation strategies to address microplastic pollution in marine environments.

Harmful algal blooms (HAB)

HAB presents significant environmental and health challenges in the Bay of Biscay and surrounding areas. Studies have identified key algal species contributing to HAB. In Cantabria, diatoms and cryptophytes have been identified as the main bloom taxa in most estuaries and coastal sites. The potentially toxic species *Pseudo-nitzschia* and *Chrysochromulina* were found in the highest concentrations (Seoane et al., 2012). Exceptional blooms of *Dinophysis acuminata* in the Bay of Biscay in 2012 were linked to anomalous upwelling during the previous winter (Batifoulier et al., 2013; Díaz et al., 2013).

The port of Bilbao faces a risk of invasion by the raphidophyte *Heterosigma akashiwo* through ballast water, highlighting the need for monitoring and preventive measures (Butrón et al., 2011). Predictive models, such as the hybrid PSO-SVM regression, are being developed to provide early warnings for HAB events (García-Nieto et al., 2015). In the Bay of San Lorenzo, algae blooms may originate from eutrophication in the Piles River delta and subsequent algae drift (García et al., 2010).

Pathogens

Finally, pathogen studies have revealed various threats in the region. Antibiotic resistance is a growing concern, with recent studies highlighting its prevalence (Vázquez et al., 2023). The transmission of *Brucella pinnipedialis* in bottlenose dolphins in Cantabria (Vargas-Castro et al., 2023) and Spanish goat encephalitis virus in goats (Balseiro et al., 2023) demonstrate the diverse impacts on animal health. Invasive fungi like *Cryphonectria parasitica* and *Fusarium circinatum* pose significant risks (Ahmad & Diez, 2023; Iturritxa et al., 2011). Additionally, *Aeromonas* spp. in hospitals (Ruiz de Alegría-Puig et al., 2023) and gastrointestinal infections (Elorza et al., 2020) further illustrate the widespread implications for public health.

Other studies have reported gastrointestinal parasites in brown bears in Cantabria (Costa et al., 2022), angular leaf spot caused by *Pseudocercospora griseola* in *Phaseolus vulgaris* in Asturias (Landeras et al., 2017), and the presence of *Salmonella* spp. and *Listeria monocytogenes* (Hurtado et al., 2017; Vallejo et al., 2022), and *Salmonella enterica* (Vázquez et al., 2022). The detection of *Mycoplasma conjunctivae* in wildlife and livestock in the Pyrenees (Fernández-Aguilar et al., 2017), vector-borne pathogens in dogs (Díaz-Regañón et al., 2020), and various *Fusarium* species (Aguayo et al., 2020; Słomińska-Durdasiak et al., 2020) emphasise the need for comprehensive pathogen monitoring and management strategies. A new host for *Lecanosticta acicola* and *Dothistroma septosporum* has also been identified, expanding the understanding of these pathogens' ecological impacts (Mesanza et al., 2021).

2.2. Habitat loss and alteration

Habitat loss in the Bay of Biscay and northern Spain significantly affects ecosystem health, biodiversity, and species distributions. Research has focused on terrestrial and aquatic environments, highlighting the impact of land use changes, climate change, and human activities such as forestry and fishing. Efforts are being made to understand and mitigate these impacts to preserve the ecological integrity of these regions. Studies addressing habitat loss have primarily been conducted in Spain and some French oceanic locations within the Bay of Biscay (Bolliet et al., 2014; Duros et al., 2017; Le Marchand et al., 2020). These studies cover a range of environments, from inland systems to estuaries, coasts, and oceans. While a few directly link habitat degradation to ecosystem health (n=9), most discuss terms like "environmental quality," "habitat integrity," and "ecosystem services. We found six supported ideas.

- ✓ **Impacts on Terrestrial Ecosystems in Northern Spain.** In northern Spain, particularly the Basque Country and Cantabria, forestry plantations have been common since the 20th century, introducing non-native species such as *Pinus* spp. and *Eucalyptus* spp. for timber production (Nogués & Cabarga-Varona, 2014; Orrantia et al., 2019; Rodríguez-Loinaz et al., 2011). These plantations have led to the fragmentation and reduction of native forest quality, affecting biodiversity and habitat connectivity (Gurrutxaga & Saura, 2014; Orrantia et al., 2019). Studies on habitat connectivity and land use highlight the need for strategic planning to restore ecological networks (Ruiz-González et al., 2014). Other valuable ecosystems, such as blanket bogs and heathlands, are also threatened by grazing and trampling pressures (Chico et al., 2019; Fraser & Rosa García, 2018).
- ✓ **Climatic Influences on Habitat.** Climate change is a critical factor shaping current and future habitats. Increased drought severity and frequency are expected to reduce suitable habitats for characteristic forest species in the Cantabrian mountains, impacting associated fauna such as the brown bear (Castaño-Santamaría et al., 2019; Penteriani et al., 2019).

- ✓ **Invasive Species and Habitat Alteration.** The introduction of exotic species and changes in land use have altered ecosystem trophic structures and critical processes like seed dispersal (Clavero et al., 2004; García et al., 2010). Establishing invasive species and habitat fragmentation further exacerbates these issues, reducing habitat richness and ecosystem functioning.

- ✓ **Terrestrial and Aquatic System Linkages.** Habitat loss also affects aquatic systems through soil erosion and pollution. Deforestation and altered forest structures increase soil erosion, affecting water quality and aquatic biota (Hernández-Romero et al., 2022). Mining activities in river basins, such as the Nalón River, have led to heavy metal pollution, impacting aquatic communities (Costas et al., 2018).

- ✓ **Estuarine and Coastal Habitat Degradation.** Estuaries in northern Spain face hydromorphological changes, invasive species, and pollution, affecting their ecosystem integrity (Ondiviela et al., 2015). Non-indigenous plants, like *Baccharis halimifolia*, further reduce habitat richness (Caño et al., 2013). Valuable coastal habitats such as salt marshes and seagrass meadows are declining due to local and regional drivers, including sea-level rise and hydrodynamic stress (Aranda et al., 2022; Valle et al., 2011).

- ✓ **Marine Habitat Loss.** Fishing activities and climate change impact marine habitats in the Bay of Biscay. Fishing disturbs seabed habitats and contributes to species bycatch (Bastardie et al., 2021). Climate change and rising sea temperatures are expected to shift species ranges, introducing potentially invasive species (Le Marchand et al., 2020). Studies have also assessed the health of specific marine habitats, such as the Capbreon Canyon and the "El Cachucho" Marine Protected Area, highlighting the need for continued monitoring and conservation efforts (Prado et al., 2019a, 2019b, 2021).

By understanding the multifaceted impacts of habitat loss and implementing strategic conservation measures, the ecological integrity of the Bay of Biscay and northern Spain can be better preserved for future generations.

2.3. Non-indigenous species

Invasive species are a significant environmental concern in the Bay of Biscay, particularly in northern Spain, where the region's mild climate, abundant rainfall, and anthropogenic disturbances provide favourable conditions for their proliferation. These non-indigenous species (NIS) affect various habitats, including terrestrial, freshwater aquatic, brackish, and marine environments. Here we explore the extent and impact of invasive species in these habitats, highlighting specific examples and their ecological consequences.

In terrestrial habitats in Northern Spain, exotic plants were initially introduced along roadsides and urban areas but have spread to freshwater bodies and coastal regions. These plants, mainly from the Mediterranean and North America, were introduced accidentally or for ornamental purposes (Campos, 2010; Campos & Herrera, 1997, 2000, 2009). Not all alien plants are invasive, but species like *Carpobrotus edulis*, *Stenotaphrum secundatum*, *Spartina patens*, *Paspalum vaginatum*, and *Baccharis halimifolia* have significant negative impacts on native flora and ecosystems, particularly in littoral habitats (Campos & Herrera, 2009). For example, *Baccharis halimifolia*, an invasive shrub, is one of the 20 most harmful invasive species in the Bay of Biscay's estuaries. Introduced in the 17th century for ornamental purposes, this North American native

species has colonised "Atlantic salt meadows," replacing native sub-halophilous communities dominated by *Juncus maritimus* (Caño et al., 2013, 2014). Its spread affects biological diversity, migratory birds, and the geomorphological dynamics of estuaries. It also poses health risks as an allergenic species, a refuge for mosquito larvae, and a cardiotoxic plant for livestock (Gobierno Vasco, 2014).

In forest ecosystems, particularly the original Querco-Fagetea communities, resist invasion. However, significant alterations have allowed the successful introduction of some non-indigenous species. Woody species like *Robinia pseudoacacia*, *Populus x canadiensis*, *Platanus hispanica*, and *Pterocarya stenoptera*, initially introduced for ornamental purposes, have spread, replacing native alder forests in some areas (Liendo, Campos, et al., 2016). Additionally, exotic tree plantations of *Pinus radiata* and *Eucalyptus* sp., introduced for timber production, now cover large areas, reducing native forest cover and biodiversity (Rodríguez-Loinaz et al., 2011; Palacios-Agundez et al., 2014).

Exotic tree plantations reduce biodiversity and carbon storage capacity compared to native forests. They alter macrofungal diversity, contribute to soil and nutrient loss, siltation of streams, and habitat fragmentation for aquatic and terrestrial species (Aihartza et al., 2003; Goiti et al., 2003; Graça et al., 2002; Sarrionandia et al., 2015). For example, the endangered bat *Rhinolophus euryale* prefers native forests over pine plantations, likely due to prey reduction from pest control measures in the plantations (Aihartza et al., 2003). Eucalyptus plantations also alter natural processes, such as nutrient cycles in streams (Graça et al., 2002), and increase disease outbreaks, introducing new pathogens like *Fusarium circinatum* (Iturrutxa et al., 2011) and *Candidatus Pythoplasma mali*, agent of apple proliferation in apple orchards, and transmitted through the alien psyllids *Ctenarytaina eucalypti* and *Ctenarytaina spatulata*, introduced through eucalyptus plantations (Rosa García et al., 2014).

NIS also impact the health of native organisms and livestock. Chestnut blight fungus (*Cryphonectria parasitica*) and the North American woodwasp (*Urocerus albiornis*) have damaged forests (González-Varela et al., 2011; Goldarazena, 2015). Livestock diseases, such as the Bluetongue virus introduced by insects and invasive mosquitoes like *Aedes albopictus*, pose significant risks to human and animal health (García-Lastra et al., 2012; Goiri et al., 2020).

Introducing fish species for commercial and recreational purposes has negatively impacted native amphibians and other aquatic life in freshwater ecosystems (Braña et al., 1996; Orizaola & Braña, 2006). Species like the crayfish (*Pacifastacus leniusculus*) and the American mink (*Mustela vison*) further disrupt these habitats, competing with and preying on native species (Rallo et al., 2001; Lecis et al., 2008).

Climate change and increasing sea surface temperatures are expected to facilitate the northward expansion of tropical and subtropical species into the Bay of Biscay. Coastal habitats are particularly vulnerable to NIS due to human activities such as marine transport and aquaculture (Borja et al., 2011; Borrell et al., 2018). Notably, not all NIS entirely replace native species; for example, introducing the Indo-Pacific clam *Ruditapes philippinarum* has resulted in coexistence with the native European carpet shell clam despite genetic hybridisation concerns (Juanes et al., 2012; Bidegain et al., 2015). Other aquaculture-related introductions include the oyster *Crassostrea gigas* and mollusc *Ensis directus*, which have facilitated the spread of other NIS like the American slipper limpet *Crepidula fornicata* (Borrell et al., 2018; Miralles et al., 2019).

On the other hand, marine transport and shipping activities, mainly through ballast water and hull fouling, are significant pathways for introducing species into estuaries and coasts. Studies have identified harmful algae in ballast water, such as *Pseudo-nitzschia galaxiae* and *Heterosigma*

akashiwo, which produce neurotoxins and cause fish kills, respectively (Ardura et al., 2020). Ports and marinas are hotspots for NIS, with the Nervión Estuary near the harbour of Bilbao showing a significant presence of alien species following port expansion (Zorita et al., 2013). Benthic organisms like *Pseudopoludora paucibranchiata* and *Monocorophium acherusicum* are common soft-bottom alien species in these polluted areas.

The establishment of alien zooplankton species such as *Acartia tonsa*, *Oithona davisae*, and *Pseudodiaptomus marinus* in the brackish waters of the Bilbao estuary highlights the opportunistic nature of these species in colonising degraded environments (Barroeta et al., 2022; Villate et al., 2018). Other exotic benthic organisms likely introduced through ballast water and hull fouling include *Theora lubrica*, *Limnoperna securis*, *Austrominus modestus*, *Ficopomtus enigmaticus*, and *Polydora triglanda*, as documented in ports across Asturias (Adarraga & Martínez, 2011, 2012; Borrell et al., 2017).

Macroalgae exhibit a high proportion of non-indigenous species, partly due to climate change and coastal pollution. Species like *Asparagopsis armata*, *Grateloupia imbricata*, *Grateloupia turuturu*, *Pachymeniopsis gargiuloi*, and *Undaria pinnatifida* have been recorded (Diez et al., 2012; Montes et al., 2016, 2017). While some exotic species coexist with native ones, others, such as *Codium fragile*, increase under environmental stress due to their tolerance and opportunism (García et al., 2018; Rojo et al., 2014).

Marine litter serves as a fomite for NIS, creating diverse habitats for species like *Balanus trigonus*, *Magallana gigas*, *Austrominus modestus*, *Amphibalanus mhirte*, and *Sargassum muticum* (Fernandez et al., 2022; Miralles et al., 2018a; Ibabe et al., 2020). Studies indicate that marine litter contains higher species densities than substrates from ports or beaches, posing a risk of bioaccumulation and altering ecosystems.

Despite the growing presence of NIS and their impacts, public awareness remains low. Effective management of species invasions requires early detection, which is challenging at low abundances. Citizen science can be crucial in monitoring and controlling NIS introductions (Clusa et al., 2018). Surveys in Asturias reveal that while local inhabitants recognise the harmful effects of NIS, they struggle to identify exotic species (Ibabe et al., 2020b). Thus, campaigns to disseminate scientific knowledge and enhance public awareness through visual and cognitive approaches are essential (Clusa et al., 2018; Ibabe et al., 2020b).

We include two useful tables for Northern Spain. Tables 2-2 include reported non-indigenous species, habitat type, status, location, and bibliographic references. Moreover, Tables 2-3 include harmful non-indigenous or associated species and use NIS as vectors in the North of Spain, including status, vector, location, affected organism, health impact, and bibliographic references.

Table 2-2. Non-indigenous species reported in Northern Spain.

Habitat	Phylum	Species	Status	Location	Reference
Terrestrial	Arthropoda	<i>Aedes albopictus</i>	Invasive	Basque Country	Goiri et al., (2020)
		<i>Ctenarytaina eucalyptii</i> , <i>C. spatulata</i>	NIS	Asturias	Rosa-García et al., (2013)
		<i>Urocerus albicornis</i>	NIS	Basque Country	Goldarazena et al., (2015)
	Ascomycota	<i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i>	Invasive	Asturias	González-Varela et al., (2011)
		<i>Fusarium circinatum</i>	NIS	Basque Country	Iturriza et al., (2011)
	Chordata	<i>Podarcis sicula</i>	NIS	Cantabria	Silva-Rocha et al., (2012)
	Duplornaviricota	<i>Obrivirus</i>	NIS	Basque Country	García-Lastra et al., (2012)
	Magnoliophyta	<i>Eucalyptus</i> spp.	NIS	Basque Country, Cantabria	Palacios-Agundez et al., 2014, Aihartza et al., 2003, Rodríguez-Loinaz et al., 2011, 2013, Goiti et al., 2003, Chauvet et al., 1997, Graça et al., 2022, Nogués et al., 2014
	Pinophyta	<i>Pinus radiata</i>	NIS	Basque Country, Cantabria	Palacios-Agundez et al., 2014, Onandia et al., 2013, Aihartza et al., 2003, Rodríguez-Loinaz et al., 2011, 2013, Goiti et al., 2003, Sarrionandia et al., 2015, Nogués et al., 2014
	Various	37 most frequent invasive alien plant	Invasive	Basque country	Campos et al., (2016)
130 taxa of plants in riparian habitats		NIS	Basque Country, Cantabria	Liendo et al., (2016a)	
9 plants in riparian habitats		NIS	Basque Country, Cantabria	Liendo et al., (2016b)	
Freshwater	Arthropoda	<i>Pacifastacus leniusculus</i>	NIS	Basque Country, Gijon	Rallo et al., (2001), Ibabe et al., (2020a)
	Chordata	4 fish of recreational interest	NIS	Asturias	Fernández et al., (2019)
		5 fish in lake mountains (Table 1)	NIS, Cryptogenic	Cantabrian Mountain Range	Braña et al., (1996)
		9 fish in rivers	NIS	Asturias	Clusa et al., (2018)
Estuarine	Arthropoda	3 copepods in estuary	NIS, Invasive	Basque Country	Villarte et al., 2017, 2018, Uriarte et al., 2016, Barroeta et al., 2020, 2022
	Arthropoda and Mollusca	5 bivalves, gastropods and crustacean	NIS	Asturias	Borrell et al., (2018)
	Foraminifera	19 foraminifera	NIS	Cantabria	Rodríguez-Lazaro et al., (2013)
		28 foraminifera	NIS	Cantabria	Pascual et al., (2019)
	Magnoliophyta	<i>Baccharis halimifolia</i>	Invasive	Europe (North Spain)	Caño et al., (2013)
	Mollusca	<i>Limnoperna securis</i>	NIS	Bay of Biscay	Adarraga and Martínez (2012)
		<i>Musculista senhousia</i>	NIS	Bidasoa estuary	Bachelet et al., (2009)
		<i>Theora lubrica</i>	NIS	Basque Country	Adarraga and Martínez (2011)
Spermatophyta	<i>Spartina alterniflor</i>	NIS	Basque Country	Benito and Onandia (1991)	
Various	23 marine benthic organisms	NIS	Basque Country	Zortia et al., (2013)	
Marine	Annelida	<i>Boccardia proboscidea</i> , <i>B. semibranchial</i>	NIS	Basque Country	Martinez et al., (2016)
	Annelida, Arthropoda	3 polychaeta and crustacea	Invasive	Asturias	Borrell et al., (2017)
	Arthropoda	<i>Hemigrapsus penicillatus</i>	NIS	North of Spain	Noël et al., (1997), Gollasch (1999)
	Chlorophyta	<i>Codium fragile</i> ssp. <i>Fragile</i>	NIS	North of Spain	García et al., (2018)
	Cnidaria	<i>Eucheilota menoni</i>	NIS	North of Spain	Altuna (2009)

Habitat	Phylum	Species	Status	Location	Reference
Various	Mollusca	<i>Anadara transversa</i>	NIS	Bay of Biscay	Fernández-Rodríguez et al., (2016)
		<i>Crassostrea gigas</i> , <i>Ensis directus</i>	Invasive	Asturias	Semeraro et al., (2015)
		<i>Crepidula fornicata</i>	invasive	North of Spain	Miralles et al., (2019)
		<i>Ruditapes philippinarum</i>	invasive	Asturias	Habtemariam et al., (2015)
		4 bivalva and gastropoda (Table II)	NIS, Cryptogenic and Invasive	Asturias	Pejovic et al., (2016)
	Ochrophyta	<i>Pacifastacus leniusculus</i> , <i>Sargassum muticum</i>	invasive	Gijon	Ibabe et al., (2020a)
		<i>Undaria pinnatifida</i>	NIS	North of Spain	Báez et al., (2010), Peteiro et al., (2008)
	Rhodophyta	<i>Asparagopsis armata</i>	NIS	North of Spain	Ramos et al., (2020), Diez et al., (2012)
		<i>Grateloupia imbricata</i>	NIS	Gijon	Montes et al., (2016)
		<i>Pachymeniopsis gargiuli</i> , <i>Grateloupia turuturu</i>	NIS	Asturias, Galicia	Montes et al., (2017)
		<i>Scageliopsis patens</i>	NIS	Basque Country, Cantabria	Secilla et al., (2008)
		7 macroalgae	NIS	Basque Country	Diez et al., (2012)
	Various	20 invertebrates (Table 1)	Cryptogenic, NIS	Asturias	Miralles et al., (2016)
		17 cirripedia, bivalves, polychaeta and cinadira (Table 2)	NIS and invasive	Asturias	Miralles et al., (2018a)
		18 taxa (Table 1)	NIS and cryptogenic	Asturias	Miralles et al., (2018b)
		71 taxa (Annex 4-3)	NIS	Gijon	Miralles et al., (2021)
		Benthic fauna and flora from soft and hard bottoms (Table 2, 4-6)	NIS	Basque Country	Zorita et al., (2009)
		20 algae (Annex 4-1)	Cryptogenic, NIS	Gijon	Ardura et al., (2020)
		224 benthic fauna and flora (Annex 4-1)	NIS	Basque Country	Borja et al., (2011)
		23 taxa (Table 4)	NIS, Cryptogenic, Invasive	Gijon	Fernández et al., (2022)
		225 taxa (Table I)	NIS	North of Spain	Aleman et al., (2012)
		NIS taxa (Table 1)	Criptogenic, NIS, Invasive	Gijon	Fernández-Rodríguez et al., (2022)
		14 taxa (Table 1)	NIS and invasive	Gijon	Ibabe et al., (2021)
5 crustacea, bivalve and polychaeta (Table 7)	NIS and invasive	Asturias	Rech et al., (2018)		
Various	Chordata	<i>Mustela vison</i>	Invasive	Spain	Lecis et al., (2008)
	Mollusca	<i>Potamopyrgus antipodarum</i>	Invasive	Asturias	Clusa et al., (2016)
		23 terrestrial and freshwater molluscs (Table A1 and A2)	NIS and Cryptogenic	Asturias	Sánchez et al., (2021)
	Various	6 plant in sea rush communities	NIS	Basque Country, Cantabria	Caño et al., (2014)
		457 plants	NIS	Basque Country	Campos (2010)
		265 vascular flora	NIS	Basque Country	Campos and Herrera (1997)
		25 new exotic flora records	NIS	Basque Country	Campos and Herrera (2000)
407 taxons of flora in Biscay (Annex 1)	NIS	Basque Country	Campos and Herrera (2009)		

Table 2-3. Harmful species that are non-indigenous or that are associated and use NIS as vectors in the North of Spain.

Phy	Harmful species	Status	Vector	Loc.	Affected organism	Health impact	Reference
Arth	<i>Aedes albopictus</i>	Invasive (Asia)	Transport of goods and private vehicles	BC	Humans	Insect bites, vector for arboviruses (dengue and chikungunya)	Goiri et al., (2020)
	<i>Ctenarytaina eucalypti</i> , <i>C. spatulata</i>	NIS (Aus)	Eucalyptus species*	Ast	Eucalyptus globulus and apple orchards	Damage on plantations due to ovoposition, vectors of "Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma mali</i> ", causal agent of apple proliferation (AP) disease	Rosa-García et al., (2013)
	<i>Urocerus albicornis</i>	NIS (N Ame)	Transportation of logs	BC	Coniferous forests	Larvae deposition and symbiont to wood-decaying fungus (<i>Amylostereum chailletii</i>)	Goldarazena et al., (2015)
Asco	<i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i> (chestnut blight fungus)	Invasive (E Asia)	Transportation of logs, introduction of infected chestnut plants	Ast	Castanea spp.	Chestnut blight disease	González-Varela et al., (2011)
	<i>Fusarium circinatum</i>	NIS (N Ame)	Insects (bark beetle and weevil)	BC	60 pine species (Pinus spp.)	Pitch canker disease	Iturriza et al., (2011)
Coss	<i>Amdoparvovirus carnivoran</i>	NA	<i>Mustela vison</i> *	Sp	<i>Mustela lutreola</i> , <i>M. putorius</i>	Aleutian mink parvovirus infection	Lecis et al., (2008)
Dupl	<i>Orbivirus</i> (Bluetongue virus BTV)	NIS (Afr, Asia)	Infected Culicoides insect introduced by winds	BC	Wild ruminants and livestock	Bluetongue disease.	García-Lastra et al., (2012)
Moll	<i>Ruditapes philippinarum</i>	Invasive (Indo-Pac)	Introduction for aquaculture purposes	Ast	<i>Ruditapes decussatus</i>	Genetic introgression.	Habtemariam et al., (2015)
Myz	<i>Peridinium quadridentatum</i>	NIS (NW Atl)	Ballast water	Gijon	Fishes, Humans	HAB, adverse effects on fisheries, economy and human health	Ardura et al., (2020)
Ochr	<i>Heterosigma akashiwo</i>	NIS (NZ)	Ballast water	Gijon	Marine Species	HAB, production of allelopathic substance, haemolytic effects on fish gills	
	<i>Pseudo-nitzschia galaxiae</i>	NIS (Aus, NW Atl)	Ballast water	Gijon	Humans	HAB, production of domoic acid, amnesic shellfish poisoning (ASP)	
Plath	<i>Dicrocoelium dendriticum</i>	NA	<i>Ceratomyxa virgata</i> *, <i>Xerosecta cespitum</i> *	Ast	Humans	Dicrocoeliosis	Sánchez et al., (2021)
	<i>Brachylaima cribbi</i>	NA	<i>Ceratomyxa virgata</i> , <i>Rumina decollata</i> *	Ast	Humans	Digenean fluke	
	<i>Acanthostomum burminis</i>	NA	<i>Melanoides tuberculata</i> *	Ast	Amphibians	NA	
	<i>Calicophoron microbothrium</i>	NA		Ast	Ruminants	NA	
	<i>Centrocestus formosanus</i>	NA		Ast	Fishes	NA	
	<i>Centrocestus unequiorchalis</i>	NA		Ast	Fishes, Birds, Rodents	NA	
	<i>Clonorchis sinensis</i>	NA		Ast	Humans	Opisthorchiasis	
	<i>Dendritobilharzia</i> sp.	NA		Ast	Birds	NA	
	<i>Echinochasmus bagulai</i>	NA		Ast	Birds	NA	
	<i>Echinochasmus japonicus</i>	NA		Ast	Humans	Intestinal helminthiasis	
	<i>Echinochasmus milvi</i>	NA		Ast	Fishes	NA	
	<i>Gastrodiscus aegyptiacus</i>	NA		Ast	Equidae	NA	
	<i>Gigantobilharzia</i> spp.	NA		Ast	Humans	Cercarial dermatitis	
	<i>Gryosoma indica</i>	NA		Ast	Birds	NA	
<i>Haplorchis pleurolophocerca</i> , <i>H. pumilio</i>	NA		Ast	Fishes	NA		

Phy	Harmful species	Status	Vector	Loc.	Affected organism	Health impact	Reference
	<i>Haplorchis taichui</i> , <i>H. yokogawai</i>	NA		Ast	Humans	Intestinal helminthiasis	
	<i>Haplorchoides cahirinus</i> , <i>H. mehrai</i>	NA		Ast	Fishes	NA	
	<i>Heterophyes heterophyes</i>	NA		Ast	Humans	Heterophyiasis	
	<i>Heterophyes pumilio</i>	NA		Ast	Cannids, Fishes	NA	
	<i>Loxogenoides bicolor</i>	NA		Ast	Amphibians	NA	
	<i>Mesostephanus haliasturis</i>	NA		Ast	Birds	NA	
	<i>Notocotylus mamii</i>	NA		Ast	Birds	NA	
	<i>Orthetrotrema monostomum</i>	NA		Ast	Odonata	NA	
	<i>Paragonimus westermani</i>	NA		Ast	Humans	Paragonimiasis	
	<i>Paralecithodendrium pyramidium</i>	NA		Ast	Quiroptera	NA	
	<i>Philophthalmus distomatosa</i> , <i>P. gralli</i> , <i>P. nocturnus</i>	NA		Ast	Birds	NA	
	<i>Procerovum cheni</i>	NA		Ast	Eels	NA	
	<i>Procerovum varium</i>	NA		Ast	Humans, Fishes	Ocular infection/inflammation	
	<i>Pygidiopsis genata</i>	NA		Ast	Rodents, Fishes	NA	
	<i>Stellantchasmus falcatus</i>	NA		Ast	Rodents	NA	
	<i>Transversotrema patialense</i>	NA		Ast	Fishes	NA	
	<i>Stegodexamene anguillae</i>	NA	Potamopyrgus antipodarum*	Ast	Eels	NA	
	<i>Brachylaima ruminae</i>	NA	Rumina decollata*	Ast	Rodents	NA	
	<i>Echinostoma</i> sp.	NA	Sinotaia quadrata*	Ast	Humans	Echinostomiasis	

Phy=Phyllum; Arth=Arthropoda; Asco=Ascomycota; Coss=Cossaviricota; Dupl=Duplornaviricota; Moll=Mollusca; Myz=Myzozoa, Ochr=Ochropyta, Plath=Plathyelminthes. Aus=Australia; NZ=New Zealand; Atl=Atlantic, Pac=Pacific; Ame=America; Afr=Africa. Loc.=Location; BC=Basque Country; Ast=Asturias; Sp=Spain.

2.4. River obstacles or freshwater diversions

The hydrogeomorphological dynamics of rivers are crucial for assessing the ecological status and must be protected as a critical environmental value. In response to the European Directive 2000/60/EC, Ollero Ojeda et al. (2008) developed a hydro-geomorphological index based on anthropogenic pressures and impacts. This index assesses the functional quality of the fluvial system, the channel quality, and the riparian corridor quality. Here, we explore various studies and effects on river systems, focusing on specific cases such as the Nansa River in Cantabria and the Pas River, as well as efforts in dam removal and its effects on river morphology and ecosystems.

The Nansa River in Cantabria is one of the most disturbed rivers in Spain (Martín & Codron, 2011). Water diversion from streams and the channelling of water from reservoirs into pipes have drastically reduced the riverbed flow. This reduction in flow, coupled with sediment and organic matter retention in reservoirs, significantly affects the water's physical-chemical characteristics. The most notable biogeographical effect is the fragmentation of river corridors due to hydroelectric use, leading to severe environmental changes. The salmon population, a vulnerable and emblematic species in Cantabria, faces near extinction. Another species impacted by water diversion is the Pyrenean desman (*Galemys pyrenaicus*), which prefers riffles overruns or pools and is more affected in rivers with water diversion (Martín & Codron, 2011; Esnaola et al., 2018).

Studies on the Pas River highlight the relationship between macroinvertebrates and gradients of hydromorphological stress and water quality. These studies correlate with the gradient of organic pollution stress, which may result from homogenising the basin's hydraulic characteristics (Álvarez-Cabria et al., 2010). The findings underscore the interconnectedness of hydromorphological conditions and aquatic biodiversity, emphasising the need for comprehensive water quality management.

Izagirre et al. (2013) researched nutrient uptake in streams impacted by hydropower plants. The study found that light levels were significantly higher in stream channels during accretion than in diversion channels. Diversion channels, being narrower, deeper, and having less substrate heterogeneity, contrast sharply with stream channels. Phosphate uptake length was significantly related to depth, a variable directly associated with discharge, highlighting the profound impact of hydropower structures on stream nutrient dynamics.

Spain has made progress in removing river barriers, with 133 barriers removed by 2022. However, a 2021 WWF report indicates that 5,423 barriers still have removal potential, with 17,906 km of potential river reconnection (Schwarz, 2021). Methodologies for dam removal monitoring have been developed, such as those by Ollero et al. (2014) for the Mendaraz and Inturia dams, and by Ibisate et al. (2016) for the Urumea and Leitzarán rivers. These studies reveal differing responses in river channels to dam removal, with the Urumea River showing rapid channel adjustment and sediment movement. At the same time, the Leitzarán River exhibited a slower adjustment due to staged dam removal.

Public perception of river fragmentation varies, with a study led by Arbolea et al. (2021) finding it to be the least valued river feature among surveyed participants. Surveys in Malaga and Asturias reveal a higher acceptance of dams in regions more dependent on them for water security than wetter areas with higher precipitation (Dopico et al., 2022). Additionally, studies in the Guadalhorce (south) and Nalón (north) rivers indicate worse bio-indicators of water quality associated with southern dams. However, stakeholders in the Guadalhorce region valued the ecosystem services of dams more highly, particularly cultural services. Despite the general

support for dams, citizens were willing to contribute financially to improving environmental health (Fernandez et al., 2022).

2.5. Coastal Construction

According to Cearreta et al. (2004), the Basque coast represents only 12% of the total surface area of the Basque Country; however, it supports 60% of the overall population and 33% of the industrial activities. Also, along the north coast of Spain, estuaries have often been modified, for example, by constructing jetties at their mouths (Flor-Blanco et al., 2015).

According to Greenpeace's (2018) report on the evolution and state of conservation of the goods and services that coasts provide between 2005 and 2014 (Table 2-4), the Basque Country is the fourth autonomous community with the most degraded coastline.

This report states that the Bizkaia province has "12.4% of its coastline degraded by urbanised soils, and the set of environmental goods and services remains stable. Three services deteriorate, and three others show a notable improvement, with the natural landscape again experiencing severe deterioration. Thus, the capacity for self-sufficiency decreases, mainly due to decreased livestock activity; deforestation harms many endangered and endemic species. The Biscayan coast is also one of those with the highest degree of anthropisation – the transformation of the environment by humans – on its beaches, with 57.1% of the beachfront urbanised. Although the coast is not suffering from such massive urbanisation, 5,104 new hectares of artificial paving and construction since 1987 is a notable increase. On the positive side, the erosion risk has decreased, and the flood buffering capacity has increased due to improved vegetation. Protected natural areas also have adequate management instruments, although they are few and far between".

Table 2-4. Ecosystem services, the ecosystems that provide them, the indicator of their evolution in the study period (2005-2014) and the assessment of their trend (Greenpeace, 2018).

Services	Ecosystem	Indicator (%, 2005-2014)	Status
Food	Crops and grasslands	-4.6	Deterioration
Minerals	Salt marshes	-	-
Coastal land	Natural beaches	-1.2	Deterioration
Genetic diversity	Natural habitats	0.0	Stable
Rainfall generation	Evaporation generating areas	+0.2	Stable
Species conservation	Habitats for endangered species	-1.3	Deterioration
Erosion control	Areas devoid of vegetation	-74.7	Significant improvement
Flood buffering	Riparian vegetation, wadis and estuaries	+30.4	Significant improvement
Knowledge	Protected natural spaces	+100	Outstanding improvement
Human enjoyment	Natural landscape**	-7.8	Outstanding deterioration

Flor-Blanco et al. (2015) explain how the construction of jetties significantly accelerates accretion at several points along the northern coast of Spain. In addition, wave refraction caused by these structures results in a shoreward drift of the beach towards the spit and a more significant accumulation of sand on the western side of the beaches. It also shows evidence of the large amounts of accumulated sediments that, by deflation, form tabular dunes. Subsequently, sparse vegetation colonises the entire dune environment. In some cases, the

original surface area of the dunes more than doubled. The process slows down when a new equilibrium is reached and sand covers the area between the breakwater extension and the previous limit of the intertidal beach. Then, erosion caused by storm surges and sea level rise begins to affect the dune fronts and forms escarpments, especially during storm periods. Subsequently, the dune fronts recover slightly during calmer periods.

2.6. Climate variability and extreme events

Cliffs dominate the Basque coastline (246 km); only 33 km are beaches, and as we said before, they support a large percentage of the population and industrial activities. According to climate change models developed by Chust et al. (2011), the sea level in the Bay of Biscay is expected to rise between 29 and 45 cm (SRES A2) and 33–49 cm (SRES A1B) as a result of regional thermal expansion and global ice-melting, under scenarios of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. The same study showed that the largest flooded area is concentrated in estuaries, as expected, since these areas are associated with extensive and flat plains. However, terrestrial and artificial habitats are the most affected.

On the other hand, as evidenced by the extreme winter storm events of February and March 2014 that affected the coasts of Galicia and the Cantabrian Sea, they will mainly materialise in erosion processes on the morpho-sedimentary environments and leaving much damage to coastal infrastructures (Flor et al., 2014).

The *Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación*, started reporting events in the Boletín de Adversidades Climáticas y Medioambientales. Reports from 2013 to 2016 contain detailed information for each autonomous community. From 2017 onwards, the reports became shorter and more generalised for Spain (Tables 2–5).

2.7. Agriculture productive systems

According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), a quarter of total anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions come from the AFOLU sector, mainly from deforestation, livestock and fertiliser application (IPCC, 2019). According to the Institute of Basque Culture, together with industry, the services sector constitutes the most critical sector of the Basque economy. This is precisely the sector that has grown the most in the last decade of the 20th century. However, fishing and agriculture have long traditions, although they have lost much of their former vigour.

The agricultural areas have north-south variations determined by altitude, Cantabrian influence, continentality, and Mediterranean influence:

- ✓ **Cantabrian valleys and depressions.** The intense pressure on flat land due to industrialisation and urbanisation reduces the agricultural areas oriented towards meadows and dairy cattle, preferably complemented in some regions with local horticultural crops (peppers), greenhouses, flowers and kiwis.
- ✓ **Cantabrian Mountains.** The rugged relief forces the increasing predominance of forest use interspersed with the mosaic of meadows of farmhouses and their small areas of cultivation.
- ✓ **The plains and valleys of Alava,** with their continental climate depressions, support fresh dry cereal crops with newly irrigated areas that are sown with potatoes, beetroot and some vegetables.
- ✓ **The Alavese Sierras,** interspersed with valleys and irrigated areas of continental crops, including seed potatoes, are dominated by forest and scrubland.

- ✓ **Ebro Depression.** The Rioja Alavesa has a strong vocation for quality vineyards in the area of Mediterranean influence with recent irrigation and cereal strips in the higher areas.

Table 2-5. Climate adversities in the Autonomous community of the Basque Country between the period 2013-2022 (n = number of agricultural losses episodes).

Year	Spring		Summer		Autumn		Winter	
	Event		Event		Event		Event	
2022	High temperatures Droughts Squalls		High temperatures Droughts Squalls	Impacts on agricultural production	Extreme temperatures 2.5-3.5 °C above mean Droughts		Squalls	
2021	Droughts Squalls		Droughts Squall	Precipitation values 50% lower than average Donosti	High precipitations		Warm temperatures Floods	
2020	High temperatures 1.5-2-5 °C above mean		Heatwaves		High temperatures Squalls		High temperatures Squalls	
2019	Droughts	Impacts on agricultural production	Heatwaves	Impacts on agricultural production	Heavy rainfalls Squall <i>Amelie</i>	Impacts on agricultural production	High temperatures Droughts	1.5-2.5 °C above mean, impacts on agricultural production
2018	Heavy rainfall Squalls	impacts on agricultural production	Squalls	10-15% increase of storm anomalies Impacts on agricultural production	Warm temperatures Droughts	Impacts on agricultural production	Squalls	Impacts on agricultural production
2017	High temperatures 2 °C above mean Hevy rainfalls Droughts Frost	warmest spring since 1965 (Spain) Risk of river overflows Cereal crops affected Vinyards affected	Droughts	Fires State of emergency in water reservoirs Impacts on agricultural production	Droughts Frost, hail	Impacts on agricultural production	Heavy rainfall	Precipitation values 50% higher than average Impacts on agricultural production
2016	High precipitation	Impacts on agricultural production	High temperatures Droughts	Impacts on agricultural production, fires on croplands and forest plantations	Droughts	impacts on agricultural production of sunflower, olive groves, beetroot and fodder	High precipitations	Impacts on agricultural production
2015	General drought	Impacts on industrialized crops	Extreme temperatures Droughts	Impacts on extensive herbaceous crops	Extreme temperatures Droughts Fitosanitary issues	Impacts on legumes and vegetables	NA	
2014	High precipitation	Impacts on extensive herbaceous crops	Hailstorm	Impacts on extensive herbaceous crops	Extreme temperatures Droughts	3 °C above mean Impacts on fodder production	Heavy rainfalls and flods Snowfall and frost	Impacts on cereals and vineyards production
2013	High precipitation	Impacts on extensive herbaceous crops	Hailstorm	Impacts on extensive herbaceous crops	Hailstorm	Impacts on extensive herbaceous crops	Floods Strong swell Heavy snowfall	Impact on extensive herbaceous crops Samage to harbors and boardwalls Transportation disturbances

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3. Case study: Transition of the Butroe River and Bay of Plentzia.

In chapter one, we proposed a conceptual framework for One Health in a socio-ecological system (SES), which included components of human, animal and socioeconomic determinants of health and nature's contributions as an approach to ecosystem health. Afterwards, in chapter two, we reviewed the literature addressing pressures in Northern Spain and the coastal-land systems of Asturias, Cantabria, and the Basque Country. Here, we want to fine-tune the scale and focus on a specific coastal-land SES where we can apply our conceptual framework and identify which pressures may be affecting the state-exposure-effect and, therefore, the health of the system.

The Butroe River transition and Bay of Plentzia is located in the Basque Country on the inner part of the Gulf of Biscay, east of the Spanish north coast. This region is influenced by the Cantabrian Sea, specifically by the Cantabria-Matxitxako coastal water mass and is exposed without upwelling. From inland, it receives the Butroe River, which collects the waters of a watershed where rivers are relatively small due to the short distance between the mountains and the coast (Lavin et al., 2012). Therefore, the Bay is affected by the activities occurring nearby and throughout the river basin. These terrestrial, freshwater, transitional and oceanic environments are highly interconnected and establish complex interactions. Consequently, to understand the Socio-Ecological System (SES) of the Bay of Plentzia, it is essential to consider the Bay unit itself and the whole of the *coastal landscape*.

Due to its location in the Gulf of Biscay, the predominant climate is temperate and somewhat rainy, with moderate winters and warm summers. Temperatures are mild, with an annual means of 13-15°C, minimums of 4 to 5 °C, and summer maximums of 40 °C when southern winds arrive. Precipitation is lower than in the easternmost part of the Basque Country, with values of 900 to 1,300 mm/year, while the mean towards the French border is 1,600 mm/year. This also translates into higher runoff values in this part of the territory. On the other hand, the mean evapotranspiration is spatially similar along the North of Spain, around 700 mm/year (URA, 2023a). Precipitations are common throughout the year, 200 days/year on average, with an irregular seasonal cycle and higher frequencies in autumn (Usabiaga et al., 2004). The general circulation pattern of the Gulf of Biscay is determined by the Azores current from the subtropical gyre and the North Atlantic current from the subpolar gyre. Figure 3-1 shows the movements of the superficial and sub-superficial water masses, highly influenced by the meteorological conditions.

Figure 3-1. Superficial water movements in the Bay of Biscay. From Lavin et al. (2012).

The Basque coast is mainly composed of rocky cliffs leading to the sea, some small estuaries, and rocky or sandy beaches, heavily influenced since the 20th century by urban settlements, industrial zones, and habitat degradation (Chust et al., 2021). The area's geological history is highly determined by sedimentation, folding and erosion processes. The Butroe River runs parallel to the direction of the rock strata, as the lithology is rather homogeneous, characterised mainly by carbonate and detrital material, with some volcanic areas in the northern area (Ropero Pascual, 2009). This allows the development of wider valleys, with a smooth relief and without any significant slope breaks (Edeso Fito et al., 2023; Eraso, 1983; Ropero Pascual, 2009). The Butroe River originates in the mounts Bizkargi (555 m), the Gaztelumendi (323 m) and the Sollube (684 m) and descends the valley to Mungia (Edeso Fito et al., 2023). It initially crosses a sandstone

substratum and then descends through calcareous rocks, occasionally encountering basaltic and gypsum sections (Anbiotek, 2009). The upper stretch of the river, with a river bed of stones and pebbles, is designed by the Basque Water Agency – URA as Butroe-A (*alto*), and receives the waters from the Atxipe and Larrauri streams. The middle section of the river, after Mungia, which acquires a more meandering shape, is characterised by gravels, sands and silts and is designated as the Butroe-B (*bajo*). It receives the waters from the Zuzentze and Oleta streams and reaches the Butroe castle. These two sections conform to the freshwater part of the river, with a longitude of approximately 60 km. After the castle, there is an artificial weir, known in Spanish by *presa de Arbin*, which delimits the highest point of tidal influence and marks the beginning of the lowest reach of the river, the transitional water body of the Butroe-*transición* or the Butroe estuary (Table 3-1). This stretch, composed of marine, fluvial and colluvial sediments, flows downstream to Plentzia, where it empties into the bay, and is recurrently invaded by the sea, earning the name *Ría de Plentzia* (Edeso Fito et al., 2023).

Table 3-1. Main morphological and hydrological characteristics of the water body Butroe-*transición*. (Modified from Solaun et al., 2023e).

	Butroe estuary
Catchment area of the Butroe River	172.2 km ²
Estuary length	8 km
Maximum depth	10 m
Mean volume calculated for 2.5 m tidal height	2.2 10 ⁶ m ³
Subtidal volume	0.79 10 ⁶ m ³
Total flooded area calculated for 4.5 m tidal height	1.599 km ²
Intertidal area	1.37 %
River flow: average annual contribution of all the river's tributaries	4.7 m ³ ·s ⁻¹
Flushing time: the time required for the average volume of water in the estuary to renew	10 h
Residence time: the time a parcel of water remains within the system	0.04 days

According to the URA, the Butroe Hydrological Unit (HU) is divided into 33 subunit catchment areas and includes the secondary rivers Andraka and Estepona (URA, 2023b). In the study area of our project, we exclude the catchment area of these two secondary rivers since they do not flow into the Bay of Plentzia but into Armintza and Bakio, respectively. Thereby we only focus on the basins that exclusively collect waters that directly reach the Bay of Plentzia. To do so, we subdivided the Butroe watershed using a DEM of 5m and the Hydrology geoprocessing tool from ArcGIS, and we obtained 45 sub-hydrological units according to the watershed section (Table 3-2) that cover an approximate extension of 18mil hectares, including 161.6 hectares that correspond to the water bodies of the Bay (Figure 3-2).

The Butroe watershed is part of the Eastern Cantabrian Hydrographic Demarcation – DHCO, as delimited by the URA, which comprises territories of the Basque Country, Navarra and Castilla León. However, the Butroe is an internal basin of the Basque Country, with no territory in other autonomous communities. Therefore, the competent authority responsible for water management is the Basque Government. On the other hand, the control and assessment of coastal and transitional waters, specifically in ports, is conducted by the State administration, while the management of the beaches and their services is under the authority of the Provincial Council of Bizkaia (*Diputación Foral de Bizkaia*) (Table 3-3). In municipal terms, the Butroe watershed includes territories of 18 municipalities (Figure 3-2); however, this area is minimal in Sopela, Loiu, Lemoiz, and Larrabetzu. Other cities, like Errigoiti, have a little bit more than 50% of their surface covered by the watershed. The natural boundary representing the watershed closely aligns with the extent of the Plentzia-Mungia region (only Errigoiti and Morga belong to another one, the Gernika-Bermeo region). On the other hand, the municipalities within the watershed can be divided between those belonging to the functional area of Mungia and those belonging to the functional area of the Great Bilbao. Essentially, the coastal municipalities, namely Sopela, Urduliz, Barrika, Plentzia, Gorliz, and Lemoiz, fall within the functional area of

Greater Bilbao. These municipalities, along with Berango, which is already outside the Butroe watershed, joined together in 1992 under the Uribe Kosta Joint Services Consortium to provide various municipal services on a joint basis.

Table 3-2. Area of sub-hydrological units according to the Butroe River section

Watershed section	Sub-units	Hectares	Sub-units	Hectares	
A	Upper Butroe	Directos Butroe 2 (izq)	R. Butroe - Alto 2	917,6	
		R. Amentzakarreta	R. Kaperiaga	323,5	
		R. Anbieta	R. Trobika	203,2	
		R. Butroe - Alto 1		2028,8	
	Atxispe R. Atxispe	R. Gabatika	513,6		
	Larrauri R. Larrauri	2000,5	R. Meakabarrena y sin nombre	750,0	
	Oleta R. Oleta	1195,2			
B	Lower Butroe	Directo Butroe (izq)	R. Kimera y sin nombre directo Butroe	214,2	
		Directos Butroe 3 (der)	R. Kiskilluerreka	571,1	
		Directos Butroe 3 (izq)	R. Metaliturri y directos Butroe	122,7	
		Directos Butroe 4 (der)	R. Telleria	346,2	
		Directos Butroe 5 (der)	R. Tosinalde	797,9	
		R. Artzubi	R. Trobika	329,7	
		R. Bitوريا		699,6	
		Zuzentze R. Mixerreka & R. Asoloerreka	R. Zuzentze	668,7	
HOBE Focus Area					
T	Butroe transition drainage	Directs Bahia Plentzia (izq)	R. Metaliturri y directos Butroe	169,2	
		R. Kukutza	R. Pikaragaerreka	136,3	
		R. Mesula y directos Butroe		277,1	
	Butroe transition	Butroe - Mesohalino	32,3	Butroe - Oligohalino	14,0
	Butroe transition drainage	R. Musaurieta	121,4	Plentzia	112,3
		R. Txatxarroerreka	266,4	R. Kukuluerreka	111,5
		R. Gazatza	266,0	R. Urgozo	243,5
	Butroe transition	Butroe - Euhalino	4,4	Butroe - Polihalino	37,0
		Bay of Plentzia	73,9		
	Butroe coast drainage	Butroe drenaje costa (izq)	69,7	Butroe drenaje costa (der)	62,7

To delimit the extent of the SES coastal landscape for the project, we used ecological boundary represented by the Butroe-*transición* water body, as delimited by the URA, which includes the Bay and the Ria of Plentzia (Table 3-1). For this reason, in the HOBE Focus Area, we include the 18 sub-watersheds that directly discharge in the Bay of Plentzia or the Butroe estuary, which comprise territories of Barrika, Plentzia, Gorniz, Urduliz, Lemoiz and Gatika (Figure 3-2). However, only the first three have their territory within the sub-basins that drain into the Butroe transition. In the case of Urduliz, Lemoiz and Gatika, the fraction of territory that discharges in the estuary is much smaller or does not discharge directly into the estuary, and therefore, we have decided not to include these municipalities in the SES of the Bay of Plentzia.

Figure 3-2. Location of the Butroe watershed and the HOBE focus area (in red). Land cover from the CORINE Land Cover 2018 and plantation forest from the Mapa Forestal 2022 of the Gobierno Vasco.

Table 3-3. Competent authorities with responsibilities in the Butroe hydrological unit (URA, 2023h)

Administración del estado	
Ministerio de Transportes, Movilidad y Agenda Urbana	Control de aguas costeras y de transición (puertos) Valoración en aguas costeras y de transición (puertos)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Dirección General de la costa y el Mar <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Demarcación de Costas del País Vasco 	Cumplimiento de la normativa, vigilancia, policía y sanción
Comunidades autónomas	
Administración General de la Comunidad Autónoma de Euskadi	Análisis de presiones e impactos Análisis económico Registro de zonas protegidas Preparación del plan hidrológico Preparación e implementación del programa de medidas
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Departamento de Desarrollo Económico, Sostenibilidad y Medio Ambiente <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Agencia Vasca del Agua (URA) 	Análisis de presiones e impactos Análisis económico Control y valoración de aguas superficiales y subterráneas, continentales, costeras y de transición Registro de zonas protegidas Preparación del plan hidrológico Preparación e implementación de medidas Participación pública Cumplimiento de la normativa (vigilancia, policía y sanción) Coordinación de la implementación Reporting a la Comisión Europea
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Departamento de Salud. Dirección de Salud Pública y Adicciones 	Control de aguas superficiales Vigilancia sanitaria de las zonas de baño
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Departamento de Seguridad <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Dirección de Atención de Emergencias y Meteorología 	Preparación del programa de medidas
Entidades locales	
	Análisis económico Preparación del plan hidrológico Preparación e implementación de las medidas Coordinación de la implementación
Diputación Foral de Bizkaia	Preparación del plan hidrológico Preparación e implementación de las medidas Labores de mantenimiento, servicio de salvamento y socorrismo, ordenación de las actividades en las playas, o de la seguridad de las personas
Consorcio de Aguas Bilbao Bizkaia	Preparación e implementación de las medidas
Ayuntamiento de Barrika, Plentzia, Gorniz	Información al público interesado Ordenación de las actividades en las playas Seguridad de las personas Gestión de infraestructuras estables
Usuarios industriales	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Representante de la Asociación Clúster del Papel de Euskadi 	Vocal en Asamblea de Usuarios de la Agencia Vasca del Agua 2023
Usos energéticos	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Representante de Iberdrola 	Vocal en Asamblea de Usuarios de la Agencia Vasca del Agua 2023
Usos agrícolas	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Representante del Sindicato de las personas agricultoras y ganaderas de Euskadi 	Vocal en Asamblea de Usuarios de la Agencia Vasca del Agua 2023
Asociaciones de consumidores y usuarios	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Representante de la Federación de Consumidores de Euskadi 	Vocal en Asamblea de Usuarios de la Agencia Vasca del Agua 2023
Particulares	
	Implementación de medidas

3.1. General context: the Butroe watershed

3.1.1. Biological framework

The vegetation of the Butroe watershed presents characteristics of the Euro-Siberian biogeographic region in its sector *cántabro-euskaldún*. Because of its geological and climatological conditions, the potential vegetation of the area would be on most of its surface an acidophilic oak woodland (*Quercus robur*) and Atlantic mixed forest-oak woodland. There could also be smaller patches of Pyrenean oak (*Quercus pyrenaica*). Along the freshwater courses, there would be a riparian forest called *aliseda*, composed mainly of *Alnus glutiosa* and *Fraxinus excelsior*. Closer to the coast, the main vegetation would be a Cantabrian holm oak forest (*Quercus ilex*), with the coastline dominated by vegetation characteristic of coastal areas. The vegetation would correspond to coastal sandbanks only in Gorniz, at the northern half of the Bay of Plentzia, where one of the few dune ecosystems of the Basque coast is located. Nowadays, anthropogenic activities have reduced the original surface of all this natural vegetation, substituting them with grasslands, crops, and forestry plantations with exotic species, like pines and eucalyptus. Only around Plentzia can there be found some remaining of the original *alisedas* forests (Diputación Foral de Bizkaia, 2014).

To conserve the natural characteristics of the area, there are many flora species under protection figures such as the “Red list of vascular flora of the Autonomous Community of the Basque Country”, as is the case of the Bizkaian endemic plant *Apium graveolens* ssp. *butronensis* (Aizpuru et al., 2010). Other flora that have been classified as endangered in the area are the populations of *Armeria euscadiensis* in the Gorniz cliffs, as well as of *Culcicta macrocarpa*, *Koeleria labescens* and *Herniaria ciliolata* ssp. *robusta*, the communities of *Salicornia obscura* and *Frankenia laevis* in Plentzia, the chain fern *Woodwardia radicans* in Mungia, and the fern *Vandenboschia speciose* in Meñaka and the Sollube mount (URA, 2022d). Additionally, the Special area of conservation (ZEC³⁴) of the Astondo dunes (Gorniz) represents a site of community interest for the conservation of coastal sandy habitats and their associated species (for more information, see the document “Medidas de conservación de la ZEC ES21130004–Astondoko Haremunak/Dunas de Astondo” from the Gobierno Vasco, 2012).

Regarding fauna communities, most are highly dependent on the forest, unless those associated with the coastal cliffs and sandbanks. Despite the disappearance and fragmentation of the original forests, the intermediate stages of heterogeneous shrublands and open spaces provide a favourable environment for most reptiles, birds, and small mammals. Species like the European polecat (*Mustela putorius*) have been observed near the river (URA, 2022d). Nevertheless, other species that require denser forests, like the European wildcat (*Felis silvestris*), the European pine marten (*Martes martes*), or the otter (*Lutra lutra*), which requires a high-quality riparian and aquatic environment, are currently absent in the watershed (Diputación Foral de Bizkaia, 2014). The Butroe river represents a potential habitat for the endangered European mink (*Mustela lutreola*), a species considered an indicator of the good quality status of the river environment and the associated forests. Some of the headwaters of the Butroe, bordering the Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve, are also special interest areas for bat species such as *Rhinolophus euryale*, *Miniopterus schreibersii* and *Myotis emarginatus* (Diputación Foral de Bizkaia, 2014).

In terms of birdlife, the most common species in the area are associated to aquatic and forest ecosystems, such as the kingfisher (*Alcedo atthis*), the common sandpiper (*Actitis hypoleucos*), the lesser spotted woodpecker (*Dendrocopos minor*), the European pied flycatcher (*Ficedula hypoleuca*), and the white-throated dipper (*Cinclus cinclus*). The Eurasian bittern (*Botaurus*

³⁴ For its acronym in Spanish, Zona especial de conservación.

stellaris) has a special area of interest along the Butroe estuary, and the hen harrier (*Circus cyaneus*) has a sensitive point in Laukiz (Diputación Foral de Bizkaia, 2014). In the forest areas, birds of prey like the black kite (*Milvus migrans*), the booted eagle (*Hieraetus pennatus*), the peregrine falcon (*Falco peregrinus*) and the Eurasian eagle-owl (*Bubo bubo*) arrive to reproduce. The littoral cliffs serve as refuges for protected rare species like the storm petrel (*Hydrobates pelagicus*) and the common shag (*Phalacrocorax aristotelis*).

In terms of freshwater fish, amphibians, and reptiles, the species composition corresponds broadly with communities across the North of the Iberian Peninsula, including the fish *Parachondrostoma miegii*, the Iberian frog (*Rana iberica*) and the Iberian emerald lizard (*Lacerta schreiberi*) as the most noteworthy. As indicated by their common name, the last two are endemic species of the region that find their population at the easternmost limit in the Basque Country (Diputación Foral de Bizkaia, 2014). In the area there are also three species of invertebrates under endangered species protection figures: the beetles *Cerambyx cerdo* and *Lucanus cervus*, and the damselfly *Coenagrion mercurial* (Diputación Foral de Bizkaia, 2014).

Figure 3-3. List of species captured in the Butroe estuary (1997-2020). The colour gradient indicates the frequency of appearance: darker blue means 100% of the occasions, and light blue on <10%. The upper x-axis shows the number of species (richness) identified in each monitored year. Species with an asterisk indicate they belong to crustaceans. (From Borja et al. 2022)

The Butroe transition is an estuary representing one of the Habitats of Community Interest found on the watershed (Diputación Foral de Bizkaia, 2014). The fauna that inhabits the estuary of the Butroe is characterized by the genus of gobies *Pomatoschistus*, the common sole (*Solea solea*), the crab *Carcinus maenas*, and the caridean shrimp *Palaemon sp.* and *Crangon crangon* (Figure 3-3) (Borja et al., 2022). Macroinvertebrate communities are often used to determine the biological status of estuaries. In the Butroe estuary, the upper part is dominated by species with good tolerance to environmental alteration, such as dipteran larvae, the gastropod *Peringia ulvae*, the isopod *Cyathura carinata*, the bivalve *Scrobicularia plana*, or the polychaete *Hediste diversicolor* (Borja et al., 2022). In the middle and external section of the estuary, *P. ulvae* predominates, and although diversity is reduced in the intermediate part, richness and density increase again in the Bay of Plentzia (Borja et al., 2022).

As previously mentioned, the estuary of the Butroe flows to the coastal water body of Cantabria-Matxitxako (194.3 km²), which also receives the waters of the Barbadun and the Nerbioi rivers.

Fresh and saltwater mix in the Bay of Plentzia, where the marine fauna consists of species that support high hydro-dynamisms and that are relatively indifferent to environmental alterations, as indicated by the absence of molluscs and the presence of the hermit crab *Diogenes pugilator*. The community is defined as an “impoverished infralittoral clean sand community” (Borja et al., 2022). In the areas of hard substrate, the macroalgae community has an elevated coverage and species richness, with minimal presence of opportunistic species. In the supralittoral, the biomass cover is minimal, with the sporadic presence of some species, like the lichen *Verrucaria maura*. The coverage increases with depth, and species like *Dictyota dichotoma*, *Bifurcaria bifurcata*, *Ulva rigida*, *Sphacelaria* sp., *Ellisolandia elongate*, *Corallina officinallis* and *Lithopyllum incrustans* appear among others (Borja et al., 2022). Regarding phytoplankton, the area has seen a decrease in the abundance and frequency of blooms related to the sanitation improvements in the metropolitan area of Bilbao. In 2021, a bloom of the algae genus *Plagioselmis* was detected between the mouth of the Nerbioi and the Butroe. Additionally, throughout recent years, other species such as *Pfiesteria* sp., *Dinophysis acuminata* and *Protoceratium reticulatum* have been reported due to their occasional high abundance or their potential toxicity that can impair human health (Borja et al., 2022).

3.1.2. Socioeconomic framework

As previously mentioned, the municipalities with the most territory within the Butroe watershed are 14: Arrieta, Barrika, Errigoiti, Fruiz, Gamiz-Fika, Gatika, Gorniz, Laukiz, Maruri-Jatabe, Meñaka, Morga, Mungia, Plentzia, and Urduliz (Figure 3-2). These municipalities will be described in the following section to characterise the socioeconomic framework of the Butroe watershed.

a. Population

The municipality that occupies the largest territory is Mungia, which also contains the most significant fraction of the population (41 %) that inhabits the Butroe watershed, followed by Gorniz, Urduliz and Plentzia (Figure 3-4). Mungia, the only municipality with more than 10,000 inhabitants (INE³⁵, 2023), although all of them have shown a positive increase since the beginning of the millennium, with a growth ratio higher than 0.3 (URA, 2023c).

Figure 3-4. Population distribution by municipality in 2022. Data from Eustat³⁶, 2023.

The number of family dwellings in the Butroe HU³⁷(understood as the URA’s management unit, i.e. with the Andraika and Estepona rivers) was 28,246 in 2018, being 17,465 principal residences

³⁵ National Institute of Statistics – *Instituto Nacional de Estadística*, INE for its Spanish acronym

³⁶ Basque Institute of Statistics – *Euskal Estatistika Erakundea* or *Instituto Vasco de Estadística*

³⁷ From now on, every time we refer to the Butroe HU, we are referring to the Butroe hydrological unit as understood by URA, i.e. including the Andraika and Estepona watersheds.

and 2,735 secondary residences (URA, 2023c). The secondary to main residences ratio is between 5 to 9 % in the inland municipalities of the Butroe watershed but increases to 10-24 % in Plentzia and Gorliz. In 2017, the average household income in the Butroe HU was the highest of all the other HUs of the DHCO (URA, 2023c). The municipality of Laukiz stands out from the others, because its value has been over 70,000 € since 2013, while Mungia's household income has been the lowest one in the area for the past eight years, being under 30,000 € (Figure 3-5).

Figure 3-5. Average net household income (familiar income). Data from Eustat (2023).

b. Economic activities

The main economic activities developed in the province of Biscay are related to the service sector: trade, transportation, and hospitality. Agriculture, livestock, and fisheries, on the other hand, have the lowest gross domestic product at market price and generate the fewest jobs (Eustat, 2023).

Figure 3-6. Number of establishments by municipality, and distribution according to the economic activity. (Data from Eustat, 2023).

When focusing on the Butroe watershed, the majority of establishments can be found in Mungia, followed by Goliz, Urduliz, and Plentzia (Figure 3-6). Most are dedicated to trade, transport, and hospitality, followed by professional (scientific) and support services (Figure 3-6).

Although historically, **tourism** has not been the main economic activity of the Basque Country, it has grown in recent years. In 2018, there were 1091 tourist accommodation places in the Butroe HU, mainly distributed among camping sites, cottages and hotels by order of relevance (URA, 2023c). Additionally, the study area has a total of 74.5 ha occupied by golf courses, which makes it the second hydrographic basin in the DHCO with the largest surface area dedicated to this activity, after the Nerbioi-Ibaizabal basin (URA, 2023c). This is mainly due to the Laukariz Country Club's golf course in the municipality of Mungia.

The **industrial activity** is concentrated in Mungia, where 2,000 and 3,000 employees are dedicated to this sector (URA, 2023c). In the municipalities of the study area, only Mungia, Gorniz, Urduliz, Plentzia, Gatika and Gamiz-Fika had companies involved in this sector in 2022 (INE, 2023). Mungia is home to 44% of these companies, followed by Gorniz and Urduliz. The rest have much less industrial activity, and Arrieta, Errigoiti, Fruiz, Maruri-Jetabe, Meñaka, and Morga have never registered a company dedicated to this sector. In the cases of Barrika, Laukiz and Lemoiz, the data is protected by statistical secrecy (INE, 2023).

According to the Agricultural Census of 2020 from Eustat, the predominant **agricultural activities**, by order of importance, are permanent pastures, arable land, woody crops, greenhouse crops, and vegetable gardens for own consumption. Of this total area, 82% is classified as "used agricultural land" (Eustat, 2020). Most of this agricultural land area is concentrated in inland municipalities, particularly in Mungia, and the extents of Gatika, Gamiz-Fika, and Arrieta. Conversely, coastal cities such as Plentzia, Gorniz, and Barrika allocate a comparatively smaller area to this activity.

The presence of gardens for personal consumption is minimal, consistently falling below 1 ha in all the municipalities (Eustat, 2020). Of the total hectares occupied by agricultural holdings in the study area municipalities, 86% are used for **livestock activities** (Eustat, 2020). Most of them consist of sheep and goat holdings in terms of livestock units (UGT³⁸). The most abundant livestock type is poultry due to the presence of 5 poultry farms in Gamiz-Fika, the most important of which is the Larrabee Farm and 21 smaller farms in Mungia. It is important to highlight that poultry production in the area is notably higher, with 2,325 units/km² compared to the mean in all the DHCOs' 275 units/km² (URA, 2023c).

The **forestry sector** in the Basque Country is of great importance, and this is also reflected in the division by a watershed made in the 2022 Forest Map, *Mapa Forestal de 2022* (Gobierno Vasco, 2022). In the Butroe HU, nearly half of the land use (43%) is dedicated to plantation forests. By order of importance, the other uses are meadows, other forests, and artificial surfaces. The original forest has been replaced by forest plantations mainly of *Eucalyptus globulus* (47.827%), *Pinus radiata* (29.59%), *Eucalyptus nitens* (12.12%) and *Pinus pinaster* (7.58%) (data from the geodatabase *Mapa Forestal 2022* of the Gobierno Vasco). According to this data, only 12.7% belongs to public property, while the rest is in the hands of private institutions.

The **fishing and aquaculture** activities in the Butroe and the Bay are relatively minor when compared to other areas of the Basque coast and primarily at a local scale. The original fishermen's association of Plentzia, called San Pedro de la Villa y Aldeaños, disappeared by the end of the XIX century, and nowadays, the local vessels that operate in the area are registered in the association of Santo Tomás de Armintza. In the estuary, molluscs and crustaceans have been historically harvested. Oysters, clams and mussels used to be collected around the bridge

³⁸ UGT for its Spanish acronym: *Unidades Ganaderas Totales*

and in the mill dams (Ropero Pascual, 2008), before this activity was forbidden. However, the Cantabrian coast is currently being studied as a potential zone for the culture of mussels, and the area Txakurzulo in the Butroe estuary has been declared an area for inland aquaculture (Gobierno de España, 2022b). Additionally, there is a centre for aquaculture research in Plentzia (Marine Station PiE-UPV/EHU).

3.1.3. Water resources

a. Water resources

The Butroe watershed has an average of 164 hm³/year of natural surface hydrological resources, calculated from 1980/81-2017/18 (URA, 2023b). To ensure the excellent condition of these resources, the URA carries out different surveillance programmes for freshwater, transitional, and coastal waters. They include, on the one hand, the monitoring of all the water bodies' status, looking at their physical, chemical, biological, and ecological characteristics, and on the other, the monitoring of specific protected areas, such as bathing areas for recreational use, areas for economically significant aquatic species, nutrient-sensitive areas, and areas under the influence of nitrates of agricultural origin. The monitoring points are distributed all along the river (three in the Butroe-A, three in the Butroe-B), but mainly concentrated in the Butroe-transición (27 points) (Borja et al., 2022; URA, 2023g). There are also two points close to the Bay of Plentzia opening, which monitors the coastal water mass of Cantabria-Matxitxako (Borja et al., 2022).

The information collected in these monitoring is then used to determine an ecological, chemical, and hydromorphological status, which is then used to determine the general status of each water body (Table 3-3). The **ecological status** is assessed using different biological, physico-chemical and hydro-morphological indicators. For more information about the process see the Annex VIII from the *Plan Hidrológico de la DHCO. Revisión para el tercer ciclo: 2022-2027* (URA, 2023g). According to how much the indicators differ from the referent conditions, the ecological status of the waterbody is classified as "very good", "good", "moderated", "deficient" or "bad". The **chemical status** can be either "good" or "worse than good", depending on general physico-chemical parameters or the presence or absence of specific contaminants listed in the *Normas de Calidad Ambiental* (NCA). The **hydromorphological status** is based on one hand on the hydrological regime, and on the other on morphological characteristics such as the river continuity, or the intertidal structure of the coast (URA, 2023g). It can be "very good", "good", "moderated", "deficient" or "bad". Finally, the **general status** is also classified as "good" or "worse than good" (URA, 2023g).

Table 3-4. Evolution of the status in the water bodies of the Butroe and the adjacent coastal water mass. Status for the period 2015-2020 has been obtained by averaging the values of all years. The ecological and hydromorphological status can be classified as VG = Very Good = Good, M = Moderate, and D = Deficient. The chemical and general status in G = Good, and W = Worse than Good. (Borja et al., 2022; López et al., 2021, 2022; Mendiguren et al., 2020, 2022; Solaun et al., 2023e; URA, 2023g).

Years	Ecological status		Chemical status		Hydromorphological status		General status	
	2015-2020	2021	2015-2020	2021	2015-2020	2021	2015-2020	2021
Butroe-A	M	G	G	G	M	M	W	G
Butroe-B	D	M	G	G	D	D	W	W
Butroe-transición	G	M	G	G	G	M	G	W
Cantabria-Matxitxako	G	G	G	G	VG	G	G	G

Table 3-4 summarises the status of the Butroe and Cantabria-Matxitxako water bodies during the past years. The chemical status in all the areas has maintained a "good" quality classification for years. However, the general status does not reach the optimal conditions due to the

ecological and hydro-morphological status. The upper section of the river (**Butroe-A**) has recently complied with the environmental objectives since fish and macroinvertebrate communities were enhanced in 2021, reflected in the improvement of its general conditions. However, the river remains highly compartmentalised, and the connectivity is not optimal (López et al., 2021, 2022). The meandering part of the river (**Butroe-B**) presents worse ecological values and higher morphological alteration. The macroinvertebrate, fish and phytobenthic community is significantly degraded, although it relatively improved in 2021, and the natural morphological characteristics of the river are highly modified due to canalisations, slope stabilisations, transverse objects and modifications of the river bed (López et al., 2021, 2022). The status of the estuary (**Butroe-transición**) has been good since the outfall of the Gorliz Waste Water Treatment Plant (WWTP), which was moved out of the Bay of Plentzia in 2011. However, its ecological status worsened in 2021 due to the degradation of the macroinvertebrate community in the inner, middle and outer estuary, which has been suggested by Borja et al. (2022) to be the result of large-scale pressures. The hydromorphological characteristics are not optimal, mainly because of the destruction of the original estuarine habitat as a consequence of urbanisation and infrastructure construction (Solaun et al., 2023e).

b. Water supply

The waters carried by the Butroe river only serve as a supply for some of the area's municipalities. The majority receive water from the external natural resource of the Zadorra system, while only three towns, Meñaka, Arrieta, and Errigoiti, are also supplied by their water resources (Figure 3-7) (URA, 2023d). The water from the Zadorra system supplies the localities within the water supply area of Venta Alta (Figure 3-7), managed by the Bilbao-Viscay Water Consortium (*Consortio de Aguas de Bilbao-Bizkaia*). The Meñaka, Arrieta and Errigoiti localities are included in smaller water supply areas, which manage their hydrological resources through their local municipalities (URA, 2023e).

Figure 3-7. General status of the water bodies, water supply areas, health classification of the consumption waters, and fluoridated water in the study area. Data from Gobierno Vasco (2023a) and URA (2023g).

The Basque Government Health Department has established an Information System for Drinking Water in Euskadi (EKUIS) (Gobierno Vasco, 2023a), where it compiles the information about the origin, supply structures, water treatment, and results of periodic analysis for water's sanitary classification. Most of the waters have a satisfying classification, except Arrieta and Zona Alta Barrio Emerando in Meñaka, which have been classified as tolerable and deficient, respectively (Figure 3-7). For the latter, more than 5% of the water samples analysed in 2022 were unsuitable for consumption, due to factors such as an inappropriate colour and turbidity, substances like aluminium, iron and manganese, and the presence of heterotrophic bacteria (Gobierno Vasco, 2023a). Additionally, in most localities supplied by Venta Alta, the water is fluoridated (Figure 3-7), and according to the Health Department of the Basque Country, the only neighbourhood which does not receive fluoridated water in our focus area is Agirre-Areantza-Guzurmendi, in the Municipality of Gorliz (Gobierno Vasco, 2023a). More information about the origin, treatment and water quality per municipality can be found in the website of the Basque Government Department of Health, in the Environmental Health and Drinking Water section.

c. Water uses

In the document, *Actualización del Estudio de la demanda de agua en la CAPV 2020*, the URA studies water uses and demands in 2018 in the Butroe HU. They distinguish between four groups of uses: for population supply, industrial uses, agrarian uses, and other uses (Table 3-5). They also include water for energy production; however, as the water use in the Butroe HU is very low, we have not mentioned it below.

Table 3-5. Water uses in the Butroe HU. Modified from (URA, 2020a).

Use for supplying populations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domestic use: principal and secondary residences • Touristic use: hotels, apartments, camping sites, cottages, golf camps... • Urban industrial-commercial use: this will be analysed with the industrial uses • Municipal or institutional: e.g. garden irrigation, road cleaning, municipal buildings...
Industrial use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Urban industrial-commercial use: connected to the urban supply network • Industrial singular: with own water intakes
Agrarian use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Urban irrigation: connected to the urban supply network • Irrigation of agricultural holdings: with own water intakes • Urban livestock: connected to the urban supply network • Rural livestock: with own water intakes
Other use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recreational use: recreational and bathing activities, sport fishing, water sports and recreational bathing • Navigation and aquatic transport

Urban demands correspond to those satisfied through the urban supply network; however, they do not only cover domestic, touristic, municipal, and institutional use but also a fraction of irrigation, livestock, and industrial-commercial use (Figure 3-8).

Figure 3-8. Water demands according to type of use in the Butroe HU in 2018. Livestock, irrigation, industrial, and tourism include both urban network supply and own intakes. Data from URA (2020a).

In the Butroe HU, the highest domestic use is located in Mungia (707,374 m³/year), probably due to its high urbanised surface area and many inhabitants. After Mungia, it follows Gorliz (276,190 m³/year) and Plentzia (199,371 m³/year), with many urban areas. The lowest urban water demand is in Morga (16,905 m³/year) (URA, 2020a). There is a remarkable fluctuation in the water demand in the coastal municipalities, dropping in December and doubling in the months of July and August, while in inland municipalities it remains stable throughout the year (Figure 3-9) (URA, 2023c). This is related to the different demographic dynamics, and the increasing population on the coast during the summer months.

Figure 3-9. Monthly distribution of annual urban demand in the Butroe. Data from URA (2023c).

Looking at the water used for tourist activities, Mungia is again the municipality that uses a larger volume (103,060 m³/year). In contrast, Gorliz and Plentzia use 3,325 and 1,790 m³/year, respectively. It includes water from tourist accommodation and golf courses. In most municipalities, the water comes from the urban supply system, and only Mungia uses a significant fraction of water from its intakes (89,600 m³/year). On the other hand, Fruiz is the only municipality with no demand for this touristic use (URA, 2020a).

Municipal-institutional use is also very related to urban areas (Figure 3-8), and according to URA, it follows the same pattern as the other urban uses. Mungia consumes 95,068 m³/year, Gorliz 62,174 m³/year, and Plentzia 44,154 m³/year. In the rest of the municipalities, the consumption is smaller, with the lowest one in Meñaka 2,016 m³/year (URA, 2020a).

Rural demands include agriculture, irrigation and livestock production. In the area, water for irrigation is only collected from the urban water supply network. It is highest in Mungia (4,720 m³/year), Gamiz-Fika (2,160 m³/year), and Gatika (1,920 m³/year), while the lowest are in Plentzia (100 m³/year), Gorliz (140 m³/year) and Barrika (180 m³/year), corresponding to the coastal municipalities. Water for livestock is the only one with its intake origin, besides the fraction from the urban supply network. The water demand is highest in Lemoiz with 24,669 m³/year (22,176 from supply network and 2,493 from own intakes), followed by Gamiz-Fika with 23,658 m³/year (21,793 from supply network and 1,865 from own intakes), and Mungia with 19,491 m³/year (15,674 from supply network and 3,817 from own intakes).

The **industrial demands** are also supplied on one side from the urban network and on the other from its intakes. Bars, restaurants, shops, and industries from the urban area are connected to the urban network, while the rest of the industries, mainly manufacturing, constructing and extractive industries, have their water intakes. Mungia has the highest industrial demand (315,084 m³/year, with an additional 7,593 m³/year coming from own intakes), followed by Urduliz (98,080 m³/year) and Gatika (68,259 m³/year) (URA, 2020a).

d. Impacts on water bodies

In the studies conducted for the 2021-2027 water planning cycle, the URA analysed the presence of impacts on the water masses of the Butroe watershed. They understand that a body is impacted if, as a result of one or more pressures, it does not achieve its environmental objectives or reflects a significant deterioration in the quality of its waters that may lead to non-compliance with its environmental objectives in the future (URA, 2023f). Understanding the reported impacts by the URA on the water bodies in the region, both at a regional and local scale, can offer valuable insights into the environmental status of the Bay of Plentzia, and might give us a starting point to determine the One Health of the SES.

The potential impacts the URA consider include organic, chemical, nutrient and microbiological pollution, habitat alteration due to morphological or hydrological changes, and accumulation of litter (URA, 2023f). While many of these are reported for other freshwater bodies of the Basque Country, in the Butroe, they only identify the presence of organic pollution due to the unfavourable oxygenation conditions in the higher Butroe. They attribute this to urban wastewater discharges not connected to the sewage system and overflow points in Arrieta and Errigoiti. They also indicate, however, the presence of other significant impacts (classified as OTHER, without specifying which ones), since the biological status is considered below good along all the rivers. Therefore, something is assumed to be impacting the river (URA, 2023f).

In the transition and coastal water bodies, the possible impacts that have been reported along the Basque coast include acidification, chemical and microbiological contamination, habitat alteration, temperature increase, accumulation of litter, changes in salinity, and piezometric demise due to water extraction (Solaun et al., 2018). The latest studies in the estuary of Plentzia have not found any of these impacts to be significant, and, according to Solaun et al. (2018), this pattern is replicated in the coastal water body of Cantabria-Matxitxako. Regarding the accumulation of litter, it is worth mentioning how the URA points out that the absence of impact might be due to a lack of standardised and objective criteria to assess it and not because this pressure is non-existent (URA, 2023f).

3.1.4. Areas of interest

The Butroe watershed presents many areas of particular interest due to biological, ecological, geological or cultural characteristics, depicted in Figure 3-10 under different protection figures. With every *Plan hidrológico* of the URA, there is a Register of Protected Areas (RZP³⁹), encompassing zones linked to water environments. Here we include terrestrial areas that are also protected by other plans or regulations.

The whole river basin is identified as a **Sensitive Area** under urban wastewater treatment standards, and one of the tributaries of the Butroe-A is considered an **Area of Environmental Interest**. All the main watercourses of the river, including the estuary, are regarded as a **Special Interest Area for the endangered species *Mustela lutreola***, the European mink. Of the approximate 18mil hectares of the river basin, 6.2mil correspond to **Habitats of Community Interest**, mainly “poor mowing mesophytic grasslands at low altitude (*Alopecurus pratensis*, *Sanguisorba officinalis*)”. Many of these habitats coincide with **the high strategic value of agro-livestock activities, where** areas with greater capacity for agricultural use and greater fragility to deterioration processes are included. The eastern border of the Butroe watershed, adjacent to the Oka watershed, coincides with the limit of the Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve, which provides for important wetlands and resting and wintering areas for migratory birds. Distributed all over the basin, there are many points of **Cultural Heritage**, which mainly include mills and forges, **Landscape** features as the Butroe Castle and the church of *N^a Sra. de Idibalzabal*, and many sites

³⁹ RZP for its Spanish acronym *Registro de Zonas Protegidas*

of **Geological Interest**, such as the dunes of Gorniz, the Butroe meander (Izuskiza) in Plentzia, and the colluvial of Urculumendi, in Gamiz-Fika.

Corresponding to the municipalities that self-supply water, in Meñaka and Arrieta, there are several Water catchment **points for urban supply**. Since they provide an average volume of more than 10 m³/day and supply more than 50 people, they are protected by a safeguard zone. Only one of them, in the town of Errotatxu (Meñaka) supplies a population of between 20,00 and 15,000. Some parcels of land in the area are included in the **Pollutant Site Inventory**, consisting of land with activities or facilities potentially polluting the soil, and includes industries, mostly aggregated around Mungia, or landfills, being the larger ones in Larrabetzu (20.5 ha) and Gatika (8.6 ha). Additionally, some areas are designated as **Restoration Areas for Environmental Improvement**, such as the Larrabetzu landfill site and the basalt quarry in Errigoiti, where environmental improvements will be carried out. The Butroe has also three areas designated as **Areas with Significant Potential Flood Risk** (ARPSI⁴⁰), one in the estuary, another on its way through Gatika, and the last one in the urban area of Mungia.

Two areas are included in the **Red Natura 2000**: the **ZEPA** of the “Marine area of the Mundaka Estuary – Cape Ogoño”, which consists of the entire coastline of the basin, and the **ZEC** and **LIC** of the “Astondo Dunes” in Gorniz, which is also an area for recovery of the endangered plant *Matricaria maritima*. The coastal cliffs in Gorniz are protected under the **Area of Naturalistic Interest of Gorniz-Armitza**, included in the Spatial Planning Guidelines (DOT), and the cliffs between Muriola and the Butroe river mouth are designated as an **Area of special interest for the endangered species *Gulosus aristotelis***, the European shag.

The Bay and the estuary are included in the **National Inventory of Wetlands** under *Ría del Butrón* (Plentzia), comprising the bay, the estuary and the Txipio marshland. The Butroe estuary has another protection, as it is an area where **economically significant aquatic species**, such as mussels, grow, although they are no longer exploited. It is also considered a **vulnerable area** to nitrate pollution from agricultural sources. It contains areas of **recovery and conservation for two threatened flora species**, which are included in the Basque Catalogue of Endangered Species, *Apium graveolens* spp. *butronensis* and the marine plant *Zostera noltii*. Additionally, the beaches of Muriola, Plentzia and Gorniz are designed as **Bathing areas** for recreational purposes and, therefore, are delimited and monitored.

⁴⁰ ARPSI for its Spanish acronym *Áreas con Riesgo Potencial Significativo de Inundación*

Figure 3-10. Areas of interest in the Butroe watershed. Based on URA (2023d). Spatial data from GeoEuskadi.

3.1.5. Pressures

Several aspects could generate pressure on the HOBE focus area along the Basque coast. These include local impacts such as coastal development and habitat alteration, wastewater discharges and sewerage schemes, microbiological pollution, heavy metals, or invasions by non-indigenous species (Franco et al., 2004). Moreover, all the activities carried out in the hydrographic basin of the Butroe River, at a regional scale, may exert a series of additional pressures and ultimately have an impact on humans, animals and ecosystem health of the SES of the Bay of Plentzia.

For each hydrological planning cycle, the URA analyses the pressures on the Basque Country's water bodies, both rivers and coastal and transitional waters (URA, 2023a). Tables 3-6 list the water-related issues considered of major importance in the DHC0 Hydrological Plan 2023 (URA, 2023a) and classify them into four major categories.

Table 3-6. A list of significant problems on the Eastern Cantabrian coast is addressed in the Plan Hidrológico de la DHC0. Tercer ciclo: 2022-2027. The ones the URA considers to be of greater relevance are in bold (URA, 2023a).

Group	Important issues
Meeting environmental objectives	Urban pollution
	Point source pollution from industrial discharges
	Diffuse pollution
	Other sources of pollution
	Morphological alterations
	Implementation of ecological flow regimes
	Invasive allochthonous species
Demand management and rationality of use	Protection of habitats and species associated with protected areas
	Urban and dispersed population supply
	Adaptation to climate change forecasts
Security in the face of extreme events	Other uses
	Floods
	Droughts
Knowledge and governance	Other adverse events
	Coordination between administrations and management
	Cost recovery and financing
	Improvement of knowledge
	Awareness raising, training and public participation

The latest studies from the URA consider that only the riverine water bodies, the Butroe-A and Butroe-B, are under significant pressure. In contrast, the transitional and coastal water masses, e.g. the waters in the Bay of Plentzia, are free of them, regardless of the centralised anthropogenic activity developed around the area (Solaun et al., 2018; URA, 2023f). In the following section, we will assess the inventoried pressures in the Butroe watershed that can influence the water bodies and ultimately affect the health of the Bay of Plentzia system from a One Health perspective.

a. Pollution

Since our focus is the Bay of Plentzia, we put water-associated pollution in the centre without ignoring the existence of other types (e.g. atmospheric pollution). Within the pressure analysis carried out by the URA in the DHC0 Hydrological Plan 2023, they analyse the pollutant loads of the rivers for organic matter (BOD₅) and nutrients (total N and P). Compared to the other main rivers of the Basque Country, the Butroe presents low pollution values, as does the Bay of Plentzia (Solaun et al., 2018; URA, 2023f). Because of their methodology, their results reflect

indicative values of the pollutant pressure in the aquatic environment. Still, they do not correspond to real concentration values (for detailed methodological information, see Solaun et al. (2018) and URA (2023f). Results of their studies show that the Butroe-B might be the river section receiving the highest amounts of organic matter, N and P, especially in the Oleta tributary, which originates on the left bank of the Butroe in the municipality of Mungia (URA, 2023f).

Although the estuary of Plentzia is considered a low to moderately polluted site (Cajaraville et al., 2016), in this section, we want to assess the possible sources of pollution originating in the watershed and arriving through the Butroe River (regional scale) and those occurring next to the Bay (local scale). Polluting pressures can come from point and diffuse sources. Point sources are associated with discharge points and the sewerage network, while diffuse sources are generally related to land uses and runoff water (Solaun et al., 2018). The pollutant sources identified in the Bay of Plentzia include:

Point source pollution:

- ✓ Urban discharges
- ✓ Industrial discharges
- ✓ Stormwater discharges
- ✓ Landfills and waste disposal facilities
- ✓ Point sources of atmospheric pollution
- ✓ Petroleum products storage area

Diffuse source pollution:

- ✓ Agricultural activities
- ✓ Livestock
- ✓ Forestry activities
- ✓ Contaminated areas due to active or abandoned human activities
- ✓ Transport
- ✓ Urban runoff
- ✓ Marine litter

Point source pollution

Most point source pollution is associated with discharge waters from urban or industrial origins. Additionally, we include emission points of atmospheric pollution. To analyse this type of pressure, we have identified the discharge points in the watershed, compiled in the 2022 Discharge Inventory (*Censo de Vertidos 2022*) of the CAPV, available on the URA website, both from urban, industrial and stormwater discharges (Figure 3-11). We included information from the Basque Emissions and Pollutant Sources (*Registro vasco de emisiones y fuentes contaminantes del 2021*; Gobierno Vasco, 2023). In the Butroe watershed, there are 121 discharge points to the public water domain or from land to sea, including 102 urban discharges and 19 discharges of industrial origin not connected to this urban sanitation network. Additionally, there are also 18 overflow points for stormwater discharges.

Of the 102 **urban discharge** points, more than half correspond to wastewater collection and treatment activities. These contain 93.6 % of the total volume of urban wastewater discharged in the area (Gobierno Vasco, 2023b).

Figure 3-11. Point source pollution in the Butroe watershed. Water discharges from the “Censo de Vertidos de la CAPV” of 2022 associated to different economic activities of the CNAE (URA, 2020a). Black dots represent overflow points of the sewerage system (URA, 2020b, 2021). Turquoise diamonds represent sources of atmospheric pollution from the “Registro de Emisiones y Transferencias de Contaminantes del 2021 (PRTR)” of the Gobierno Vasco (2023b).

Most discharge points are found in inland municipalities, while only four are connected to the urban sanitation network in Barrika, Plentzia, and Gorliz. The main discharge points in the watershed correspond to the two main WWTPs, Gorliz and Mungia, both managed by the Bilbao-Viscay Water Consortium. Other smaller WWTPs exist, such as the Ametza WWTP, the Meñakabarrena WWTP in Meñaka, and the Berreagamendi 1 and 2 in Mungia. However, their equivalent inhabitants are less than 2000, so their pressure is lower.

The Mungia WWTP treats water coming from the upper and the middle Butroe. It receives discharges from industries in Mungia and Gatika, as well as from the urban sewage system of the municipalities of Mungia, Fruiz, Gamiz-Fika, Maruri-Jatabe, Gatika and Laukiz (URA, 2021). The Gorliz WWTP began operating in 1997 and collects the wastewater of the municipalities of Barrika, Gorliz and Plentzia. According to the URA’s 2022 Discharge Inventory, the pollutant load of the raw wastewater before treatment is 17,776 equivalent inhabitants. However, in the *Resolución RTM-B-2019-0001_5-7/V/B* (URA, 2020b), it is pointed out that the equivalent number of inhabitants is 18,446, 5,924 of them occasional inhabitants, probably living in the area only during summer.

Initially, this WWTP was discharged into the Bay and operated on with a primary physico-chemical treatment. In 2006, it was improved with a secondary biological treatment, and in 2011, the outfall was moved out of the bay, which improved the water quality status (Borja et al., 2022; Díez et al., 2012). The water in this WWTP can follow two routes (Table 4-7), the first one (V1) going through a complete treatment and the second (V2) going through an incomplete one. V1 includes a pre-treatment, biological treatment and disinfection, a secondary aerobic treatment with DBO removal above 80%, and total nitrogen and phosphorus removal. Later, the treated waters will be discharged in the submarine outfall just outside the Bay of Plentzia. V2, on the other hand, is the route waste water follows when intense rainfall events occur. Here, there is only pre-treatment of the water, which is stored in storm tanks, to be released into the environment

through overflow spillways when the WWTP's capacity is surpassed. For more information about water treatment at the Gorliz WWTP, see Quintano (2005).

Table 3-7. Characteristics of the WWTP and annual mean of pollutant concentrations in 2022 for the emission of treated wastewater. Treatment V1: complete, pre-treatment, biological treatment and disinfection. Treatment V2: incomplete in rainfall events, pre-treatment and storm tank storage. Pollutants permitted concentration between brackets. Data from: (a) URA (2020b, 2021)(b) Datos de aglomeraciones mayores a 2000 habitantes equivalentes (URA, 2022b), and c) Mijangos et al. (2020)

	WWTP			
	Gorliz		Mungia	
Population equivalents ^a	18,446 (10,373 fact residents and 3.924 occasional residents)		21,616	
Origin ^c	1.3 % Hospital	98.7 % Domestic	3.1 % Industrial	98.7 % Domestic
Max. autor. flow (m ³ /year) ^b	1,765,972		3,150,000	
Max. flow per treatment (m ³ /h) ^a	V1: 863	V2: 2,160	V1: 650	V2: 927
Annual volume (m ³) ^a	1,700,000	65,972	2,600,000	550,000
Effluents discharges ^c	Submarine pipe that releases effluent 1 km from the coast, at 18 m depth in the Bay opening		Effluent into the upper part (22 km from the mouth) of the estuary	
Average pollutant concentrations in 2022 (mg/L)^b				
Chemical Oxygen Demand	43.9 (125)		37.45 (125)	
Biological Oxygen Demand	4.77 (25)		4.93 (25)	
Suspended Sediments	13.59 (35)		11.95 (35)	
Total Nitrogen	NA (15)		4.11 (15)	
Total Phosphorus	NA (2)		1.23 (2)	

For these WWTPs, certain parameters are continuously monitored to ensure that they do not exceed the emission limit values established by the regulation of urban wastewater. These are the biological oxygen demand, chemical oxygen demand, and the suspended solids, and additionally include total nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) if the spill discharges into sensitive areas to nutrient supply. Table 3-7 shows how none of the emission limits was exceeded in 2022, however, it is worth mentioning that in November 2022, the phosphorus concentration in Mungia WWTP was 2.39 mg/L, 0.39 units above the allowed concentration.

Storm water discharges serve as overflow points to relieve the sewage system during heavy rainfall events. Along the Butroe river there are many of these (Figure 3-11), 10 associated with the Mungia sanitation network, and 10 associated with the Gorliz one. If the WWTP is permitted, maximum flow is exceeded, whether due to a lack of transport or treatment capacity; these tanks serve as regulation infrastructure and cause overflows to relieve the load on the primary sanitation network.

They are distributed along the Butroe watershed, more concentrated in the lower stretches. At the Bay of Plentzia scale, the outfalls from Gorliz WWTP are of special relevance. Six are associated with the collector network along the Butroe estuary, one is associated with the emergency collector of the WWTP, and three discharge next to the treated wastewater discharge point outside the Bay (Figure 3-11). Some of these overflow points have a screening system of 4 mm.

Episodes of storm overflows must be recorded, and the relieved flows (treated and no-treated) must be reported to the URA and be available in the internet tool DKT⁴¹. This data must be provided by the operator of the WWTP and be publicly available on the URA's website. In the graphs provided, however, only the treated flows are reported, and data on the volume of discharged untreated water is not yet available. This prevents us from knowing the actual load of pollutants carried by the river, which finally reached the Bay of Plentzia. Consequently, we do not have a true picture of the contamination state of the Plentzia system since, for example, in

⁴¹ DKT for its Basque acronym *Datuak Kudeatzeko Tresna/Sistema de Carga de Analíticas*

the case of N and P, the main pathway of arrival is through the waters of the river and not so much through discharge points (Solaun et al., 2018).

Most of the **industrial discharges** are located in the municipality of Mungia, in the middle section of the Butroe (Figure 3-11). Only two produce hazardous substances, one related to waste treatment and the other with metal treatment and coating industry. The first, in Barro Astorekas, Larrabetzu, is an inert substances⁴² landfill discharge. It belongs to Cespa Gestión de Residuos S.A. and in the last years, it has contained hazardous wastes, such as certain laboratory chemicals, non-chlorinated-mineral-hydraulic oils, contaminated containers, among others (Gobierno de España, 2022a). This is one of the areas that has been designated as a restoration area for environmental improvement (Figure 3-9). The second one, in Mungia, belongs to Estampaciones Bideazabal S.L., a company dedicated to producing, assembling, and distributing sheet metal parts and products.

In 2022, a total of 209,437.45 m³ of industrial wastewater was discharged into the river; most of it came from the gravel bed in Errigoiti, where the company Áridos y Canteras del Norte, S.A. carries out the extraction of basaltic aggregates (Figure 3-11). Another significant fraction belongs to waste management, especially for treating and eliminating waste and the aforementioned Cespa Gestión de Residuos S.A.U. in Larrabetzu. Almost another third of the wastewater comes from manufacturing industries. From these, the one that generates the greatest volume of wastewater is GARAIA Koop, in Mungia, a cooperative dedicated to the production and processing of local and seasonal agricultural products, with labels such as Eusko Label and Euskal Baserri, among others. Finally, a much smaller fraction of the industrial wastewater discharged in the area corresponds to economic activities related to agriculture, such as winemaking, poultry farming, and other livestock support activities (Figure 3-12).

Figure 3-12. Industrial discharges classified according to the associated economic activity of the CNAE and the corresponding volume (m³) of wastewater discharged in the environment in 2022.

Regarding **landfills and waste disposal facilities** the main one, registered in the Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (PRTR⁴³), is the one from Larrabetzu, from the company Cespa Gestión de Residuos, S.A. It is the same landfill mentioned in the *Industrial discharges* and is responsible for the aforementioned wastewater discharges. With a surface of 366.600 m², this landfill eliminates waste previously treated or not reusable, consisting of stabilised/solidified waste, insulation and construction materials containing asbestos. Other waste, which is considered reusable, such as paper and cardboard, metals, wood, plastic and metal packaging, end-of-life tyres, etc., are separated and sent for recovery to other specified plants (Gobierno Vasco, 2013). The activity of the landfill also generates several types of waste that have to be transferred as well to other waste treatment plants. Table 3-8 describes the amount of waste generated in 2020, when the main was sewage sludge.

⁴² Inert substances are those that do not experience any transformation and do not present any risk to surface or groundwater.

⁴³ Registro de Emisiones y Transferencias de Contaminantes

Table 3-8. Dangerous and no-dangerous waste was transferred by the landfill in 2020. Data from Gobierno de España (2022a).

Type	Descripción	T/year
No-dangerous	Plastic packaging	0.025
	End-of-life tyres	0.04
	Paper and cardboard	0.03
	Glass	0.015
	Septic tank sludge	3.36
Dangerous	Non-chlorinated mineral hydraulic oils	0.01
	Packaging containing traces of, or contaminated by, hazardous substances	0.2
	Laboratory chemicals consisting of or containing dangerous substances, including mixtures of laboratory chemicals	0.01

The decontamination and waste management activities developed in the Larrabetzu landfill generate a series of pollutants and waste residues (Tables 3-8 and 3-9). The lixiviates of the landfill are collected and conducted at a treatment plant, where they follow a physicochemical and biological (nitrification-denitrification) treatment. After the treatment, they are released in the Atxipe stream, which will flow into the Butroe river. This flow is controlled by an environmental monitoring programme, which, in 2021, gave the annual concentrations of emitted pollutants specified in Table 3-9.

Finally, it is worth mentioning that the URA has reported the presence of several old waste deposits, all of them in the channel police area. (URA, 2023f) However, no further information on these deposits has been found.

Table 3-9. List of pollutants and quantities generated by the landfill and emitted to the environment after the treatment process in 2021. Data from Gobierno de España (2022a).

Receiving environment	Pollutant	Kg/year
Atxipe stream	Organohalogen compounds and substances that can give rise to compounds of this class in the aquatic environment (such as AOx)	9.88
	Arsenic and its compounds	0.25
	Nickel and its compounds	0.76
	Copper and its compounds	0.22
	Zinc and its compounds	0.7
	Chlorides (as total Cl)	23943.75
	Phenols	2.04
	Fluorides	37.87
	Total nitrogen	15.01
	Total phosphorus	7.87
	Chemical oxygen demand (COD)	2029.77
	Total organic carbon (TOC)	858.3

In the area, there are also two sources of **atmospheric pollution**, also included in the PRTR, corresponding to two installations for intensive rearing of poultry. One is the Granja Uriagereka, S.L., in Mungia, and the other is the Larrabe Oilotegia in Gamiz-Fika. The pollutants emitted to the atmosphere in 2021 are listed in Table 3-10). The Larrabe Oilotegia has also a wastewater discharge that has been mentioned before in the industrial discharges related to agricultural activities. Between these two farms, the study area has more than 40,000 places for laying hens in industrial complexes dedicated to producing and marketing eggs (Gobierno Vasco, 2012).

Table 3-10. Amount of pollutants emitted to the atmosphere in 2021 by the two poultry farms in the Butroe SA included in the PRTR. Data from Gobierno Vasco (2023b).

	Emitted quantity (kg/year)	
	Gamiz-Fika	Mungia
	Larrabe Oilotegia, S.A.t.	Granja Uriagereka, S.L.
Methane (CH ₄)	17654.42	8314.56
Nitrous oxide (N ₂ O)	1541.73	726.55
Ammonia (NH ₃)	4476	3251.56
Particulate matter (PM ₁₀)	18185.76	8567.89
Total suspended particulate matter (TSP)	2	-

As for **storage areas for petroleum products**, although there are no refineries in the study area, there are seven stations and a wholesale trade concentrated in the lower and middle reaches of the river, some of them close to the Butroe river course (URA, 2023f).

It is also worth mentioning that in the coastal mass of Cantabria-Matxitxaco, just over 10 km from the coast of Armintza, an exploitation permit (*Permiso Albatros*) has been granted for the extraction of fossil fuels (Gobierno de España, 2023b). It covers a total surface of 3,233.88 ha and is operated by REPSOL Investigaciones Petrolíferas S.A. (RIPSA). While the gas storage platform and pipelines pose a potential risk (Borja et al., 2011), no references have been found to indicate a pressure in the area.

Diffuse source pollution

Pollution from diffuse sources can come from agricultural, livestock, and logging activities, contaminated areas, transport, urban runoff, and debris and plastic (Solaun et al., 2018; URA, 2023f).

To assess the pressure of **agricultural activities** in the Butroe SA, we determined the land area covered by agricultural plots for crop or livestock production, which farmers have registered in the SIGPAC⁴⁴ 2023. According to this geospatial data, the agricultural land used for cultivation of crops or for livestock production represents 46.36 % of the Butroe watershed surface. Many of these parcels are used for pastures (61%), shrub pastures (22%), and pastures with trees (3%), while only a smaller proportion is used for the production of vegetables or fruits (Figure 3-13).

⁴⁴ Geographical Information System for Agricultural Parcels – SIGPAC, by its Spanish acronym, *Sistema de información Geográfica de Parcelas Agrícolas*

Figure 3-13. Types and surface percentages of agricultural plots for crop or livestock production the Butroe SA. Null percentage indicates that the crop type is present, but its surface coverage is very small. Data from SIGPAC 2023.

Agricultural parcels have a denser distribution in the sub-catchments of the middle Butroe, in areas belonging to Gatik and Mungia; therefore, this section could be under higher pressure than the rest of the river. However, the URA's analysis on agricultural diffuse pollution (kg/ha of N and P) indicates that this pressure is insignificant in the Butroe watershed. They find that in Errigoiti, on the upper reaches of the river, the nitrogen concentration is higher than the acceptable threshold, and therefore, waters could contain pollutants (URA, 2023f). According to data from SIOSE⁴⁵. The sub-watersheds corresponding to the Errigoiti area have a rather low surface coverage of agricultural parcels compared to other areas; however, it is still between 24 and 36% (Figure 3-14). The main production consists of herbaceous crops, non-citrus fruit trees, and meadows. It would, therefore, be advisable to carry out a more detailed study of agricultural activity and nitrogen loads in Errigoiti.

Figure 3-14. Percentages of agricultural plots for crop or livestock production the Butroe SA. Data from SIGPAC 2023.

Livestock activities, especially when the livestock is not housed and the wastewater collected, can also be a source of diffuse pollution. No geo-referenced information on livestock holdings in the Butroe watershed has been found, and neither the pastures registered in SIGPAC used for grazing livestock could be identified. Therefore, we could not analyse the diffuse pressure of livestock per sub-watershed. However, Eustat conducted an Agricultural Census (*Censo Agrario*) in 2020, where the number of livestock heads is documented per municipality. Following these numbers, in the study area municipalities, there are 488 livestock holdings; however, this number does not reflect which of these farms are located within the Butroe watershed since it might include some outside the drainage divide. It might exclude some within the watershed but in unaddressed municipalities (e.g. Sopela, Lemoiz, Loiu, or Larrabetzu). Most of them can be found in Mungia (108 farms), and as has previously been specified, they are mainly sheep and goats. Another way to assess the livestock pressure is by looking at the livestock units⁴⁶. There

⁴⁵ Land Occupation Information System - SIOSE, by its Spanish acronym, *Sistema de Información sobre Ocupación del Suelo en España*

⁴⁶ According to the INE, a livestock unit is a value for expressing livestock data, in which a coefficient is assigned to each species and type, to aggregate them into a common and comparable unit. It is used to add livestock of cattle, sheep, goats, pigs, poultry, and rabbits in a comparable way (it excludes hives and bees).

are a total of 7,637.90 livestock units in the region, with Gamiz-Fika and Mungia the municipalities with the highest number, 3,127.33 and 2,416.71, respectively.

In the URA's pressure analysis (URA, 2023f), they calculated the pollutant loads of nitrogen and phosphorus emitted to the Butroe due to livestock farming. According to their results, this could also be the case for the water flowing through Gatika. Therefore, as Solaun et al. (2018) also mention, the Butroe-B section is considered to be under pressure by livestock activities.

Forestry activities are highly present in the study area. These activities' pressures are particularly related to certain intensive practices with heavy machinery consisting of clear-cutting and land preparation for the next plantation. These mainly occur in eucalyptus and conifer plantations, which account for 96.98 % of the plantations in the area (Figure 3-15). The sub-catchment areas with the highest percentage of plantation forest (between 47 and 70% of the surface) are located at the headwaters of the Butroe River, and in the north-side of Mungia (Figure 3-16).

Figure 3-15. Extension of forest types in the Butroe SA. Data from Mapa Forestal 2022 of the Gobierno Vasco.

Figure 3-16. Subwatershed with the highest coverage by plantation forests. Data from Mapa Forestal 2022 of Gobierno Vasco.

On the other hand, **contaminated areas due to active or abandoned human activities** are also present in the area (URA, 2023f). However, the surface they cover is very small compared to other neighbour watersheds (e.g., the Nervion-Ibaizabal). In the Butroe, the areas that present these characteristics are concentrated around Mungia and the middle section of the river. Contaminated soils are also present in a sub-catchment of Barrika, which flows into Muriola Beach. Since it corresponds to a bathing area, further investigation of the nature of these plots in Barrika would be appropriate.

Pressure due to **land transportation** (roads, highways, main roads, urban roads, railroads and roads without a classification) is relatively low (URA, 2023f). The area under the highest pressure is the village of Plentzia. The other two municipalities of the Bay of Plentzia also present a higher percentage than the rest of the watershed, which is also the case for the city of Mungia and the south of the municipality of Mungia, where the highway to Bilbao passes through. The **maritime transport** is dense around the opening of the Bay. The fishing activity is concentrated in the harbours of Santurzi and Bermeo, and most fishing routes follow the coastline. Therefore, many vessels pass in front of the Bay. Additionally, some longline fishing vessels that are engaged in fishing operations stay off the coast of the study area. Inside the Bay of Plentzia, the main pressure would come from recreational boats anchored in the area that move in and out of the estuary. The port is called La Gallarda, which hosts 168 pontoon moorings (Ferrer, 2017). Outside, along the estuary and up to the bridge of Plentzia, many other vessels not assigned to the port use the space for berthing. The dock has a higher probability of spillage since people supply fuel to the vessels, where goods are loaded and unloaded, where used oils are collected, etc. Although no record of recent spill accidents has been found, the harmful substances that can be accidentally spilt in the port are fuel oil, diesel, gasoline, sodium hydroxide, NaOH, potassium hydroxide, KOH, etc. (Ferrer, 2017).

Another source of diffuse pollution comes from the **runoff of urban and industrial areas**. Besides having a sewerage system that collects wastewater, rainwater passing through these poorly permeable surfaces can carry pollutants that eventually reach the water bodies through surface runoff. If we consider built-up and unbuilt-up land, paved or sealed areas, artificial green areas and urban trees, extraction or disposal areas, and transport routes, the areas with the higher occupation are around the Bay of Plentzia and in Mungia (SIOSE, 2017).

Marine litter, which can be either macro- or micro-particles, can generate pressures on the environment and organisms depending on its quantity, spatial distribution and composition (Solaun et al., 2018). It comprises any persistent solids of non-natural, e.g., manufactured origin, which have been discarded, deposited or abandoned in marine and/or coastal environments. In the Bay of Plentzia, there is no current information available on its accumulation, so the potential pressure it may exert remains unknown.

b. Changes in morphology

Morphological alterations of the habitat are the second type of pressures on the Bay of Plentzia. They can occur at two scales: locally, in the bay, the adjacent estuary and the nearby coast, and regionally, on a bigger scale, at the watershed level (Table 3-11). The second comprises alterations in the river course and ultimately has implications for the freshwater that carries the Butroe River and arrives at the Bay. These pressures have repercussions on the hydrological regime of the estuary and the Bay.

Table 3-11. A list of morphological alterations was identified in the HOBE focus area and the Butroe watershed (Solaun et al., 2023e).

Bay of Plentzia	Butroe River
Longitudinal Alteration of the Coastline	Longitudinal Alteration of Margins
Channelling infrastructures	Bank defences
Longitudinal structures of protection	Channelling infrastructures
Port docks	River Covers, Curts or Deviations of the Watercourse
Physical Alteration of the Seabed	River covers
Dredging	Artificial cutting of meanders
Transversal Alteration of the Coastline	Channel detours
Channel dikes	River Obstacles
Breakwaters	Wires, dams...
Jetties	Inadequate Riparian Vegetation
Physical loss	Riparian Quality Index Adapted
Isolation of inter-tidal zone	
Occupation of inter-tidal zone	

The Butroe transition has a margin of a total length of 21,531 m, of which 6,968 m (32%) are **longitudinally altered**. Most of these structures are coating channels in sections of the lower estuary, which cover a longitude of 4,242 m. Additionally, there is also one longitudinal 203 m structure of protection on the beach of Gorliz and several docks in the port of Plentzia, which cover 724 m (Solaun et al., 2018).

The **physical alteration** in the study area has not been on the seabed but by dredging activities inside the port of Plentzia and along the estuary (Table 3-12). The Butroe transition is the body of water with the most considerable dredged material on the Basque Coast, mainly for beach regeneration (Solaun et al., 2018). Another activity planned in the Bay of Plentzia that could generate this type of pressure is the construction of the artificial reef by the Gorliz town council and the PiE-UPV/EHU. In the framework of the PIE REEF project, an eco-designed reef is to be built in front of Errotatxu cove to protect and restore marine habitats in the area, promoting the circular economy, ecotourism, training and scientific activities (Ayuntamiento de Gorliz, 2022).

Table 3-12. Extraction of material in the Butroe estuary used for beach rehabilitation (Solaun et al., 2018).

Extraction area	Date	Volume (m ³)	Regenerated beaches
Butroe (channel)	1986	100,000	Plentzia and Gorliz
Port of Plentzia	2002	95,000	Plentzia and Gorliz
Butroe (channel)	2003	112,000	Plentzia and Gorliz
Butroe (mouth and channel)	2007	75,787	Gorliz

The Butroe transition presents a low **transversal alteration of the coastline**. In the Bay of Plentzia, there are only channel dykes, two measuring less than 50 m and two measuring more. The length of coastline alteration is 664m, representing only 3% of the 21 531 m of total coastline.

The **physical loss** of the water body implies the total or partial disappearance of a body of water, mainly associated with land reclamation, infrastructure construction, or agricultural activities. The surface of the public domain that the port of Plentzia occupies is 189,570 m², representing less than 20% of the surface of the water masses (Solaun et al., 2018). Regarding sections of the estuary that are isolated, the Butroe estuary is the water mass with the highest surface isolated in all the Basque Country (90,763 m², 5 % of the total surface), corresponding to the old tide mill

of Plentzia and the meadow Txipio, which was isolated from the rest of the river by the Barrika-Plentzia road due to its use as agricultural fields during the last century (Solaun et al., 2018).

At the regional scale, morphological alterations of the Butroe River are related to modifications in the river course or the river margins. **Longitudinal alterations of the margins** are due to bank defences and channelling infrastructures. There are 63 bank defence structures, with a longitude of 5,727 m, affecting only 4.2 % of the margins, and 82 channels, with a total longitude of 13,933, covering 10.3 % of the margins. None covers more than 30% of the water mass's total longitude; thus, they are not considered to exert significant pressure (URA, 2023f).

Another river flow alteration may be due to the construction of **river covers, artificial cutting of meanders, curvature reduction actions or channel detours**. The Butroe presents 5 covered sections along its course, occupying a total longitude of 183 m, most in the lower Butroe, representing only 0.3 % of its total longitude. Thus, the pressure is considered low. The most affected section is in the Oleta tributary (Butroe-B), which has a covered longitude of 117 m (URA, 2018). About cuts or detours of the waterway, the Butroe presents 11 sections, representing a total length of 50,219 m of original modified length, which nowadays corresponds to 48,940 m of modified section. The cut length represents 1.9% of the total watercourse length, the highest value for a river in the DHCO (URA, 2018). This pressure is considered to be especially elevated again in the Oleta tributary (245 m cut) and a section of the main Butroe (288 m) (URA, 2018).

Another type of morphological alteration is **river obstacles**. The AMBER Project identified 60 river obstacles in the study area, 26 of them weirs, 2 dams, and 32 others (AMBER Consortium, 2020). Some of these infrastructures are now in obsolete conditions: the dam of Sollube, in Meñaka, has been partially demolished (URA, 2018), while the other one, of Laukaiz-Oleta, in Mungia, is still being used for recreational activities, water supply by the golf course of Laukariz Country Club (URA, 2023f). All these obstacles give a mean passability index low to the river, especially to the lowest section (URA, 2023f).

Finally, morphological alterations along the river are also reflected in **inadequate riparian vegetation**. In the 70s, many sections of the riparian forest were eliminated. Although many of them have been re-naturalised, the Riparian Quality Index Adapted (RQIA) is inadequate for more than 50% of the river longitude, which means that the structures and functions of the riparian community remain deteriorated. Only the river's headwaters maintain the original riparian width, with the original alluvial forest of *Alnus glutinosa* and *Fraxinus excelsior* (URA, 2018).

c. Alteration of the hydrological regime

The pressures related to the alteration of the hydrological regime in the area are mainly water abstraction. The Bay of Plentzia is a system highly influenced by the river; alterations to the hydrodynamics of the river will have consequences in the amount of water that flows into the sea and, therefore, in the hydrodynamics of the bay. The causes might be found in riverine **water abstraction** for different uses in the watershed and in physical alteration of the morphology of the river, which has already been reviewed in the previous section.

Borja et al. (2006) consider that in marine and estuarine environments of the Basque Country, the main water abstractions are for hydroenergy, aquaculture and thalassotherapy (use of seawater in cosmetic and health treatment). However, in the Bay of Plentzia, no surface water withdrawals could be considered a significant pressure on the system (Solaun et al., 2018). At a watershed level, water abstraction from local resources only occurs in Meñaka, Arrieta, and Errigoiti and is never large enough to approach the limits set by the ecological minimum flow (URA, 2023a).

d. Biodiversity loss or changes

Resources exploitation that can pressure coastal systems are related to fishing/angling, shellfishing and algae exploitation. These activities might impact the exploited communities and

the associated ecosystems where these activities are developed (Galparsoro & Borja, 2021). As mentioned, the port of Plentzia has a recreational rather than a fishing function. Fish catches are small-scale, so the pressure is probably not very high. As far as shellfishing is concerned, it has also been mentioned that, despite having potentially exploitable areas, this activity has ceased in the Butroe estuary. Finally, no record of any seaweed exploitation in the area has been found.

Another critical pressure to consider is introducing non-indigenous species (NIS), which can affect individuals, communities, ecosystems, and socioeconomic levels (Alemany et al., 2012). Over the last decades, the presence of NIS organisms has been increasing, linked to many other reasons for global change and shifting from temperate species to tropical and subtropical ones (Borja et al., 2011; Campos et al., 2016). Gorliz has the highest invasion level and NIS flora species records. Annex Chapter 3-1 shows the most relevant invasive species detected near the Butroe, considering their wide distribution, high abundance and recorded negative impacts.

At the Bay level, the presence of NIS might have important implications for the marine ecosystem. In the NIS inventory of the Basque coast elaborated by Zorita et al. (2009), they studied the presence of exotic macroalgae and macroinvertebrates of hard and soft sea bottom. In the Butroe estuary, they recorded 190 native species and 21 exotics, only 1.6% cases of exotic vs. native species, few when compared to other river bodies of water, such as the Nerbioi, with 3.6%. In the coastal water mass of Cantabria-Matxitxako, they found 899 native species vs. 34 exotics (0.6 %)(see Zorita et al. (2013) for more information).

Presence of NIS at the watershed level might also have effects on the Bay. The riparian habitat has been particularly vulnerable to the introduction of species, either due to artificial revegetation of slopes, or by the arrival of fast-growing species from parks and gardens. Among the allochthonous flora species found in the Butroe watershed there is a citation of the herbaceous perennial *Fallopia japonica*, considered one of the 100 most harmful invasive species worldwide, which in other watersheds, has had severe repercussions for original riparian habitats and relevant socioeconomic consequences (Herrera Gallastegui & Campos Prieto, 2010). *Carpobrotus edulis*, *Cortaderia selloana* and *Baccharis halimifolia*, all included in Spain's 20 most harmful alien species, appear in more abundance around the area.

Introduced diseases are also a relevant pressure in the area. An example can be the Bluetongue (BT) disease, produced by an arbovirus from sub-Saharan Africa, Asia and the Middle East, which appeared for the first time in the Iberian Peninsula in 1998, associated with the biting midge *Culicoides* sp. The Basque Country was a low-risk area for BT until 2007, when several outbreaks occurred in the autonomous community, with some reports close to the Butroe. It affects mainly cattle, sheep, and goats, producing a series of clinical signs (ataxia, mouth ulcers, fever...) and mortality (García-Lastra et al., 2012). Another example of an introduced disease is the pitch canker caused by the American fungus *Fusarium circinatum*. This disease negatively affects *Pinus* species, impacting their growth and causing the death of mature trees and seedlings. It has detrimental effects on native populations and plantation trees, and Iturritxa et al. (2011) identified a *Pinus radiata* infected by this fungus in Laukiz.

Finally, another source of possible impacts on the system is the appearance of **Harmful Algal Blooms**. However, no toxic blooms have been recently reported, and the last phytoplankton proliferation in the Bay occurred in 2021 and was produced by the species *Plagioselmis* sp. On the other hand, in 2022 other potentially harmful species were detected (Annex Chapter 3-2), although none in harmful concentrations. Some of them have toxin-producing capacity, or serve as vectors for toxins, while others can be harmful to ecosystems by the simple fact of the great biomass abundance of the bloom. Toxic species like *Dinophysis acuminata* and *Prorocentrum reticulatum* have lower alarming concentrations thresholds, and the detection of species such as *Alexandrium* sp., already indicates a possible risk (Revilla et al., 2023).

e. Climate change

Although climate change is a global phenomenon, many of its effects can be seen locally. They are related to the increase in temperature, the rise of the sea level, and the increase in extreme events such as floods and droughts (URA, 2023i).

The URA states that with an **increase in temperature** in the freshwater domain, there would be a loss of habitat for cold water fish species, reduction of dissolved oxygen in the water and impacts on macroinvertebrate species, which is likely to happen in the Butroe under the high emission scenario of RCP8.5 (URA, 2023i). On the coast, sea temperature has also increased from the surface to 100 m depth since the 1980s, which may have favoured warm-water species arriving at the Bay and displaced original cold-water species (Chust et al., 2022).

Sea level rise is also a consequence of climate change, and it has been reported to increase between 1.5 and 3.5 cm per decade in the Gulf of Biscay. Additionally, extreme wave events have been observed in the area, with wave heights increasing by 16.8 cm per decade (Chust et al., 2021, 2022). This might have several impacts, including coastal erosion, morphological alterations of the estuary, and risks to the coastal socio-ecological system. See the KOSTAEGOKI Project Summary Document I for more information on the vulnerability and risk of Climate Change in the Basque Country (Ihobe S.A. & Gobierno Vasco, 2022).

Figure 3-17. Flow concentration zone in the Butroe watershed (GeoEuskadi). Land cover from Corine Land Cover 2018, Plantation forests from Mapa Forestal 2022 of the Gobierno Vasco.

In the Butroe watershed, **droughts** are not considered a major gravity problem. On the other hand, several areas of significant potential **flood** risk (ARPSI) have been identified in Plentzia, Mungia and Gatika (URA 2023j). Figure 3-17 indicates that the Flow Concentration Zone of the Butroe, which covers 857 ha and corresponds to the area most likely to be flooded, consists mainly of heterogeneous agricultural areas upstream of Mungia and in Gatika. It also covers the urban centre of Mungia and, on a smaller scale, some infrastructures in Plentzia and Barrika, where the rising water could cause the beaches to disappear and bring the intertidal limit inland (URA, 2023i).

3.2. A One Health Approach applied to the Socio-Ecological System of the Transition of Butroe and Bay of Plentzia

The overview of the Butroe watershed contextualises the SES of the Bay of Plentzia and indicates potential influences that may come from the Butroe to the Bay. However, to better understand how health is determined in the system, we are interested in a more specific focus on the local surroundings (Figure 3-18). The HOBE Focus Area has a total surface of 2548.26 ha, of which 73.9 ha correspond to the surface of the Bay (Table 3-2). The remaining 2474.4 ha (including the 87.7 ha of the estuary's surface) belong mainly to Gorniz (782.46 ha), Barrika (589.58 ha), and Plentzia (584.45 ha), which is wholly included in the Focus Area. It is worth noticing that a lesser extent of the area, with urban centres and agricultural activities, belongs to Urduliz (212.06 ha), Lemoiz (192.27 ha), and Gatika (112.92 ha) (Figure 3-18). However, our focus will be on the first three municipalities, as these are the coastal ones with the most interrelation with the Bay.

Looking at our conceptual framework, we visualise the configuration of health from four groups of determinants: Nature's Contribution to People (Brauman et al., 2020; Díaz et al., 2018), Determinants of Human Health (Choi & Sonin, 2018), Determinants of Animal Health (Bauman & Parmley, 2021; Wittrock & Duncan, 2019; Card et al., 2018; Cipolla et al., 2015), and Socioeconomic Determinants of Health (Rój & Jankowiak, 2021). As shown in Chapter 1, these determinants might interact at different levels of system organisation. For example, in human health, they can interact on the scale of global society, culture or nation, community, family, person, microbiome, organs, cells or molecules (see Figure 1-1). Here, our main focus will be on the interactions that take place at the intermediate scale (e.g., community, family and person), not forgetting that these are part of a larger multiscale network of interrelationships that shape the OH of the Bay of Plentzia.

Figure 3-18. Socio-ecological system of Butroe River transition and Bay of Plentzia. DOT = Directrices de Ordenación Territorial.

3.2.1. Human Health

The public health system of the Basque Country, Osakidetza, has a health centre in each municipality that must provide **quality health care** to the local inhabitants. In addition, the Gorliz hospital, which has been located on the beach since 1919, provides care for patients with non-acute pathologies in the stabilisation phase, convalescence, palliative care, and rehabilitation treatment. However, for general hospital care, the inhabitants of the Bay must go to the Alfredo Espinosa Hospital, located in Urduliz, outside the HOBE Focus Area. Additionally, there are several private clinics for general medicine, physiotherapy, osteopathy, podiatry, dermatology, psychopedagogy, nutritionists, and dentists. Some importance has also been given to the **health literacy** of the Bay's inhabitants through the promotion of the Osasun Sarea Gorliz and a meeting space for citizen's involvement in the construction of their health through participative sessions, workshops and seminars, public marches, or the creation of the Aramburu Pharmacy-Museum, in the pharmacy with the same name opened in 1888, with exhibitions on the evolution of medicine over the last century.

The physical environment, both natural and built, is also an important factor that contributes to health. The **location** of the three municipalities facilitates the outdoor activities of its inhabitants, both in blue (e.g., beaches, sea, and estuary) and green areas (e.g., the pine forest of Gorliz, hiking trails along the coastal cliffs and the river shore...). However, this is associated with the inhabitant imbalance between the winter and summer months, when the population of the Bay is triplicated. The location is also related to many other factors (e.g., crime level, public space, education and job opportunities...) that will be discussed further below in the socioeconomic determinants. On the other hand, it may also determine the presence or absence of **pollution**. Due to the recreational use of the bathing areas, the beaches of Muriola, Plentzia and Gorliz are protected and monitored with special interest to ensure an excellent health status of both the population and the environment (Table 3-14).

Table 3-14. Assessment of the factors that may be detrimental to the health control of the bathing waters in the Bay of Plentzia. From (Solaun et al. 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d).

	Muriola	Plentzia	Gorliz
Subjected to relevant pollution pressures	No	Yes	Yes
Riverine influence	Yes	Yes	Yes
Urban sanitation	No	Yes	Yes
Port facilities	No	Yes	Yes
Industrial facilities	No	No	No
Global contamination risk	No risk	Low	Low
Microbiological contamination risk	No risk	Low	Low
Susceptibility to proliferation of biological elements	No risk	No risk	No risk
<i>Phytoplankton proliferation risk</i>	Low	Low	Low
<i>Microalgae proliferation risk</i>	Very low	Very Low	Very Low
<i>Macroalgae proliferation risk</i>	Very low	Very Low	Very Low
<i>Jellyfish proliferation risk</i>	Low	Low	Low

The beaches of Plentzia and Gorliz may receive pollutants from the Butroe River, the Gorliz WWTP and its overflow discharge points (Figure 3-19) and the port facilities; therefore, they are considered to be subjected to relevant pressures. On the other hand, Muriola receives to a lesser extent the influence of the Butroe, and although it has a small stream coming from the urban

areas of Barrika, which has been in the past responsible for point pollution episodes (Molano, 2014), nowadays is considered to be free of relevant pressures (Table 3-7). The health controls of the bathing waters from 2016 to 2022 suggest excellent conditions (Solaun et al., 2023a, 2023b, 2023c). Only on rare occasions there have been episodes of microbiological contamination by *Escherichia coli* and intestinal enterococci after episodes of heavy rain. Between 2016 and 2022, these limits have been exceeded in 5, 14 and 20 % of the samples collected annually in Muriola, Plentzia and Gorliz, respectively, usually as a result of precipitation, sewage system overflow and spring tides (Solaun et al., 2023a, 2023b, 2023c). The URA considers therefore that only Plentzia and Gorliz have a low risk of microbiological contamination, due to the presence of the Butroe mouth, the streams Txatxarro and Gasatxa, and the discharge point of the Gorliz WWTP, while Muriola has no risk. Additional monitoring suggests that the probability of biological proliferation (e.g., phytoplankton, microalgae, macroalgae, or jellyfish) is rather low or very low. See “*Perfiles de las aguas de baño de las cuencas internas del País Vasco. Revisión 2023*” for more information (Solaun et al., 2023a, 2023b, 2023c).

Figure 3-19. Muriola, Plentzia, and Gorliz bathing areas. Location of the environmental control points (*Puntos de control ambiental*), bathing water quality sampling points (*Control sanitario*), and sampling points of the URA’s monitoring programme for the status of the water bodies (*Punto RED*) in the Butroe-transition. On the map is indicated a drainage scheme (*Red de saneamiento*) and discharge points (*Punto desembaldamiento*) of the urban sanitation network. Image extracted from *Perfiles de las aguas de baño de las cuencas internas del País Vasco. Revisión 2023*. Plentzia (Solaun et al., 2023c).

Another factor altering health is the presence of foreign substances (**allergens**), usually harmless to most people but which can trigger an overreaction of the immune system of others (National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences, 2022). There are many substances that can be allergens such as pollen, fungal spores, house-dust mites and animal epithelial materials. The invasive bush *Baccharis halimifolia*, besides its impacts on biodiversity of sub-halophytic communities, marshes, cliffs and meadows, is also considered an allergenic plant due to the amount of pollen it produces and therefore may have an additional impact on human health (Herrera Gallastegui & Campos Prieto, 2010).

Individual behaviour is also important in shaping human health. It is very related to **psychological assets, physical activity, healthy sleep patterns, and diversity and healthy diets**. Osasun Sarea in Gorniz raises awareness of these healthy behaviours, as well as many other associations (e.g., Goazen UP, the rowing club Arkote Arraun Taldea, etc.), which promote the benefits of outdoor activities for human mental and physical health, as well as the protection and appreciation of the local natural environment. A person's state of health is also greatly influenced by the **microbiome**, which consists of both helpful (symbiotic) and potentially harmful (pathogens) microbes. The disappearance or alteration of symbiotic microbes can have negative consequences for human health and can be a consequence of other factors such as exercise, diets, infectious diseases or medication patterns (National Human Genome Research Institute, 2024). Pathogens have been a health concern in the Bay due to their association with microbial pollution episodes. Although the risk of microbiological contamination is low in all the Bay (Table 3-7), heavy rainfall or episodes of spring tides together with moderate rainfall have been responsible for exceeding the established microbiological limits of *Escherichia coli* and intestinal enterococci, and therefore for a preventive bathing ban in the Bay during several occasions in 2023, 2022 and 2021 bathing seasons (Diputación Foral de Bizkaia, 2024b). Microalgae with toxic potential are another type of pathogen for humans. Many of them have been detected in the area (see Annex Chapter 3-2) and toxicity episodes in the French south-west coast have been reported (Solaun et al., 2023a), however, there is no record of any impact on local bathers (Solaun et al. 2023a, 2023b, 2023c).

3.2.2. Domestic Animals and Wildlife Health

Veterinarian medicine provides access to **animal pharmacology and drugs**. In the municipalities of the Bay, three veterinary clinics attend to domestic animals, two in Gorniz and one in Plentzia. According to the Identification Registry of the Autonomous Community of Euskadi, updated on January 11th 2024, the number of pets between the three municipalities reaches 3,751 registered domestic animals, most of them luxury and company dogs, many felines, eight ferrets and one bird (Table 3-15).

Table 3-15. Pet registry in the Bay of Plentzia. Data from the Identification Registry of the Autonomous Community of Euskadi January 2024, which is monthly updated (Gobierno Vasco, 2024).

	Hunting	Shepherd	Guardianship and defence	Luxury and company	Assistance	Other	Grand Total
Barrika	79	11	28	589	1	3	711
Canine	79	11	28	533	1	1	653
Feline				56		2	58
Gorniz	239	32	68	1433		2	1774
Canine	239	32	67	1199		2	1539
Feline			1	226			227
Ferrets				8			8
Plentzia	145	11	36	1073		1	1266
Birds				1			1

	Hunting	Shepherd	Guardianship and defence	Luxury and company	Assistance	Other	Grand Total
Canine	144	11	36	921			1112
Feline	1			151		1	153
Grand Total	463	54	132	3095	1	6	3751

In the focus area, many stray and feral cats live in urban areas and the surrounding natural environment. This situation led in 2020 to the creation of the association Katu Arima Gorliz - Katu Bihotz Plentzia to implement the Trap-Neuter-Return (TNR) method to control the increase of cats in the feline colonies of the vicinity. The approach is based on sterilisation and aims to promote the compliance of their **daily living needs** and an appropriate **social environment**, providing hygienic feeding, ensuring safe shelter, and promoting a philosophy of social awareness regarding the need for implementation and respect for animals and their habitat.

The areas designated for habitat or species protection also contribute to maintaining the living needs of wildlife. The ZEPA of the Marine Area of the Mundaka estuary - Cabo de Ogoño, which comprises all the marine area in front of Bay (Figure 3-18) and has a total extension of 17,541.98 ha, was designated in 2014 for the protection of the breeding colonies of the European storm petrel (*Hydrobates pelagicus*) and the European shag (*Phalacrocorax aristotelis aristotelis*), established along the rocky cliffs and islets, the latter also foraging in the rather shallow waters of the area. Additionally, it is an area of high diversity of migratory birds, among which stand out the Balearic shearwater (*Puffinus puffinus mauretanicus*) and the Northern gannet (*Morus bassanus*). The Elخالde cliffs, on the left side of the Bay between Muriola and the Butore mouth, are also protected as nesting areas for the European shag (Figure 3-18).

In the hills on the right of the Bay, there is the Wildlife Recovery Center of Biscay, created in 1999, which treats, heals and rehabilitates wild fauna from all Biscay for their subsequent release and carries out an epidemiological control of wildlife and a compilation of genetic archives of threatened species. Diseases in wildlife can involve zoonoses, impact livestock health and hunting production, and may affect wildlife conservation (Diputación Foral de Bizkaia, 2024a). Next to this centre is the Provincial Farm of Biscay, which carries out programmes for genetic improvement and conservation of autochthonous cows, horses and ponies. Regarding farmed animals in the Bay, the Agrarian Census of the Basque Country 2020 identifies 101 cattle, 55 goats, 181 sheep, 49 horses, and 45 bee hives in livestock holdings between the three municipalities (Eustat, 2020). However, the exact location of the farms or the pastures inside the HOBE focus area remain unknown.

Domestic **animals' food security and nutrition** depends on the owners and their economic capacities. On the other hand, wildlife and some non-confined farm animals are more dependent on natural resources, which makes them more vulnerable to alterations in their natural habitat. For example, the already mentioned invasive bush *Baccharis halimifolia*, is known to contain a carotid toxic glycoside that has caused tremors, seizures, diarrhoea, and other gastrointestinal symptoms in cattle in the USA (Herrera Gallastegui & Campos Prieto, 2010). Despite being a widespread shrub in the Basque Country, no cases have been reported, probably because the palatability is low, or the quantity required to cause symptoms is very large (Gobierno Vasco, 2014). However, the presence of this species in the area contributes to an increased risk of food poisoning in grazing animals.

Mortality pressure on wildlife is mainly related to the local fishing activities (e.g., on European squid) since in the area hunting is not allowed. Urbanisation and automobile traffic could also have an impact on wildlife mortality, but no studies or reports of wildlife roadkill cases have been found. Eutrophication poses a pressure on wildlife mortality in many places. However, the good quality status of the waters decreases the susceptibility of the Bay to suffer a eutrophication

episode (Solaun et al., 2018). Since the decrease of ammonium in the 2000s-decade, phytoplankton blooms have become less frequent, and when they occur, it is at the headwaters of the estuary or outside and during spring or summer. However, some potentially harmful species (see Annex Chapter 3-2), which cause negative effects on fish and invertebrates, were detected in the estuary and the adjacent coast in 2021 and 2022, always in concentrations too low to be considered harmful (Borja et al., 2022; Revilla et al., 2023).

3.2.3. Nature's Contributions

More than three-quarters of the area's surface (1761.99 ha) consists of forests, sea cliffs, shrublands, and grasslands. These natural habitats make up 79.87% of Barrika's area, 67.82% of Gorniz, and 64.84% of Plentzia (see Annex Chapter 3-5). In an appropriate health status, these natural habitats should provide **habitat maintenance, formation and protection of soils, and regulation of freshwater quality and quantity**. However, over half of the forested area comprises plantation forests, primarily eucalyptus, used for wood production. According to the Forest Map of the Basque Government these plantations cover 409.62 ha, and are often disturbed by logging, disrupting the ecosystems' regulatory functions (Gobierno Vasco, 2022). Another degraded habitat is the riparian forest; as previously observed, the RQIA indicates inappropriate quality for over half of the upstream margins, suggesting a limited capacity to fulfill regulatory functions. Additionally, only 6.78 ha of riparian forest remain in the Butroe estuary stretch, according to the Forest Map. The introduction of allochthonous species, especially if they become invasive and transformative, also affects ecosystem functioning. In the Butroe estuary, *Baccharis halimifolia*, a North American shrub, has spread along the Cantabrian coast and is considered one of Spain's 20 most damaging invasive alien species (Herrera Gallastegui & Campos Prieto, 2010). The development of its monospecific scrub in saltmarshes alters not only the estuary's physiognomy and diversity but also its structure and sedimentary processes shaping its geomorphology (Ihobe S.A. & Gobierno Vasco, 2014).

Water bodies cover a surface area of 124.71 ha, encompassing the estuary and the Bay, offering crucial marine and transition habitats. These habitats have maintained a good ecological status since the relocation of the Gorniz WWTP outfall and the reduction in nutrient inputs from the Butroe River, particularly ammonia and phosphate. However, the ecological status deteriorated to "moderate" in 2021, due to poor results of macroinvertebrate indicators not only in the outer and middle estuary but also in the inner area, suggesting broader unidentified anthropogenic pressures beyond local activities (Borja et al., 2022). In terms of hydromorphology, the Butroe estuary is moderately altered, occupying only 41.1% (135.8 ha) of its original or potential habitat, with the rest occupied by urban and agricultural structures (Solaun et al., 2023e). Approximately 33.9% of its length is altered by infrastructures such as Plentzia harbour quays, breakwaters, jetties, seawalls, and water canalizations. Additionally, 6.1% of the Butroe surface is isolated, with the Txipio marshland separated by the Barrika-Plentzia road, and the former tidal mill park connected to the estuary through a small gate (Solaun, et al., 2023e). To prevent further habitat degradation, several areas have been designated for flora conservation and restoration efforts (Figure 3-18). The upper estuary hosts the bizkaian endemism *Apium graveolens subsp. butronensis*, whose habitat has dwindled in recent years (Aizpuru et al., 2010). Further downstream there are patches for the recovery of the endangered *Zostera noltii*, where transplantation trials have been carried out (Garmendia, 2015).

Another significant regulating contribution is **climate regulation**, supported by ecosystem processes on a global scale. However, human activity's modification of these processes and subsequent climate change has local-scale effects evident in the Bay of Plentzia. The KOSTAEGOKI project (2022) aims to assess the impacts of climate change consequences, such as mean sea level rise (SLR) and coastal erosion, on the Basque coast under various climatic scenarios. Annex Chapter 3-3 and 3-4 detail the project's findings for the municipalities of

Barrika, Plentzia, and Gorniz, and their respective beaches. Plentzia emerges as the most exposed municipality, with 51.79 ha potentially affected in the worst-case climatic scenario (compared to 22.08 ha in Barrika and 21.86 ha in Gorniz), and the highest percentage of residential area impacted (19.73% versus 3.46% in Barrika and 0.13% in Gorniz). Additionally, with a SLR of 70 cm, the Muriola beach is expected to completely disappear by 2100, while the Plentzia beach would shrink by 60%. The percentage of potentially affected people is higher in Plentzia under present climatic conditions, but in the worst-case scenario of sea level rise, it becomes higher in Barrika by 2100, affecting a total of 9.35% of the population (compared to 7.85% in Plentzia). The study also addresses the economic consequences of climate change on Plentzia municipality, highlighting trade, hotel services, and transportation as the most affected sectors (Annex Chapter 3-4). In the worst-case climatic scenario with a SLR of 1 m, the economic loss associated with tourism at Plentzia beach would amount to 300 million euros (Ihobe S.A. & Gobierno Vasco, 2022).

In the Bay of Plentzia there are also some natural habitats that offer protection in front of **hazards and extreme events**, as the ones just mentioned. One of them are the marshland areas of the estuary, which are Isuskiza (on the upper side), Ostrada (in the middle) and Txipio (next to the Plentzia bridge) (represented in a dark blue in Figure 3-18). During the 19th century, these natural areas were occupied and modified for agricultural purposes, to later be abandoned in the 20th century (Carreta & Duo, 2019). Since then, they have followed an environmental remediation through natural sedimentation processes which has allowed them to partially recover their original environmental functions. The Txipio marshland is the biggest and more controversial of the three, since in the 80s it was threatened by the *Marina de Txipio* Project, which intended to build a macroubanization and a private marina. The construction never took place thanks to the creation of Txipio Bai Elkarte Naturalista, which through awareness-raising activities for the revaluation of the wetland, managed to get the Basque Government to declare it a Special Protection Area in the Territorial Sectorial Plan for Wetlands of the Basque Autonomous Community. Besides giving refuge to many waterfowl and wading birds, and being a fish spawning and breeding area, it also serves as a flood plan in case of extreme flooding events (Carreta & Duo, 2019). This marshland, together with the adjacent margins of the estuary, is considered an ARPSI (Figure 3-18) that can flood during extreme events with a return period of 10 years. The Astondo dunes in Gorniz (Figure 3-18), which is one of the most extensive dune systems of the Basque coast, is also another natural habitat which gives protection, in this case, from coastal erosion. In addition, it is the dune ecosystem with the largest number of vascular plant species, six of them included in the Red List of the Vascular Flora of the Basque Country (Aizpuru et al., 2010; Gobierno de España, 2003).

The water bodies of the Bay of Plentzia and the estuary represent a source for **food and feed** for the organisms of the area and the fisherman, which may sell their capture products to other consumers. The *Ría* was considered a shellfishing area, although it is no longer in use. The area also contains some agricultural activities, mainly grasslands, but also non-citrus fruit trees, herbaceous crops and vineyards. Excluding grasslands, Barrika has the largest surface of agricultural areas (see Annex Chapter 3-5). In this municipality, the Crusoe Treasure Underwater Winery, grows the grapes in one of the vineyards of Barrika, and then uses a submerged cellar to mature their wines, which serves as an artificial reef in the coastal waters off the Bay (Crusoe Treasure, 2022). Another type of **material and assistance** provided by the natural environment in the area is the timber production, historically provided by oak trees of the original natural forest. Currently, many have been replaced by eucalyptus trees (377.80 ha) and pinus (39.99 ha) (2022 Forest Map of the Gobierno Vasco).

In terms of non-material contributions, the Bay itself represents a source of **inspiration and learning**, which is profited by the marine research station of PiE-UPV/EHU (e.g., the HOBE project). The area also contains 21 points of geological interest (Figure 3-18), many on the coastal

cliffs, and some plots of the historic forest of Isuskitza, in the “Abanico de Plentzia”, were restored in 2017 by the children of the Public School of Plentzia (Ayuntamiento de Plentzia, 2017). Additionally, the coastal cliffs and hills in Gorniz are an Area of Naturalistic Interest included in the Spatial Planning Guidelines (DOT) (Figure 3-18), with the objective of preserving its ecological and cultural values.

Table 3-13. Bathing areas description. From Solaun et al. (2016, 2023a).

Bathing areas	Muriola	Plentzia	Gorniz
Municipality	Barrika	Plentzia	Gorniz
General characteristics			
Orientation	E	NW	W
Longitud	45 m	356 m	842 m
Low tide area	5,225 m ²	75,497 m ²	98,302 m ²
High tide area	1,737 m ²	34,135 m ²	78.141 m ²
Urbanization degree	Isolated	Urban	Semi-urban
Influx of bathers	Medium	Massive	High
Access by car	No	Yes	Yes
Bathing water hydrodynamics			
Currents dominance	Astronomical tide and wave breakage		
Waves exposure	Low	Medium-low	Low
Water renewal times	=< 7 days		

The Bay of Plentzia is also a great location for **physical and psychological experiences**. Three beaches constitute three bathing areas: Muriola, Plentzia and Gorniz (Table 3-13, Figure 3-18). On the left side and with an east-wards orientation, the Muriola beach is the smallest and was artificially generated with silica sand from a nearby quarry. It receives less wave energy from the Bay and presents a small stream that flows into the beach itself, coming from the neighbouring urban areas of Barrika. On the other side of the Butroe mouth, there are the Plentzia and Gorniz beaches, separated by a breakwater and the former sanatorium (nowadays PiE-UPV/EHU Marine station) from each other. The first one is classified as an urban beach, and the second one as a semi-urban. Both are surrounded by man-made structures, and care and recreational facilities (Solaun et al., 2023e). They receive a high number of visitors, especially during summer, who come for the many activities developed in the Bay, including recreational bathing, aquatic sports, and touristic tours. The hills surrounding the Bay, of a rather rural character, favour the presence of rural tourism, with rural touristic houses, a camping area in Gorniz, and several hiking trails.

Finally, the coastal landscape of the Bay imparts a **sense of identity** and connection to various local habitats for its residents. This is reflected in the presence of several associations dedicated to the protection, appreciation, and restoration of these ecosystems. Examples include the Txipio Bai association for the protection of the Txipio marshland, the SOS Itsasadarra movement against the construction of docks in the Plentzia estuary, the project Plentziako Herri Lurak for the restoration of forests, the NGO AMBAR for the protection of cetaceans, the mycological association of Plentzia, and the Isuskiza Bizirik neighbours’ association in the *Abanico de Plentzia*, among others.

3.2.4. Socioeconomic Determinants of Health

The local governments of the three municipalities have conducted, or plan to conduct, some participatory processes to understand the citizen’s needs and demands. In 2022, the municipality of Plentzia conducted the *Plentzia Auzoekin Bat*, a participatory process which

included questionnaires and sessions with neighbours and aimed to address various municipal issues in Plentzia. According to the survey, the locals gave the municipality a score of 8.45 as a place to live, with zero not at all satisfied and 10 very satisfied. However, 28,9% of the interviewed citizens believed that the municipality has been deteriorating over the last few years, mainly due to the neglect of the village, dirtiness, and poor management by the authorities (Gizaker, 2022). In 2022, the Barrika town council also announced the realisation of a Sociological study of citizens' needs and demands (Zárate, 2022). However, we have not found the report with the results obtained.

Demographics describe the characteristics of the inhabiting population. While Plentzia is the smallest municipality, it presents the highest population density (Table 3-16). Concerning the population age, the three municipalities present a similar constrictive population pyramid (Annex Chapter 3-6), where most citizens are between 40-65 years old, and the number of young people is lower. The percentage of people aged 65 and over is around 20 % in the three municipalities (Table 3-16). Regarding **race and ethnicity**, more than three-quarters of the population was born in Bizkaia. Most of the remainder comes in roughly equal parts from other Spanish provinces and foreign countries (Table 3-16). This situation differed eight years ago when the foreign population was almost half what it is now. Today, people from other European countries, Maghreb countries, and the rest of Africa, North and South America, Asia, and Oceania inhabit the area. The percentage of foreign population is highest in Plentzia (Table 3-16), and most are from South America and other European countries (Eustat, 2023).

Table 3-16. Population statistics from Eustat (updated 01/01/2023). ^a Note that these statistics refer to the whole territory of Barrila and Gorliz, some of which is not included in the HOBE Focus Area. Plentzia, on the other hand, is included in its entirety.

	Barrika^a	Plentzia	Gorliz^a
Total population	1581	4459	6110
Men	809	2161	2974
Women	772	2298	3136
Density (population/km2)	208.3	759.6	606.2
Population aged 65 and over (%)	22.8	20	20.2
Population origin (%)			
Bizkaia	79.4	78.1	80.6
Araba	0.9	0.6	0.6
Gipuzkoa	1.6	1.1	1
Other Spanish provinces	9.4	8.5	8.6
Foreign born population	8.4	11.7	9.2

Income and **working conditions** are similar in the three municipalities. Compared to the rest of Bizkaia, the three municipalities present a high personal and household income, with Barrika having the highest (Table 3-17). This municipality is also the one that presents the biggest gap between the 20% of the population with the lowest income and the 20% of the population with the highest one. Additionally, women tend to have a lower personal income than men (Table 3-17). The unemployment and occupancy rates are similar between the municipalities and Bizkaia, and in 2021, Plentzia was the only one investing in employment promotion. The results obtained from the citizen survey one year later indicate, however, that people perceive the bad conditions for small commerce as one of the main problems in Plentzia (Gizaker, 2022).

Table 3-17. Average income in 2021 and working conditions in 2022. Statistics from Eustat (updated 2023).

	Barrika	Plentzia	Gorliz	Bizkaia
INCOME				
Average household income	64763	55992	52195	47005
Total average personal income	27571	26830	25671	22944
20% of people with the lowest income	148	214	232	-
20% of people with the highest income	77568	70266	65204	-
Average personal income available	22215	21896	20982	19366
Men	24373	25450	24944	23026
Women	19986	18591	17261	15508
WORKING CONDITIONS				
Unemployment rate	9.8	9.6	9.3	9.3
Occupancy rate	51.9	52.4	53.3	55.8
Municipal expenditure on employment promotion in 2021 (€)	0	74411	0	-

The **political governance** of the municipalities changed with the elections in May 2023. Nowadays, Barrika is governed by the EAJ/PNV, Plentzia by EH Bildu, and Gorliz by the local political party of Gorliz Bizirik. The participatory process *Plentzia Auzoekin Bat* gives a very valuable insight of the citizen's perception of their local government. Overall, they rate the labour of the town council during the previous government of the EAJ/PNV, with a 5 out of 10, being zero not at all satisfied, and 10 very satisfied. 27.1% actively had a bad image of the Plentzia town council. They believe they were mismanaging the municipality; they felt them distant and absent and not listening to the inhabitants. Additionally, the municipality's management of Plentzia during the COVID-19 pandemic was perceived as good by 32.9% of the population, as neither good or bad by 33.4%, and as bad or really bad by 16%, mainly due to a lack of vigilance and the inactivity of the government. Another aspect mentioned in the study of Plentzia is that most of the surveyed population (84.3 %) believes that the town council should unify some services with Gorliz municipality to act jointly and more effectively together (Gizaker, 2022).

The **built environment** is a major factor affecting the quality of health and the experience of wellbeing, and it represents the 18.59 % percentage of land cover in the HOBE Focus Area (SIOSE, 2017). It consists mainly of urban fabric, transportation networks, paved areas and isolated buildings, distributed in six urban centres: two in Gorliz, two in Plentzia and one in Barrika. Most of it is located around the beaches of Plentzia and Gorliz, which facilitates its access and enjoyment, as well as the availability of several services (Table 3-7). Four local roads arrive at the bay: BI-3114 (Sopela to Plentzia), BI2704 (Loiu to Plentzia), BI-2120 Mungia to Plentzia and BI-3151 (Plentzia to Ba). The artificial areas conform to a total surface of 363.70 ha, from which only 12.26 correspond to artificial green areas and urban trees (see Annex Chapter 3-5).

From the study of citizens' needs and demands in the neighbourhoods of Plentzia, the Urban Planning area was one of the greatest concerns to the residents (Ibatuz S.L., 2022). The most commented contributions were the lack of parking, the improvement of the cleaning and gardening service, the repair of pavements and roads in poor condition, and the creation of a cycle lane with an exit through the Butroe. Other projects requested during the surveys were related to the development of the area around the Plentzia metro station, the widening of the Mungia Bidea road, the development of the river, and the provision of mechanical accesses to the Plentzia Old Town and Gatzamine neighbourhood (Gizaker, 2022). The three municipalities have an online platform, Udala Zabaltzen, where the citizens can report incidents or possible improvements on the streets that are afterwards addressed by the local authorities.

Besides the already mentioned public and private health centres, another way of **accessing healthcare**, particularly from the location, is the lifeguards and hondartzaina from the Accident Prevention, lifeguarding and Assistance service of the *Diputación Foral de Bizkaia*. The beaches also have other services that contribute to the safety and security of the users (Table 3-18). Beyond the coast, the perception of safety in Plentzia is rather good. Around 79% of the interviewees feel safe walking alone at night (90.5% male, 67.6% female), and only 33,4% of the interviewed neighbours are concerned about the security in Plentzia, especially those living outside the main urban centres. Although 62.9% do not consider any neighbourhood as insecure, the one that receives a lower safety perception is Txipio (Gizaker, 2022).

Table 3-18. Socioeconomic characteristics of the bathing areas. From Solaun et al. 2023 and Solaun et al. 2016.

	Muriola	Plentzia	Gorliz
Socioeconomic characteristics			
Services	Pedestrian access Information panels Showers, toilets, bins	Vehicular traffic and pedestrian access Informational panels Megaphone system Changing rooms, toilets, sinks, showers-foot wash stations, drinking water sources, Yellow and green bins Assisted bathing	Vehicular traffic and pedestrian access Informational panels Megaphone system Toilets, sinks, showers, showers-foot wash stations, drinking water sources, Yellow and green bins Assisted bathing
Safety Surveillance	Lifeguards (2) Hondartzaina First aid kit Telephone contact with the medical team	Lifeguards (4) Hondartzainas (2) Watchtowers, first aid kit, lifeguard post Rescue quad, boat Telephone contact with the medical team Bracelets for lost children	Lifeguards (6) Hondartzainas (2) Watchtowers, first aid kit, lifeguard post Rescue quad, boat Telephone contact with the medical team Bracelets for lost children
Other services	Distant parking area	Marked bathing area Children's play area Sports area Support area (benches) Bicycle rack Promenade	Marked bathing area Children's play area Picnic area Bicycle rack Promenade
Bathing uses	Bathing, surfing, boogies	Bathing, surf, boogies, canoeing	Bathing, jet skis, canoeing, windsurfing, sailing

The **education** centres in Barrika, Plentzia and Gorliz consist of two kindergartens (Gorliz Haurreskola and Pottoli Haur Eskola), two elementary and primary schools (Gorlizko Ikastetxea and Plentzia Eskola), and a high school (Uribe-Kosta BHI, included in the Scholar Agenda 2030). As mentioned, the local authorities also contribute to organising workshops and seminars about sustainability and health education. From Uribe Kosta, Ekogune offers several courses to promote sustainable development while strengthening the region's identity and consolidating the municipality's Local Agenda 21 processes. In Gorliz, Osasun Sarea organises seminars on practical keys to a balanced and straightforward diet for the elderly and theoretical-practical workshops on CPR (Cardio-Pulmonary Resuscitation). Additionally, the environmental association AMBER has organised courses, workshops, and training talks for the correct collection of data and samples of marine animals.

These activities also contribute to increasing **social connectedness** and promoting the **culture and tradition** of the area. Many of the citizens are organised and participate in associations that focus on different themes: culture, sport, environment, youth, women, neighbourhoods, etc. Each municipality has its magazine, in which it communicates the most relevant news and events, *Barrika Aldizkaria*, *Revista Astillero* of Plentzia, and *Gorliz Aldizkaria*, and in Plentzia there is *Plentzia Telebista (PTB)*, as an audiovisual communication channel.

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